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ABOUT THE JOURNAL

The Journal of Economics, Law, and Society (JELS) is a pioneering academic platform dedicated to the comprehensive exploration of economics, law, and society, with a distinct focus on Islamic economics, banking, and finance. Our mission is to foster interdisciplinary dialogue, cultivate a deep understanding of these interconnected disciplines, and promote the exchange of innovative research to advance both theoretical knowledge and practical applications.

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Contents

Editorial	1-3
Acknowledgment.....	4
Examination of Sukuk Structures in the Turkish Participation Financial System ..	5-19
<i>Burhan Uluyol & Pashtrik Hajraj</i>	
Surah Al-Qalam and the Tragedy of the Commons	21-35
<i>Haris Lloyd</i>	
Islamic Finance as a Crisis-Resilient Framework: Insights from the Global Financial Crisis	37-53
<i>Halima Alisic, Betul Dinc & Anitë Salihu</i>	
Adapting to Change: Financial Institutions Among Bosnian Muslims in the Austro- Hungarian Era (1878-1918)	55-76
<i>Edin Kadric</i>	
Harmonizing Economic Growth with Environmental Justice: Circular Manufacturing Pathway	77-93
<i>Hazik Mohamed</i>	

Editorial

We are pleased to present the second issue of the *Journal of Economics, Law and Society (JELS)*. This issue builds on the foundations laid in our inaugural publication, continuing to explore the critical intersections between economics, law, and societal dynamics. Our aim remains to foster scholarly discourse that bridges diverse disciplines, addressing contemporary challenges with innovative, multidisciplinary approaches.

The second issue features five diverse and thought-provoking articles that contribute to the advancement of knowledge in Islamic finance, economic sustainability, and the historical evolution of financial systems. Each article underscores the journal's commitment to high-quality research and its role as a platform for intellectual exchange.

The first article, ***“Examination of Sukuk Structures in the Turkish Participation Financial System”*** by Burhan Uluyol and Pashtrik Hajraj, delves into the evolving landscape of Islamic finance in Turkey. By analyzing sukuk contracts and their alignment with Islamic economic principles, the study offers insights into the need for a transition from debt-based to equity-based sukuk structures, advancing ethical and sustainable financial practices.

The second article, ***“Surah Al-Qalam and the Tragedy of the Commons”*** by Haris Lloyd, presents a unique integration of Islamic scriptural insights with modern economic theories. Through a detailed exegesis of Surah Al-Qalam, the author draws parallels between Qur’anic principles and contemporary challenges like environmental conservation and public resource management, illustrating how traditional Islamic values can address global issues.

“Islamic Finance as a Crisis-Resilient Framework: Insights from the Global Financial Crisis,” the third article, authored by Halima Alisic, Betul Dinc, and Anitë Salihu, examines the resilience of Islamic financial institutions during the Global Financial Crisis. By emphasizing Shari’ah-compliant practices and their alignment with the real economy, this study highlights the potential of Islamic finance as a stable and equitable alternative to conventional financial systems.

The fourth article, ***“Adapting to Change: Financial Institutions Among Bosnian Muslims in the Austro-Hungarian Era (1878–1918)”*** by Edin Kadrić, offers a historical perspective on the transformation of financial systems in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The study explores how Bosnian Muslims

adapted to European economic paradigms during a period of significant socio-economic transition, providing valuable lessons on the interplay of tradition and modernity.

Finally, “*Harmonizing Economic Growth with Environmental Justice: Circular Manufacturing Pathway*” by Hazik Mohamed addresses the critical balance between economic development and environmental sustainability. By advocating for circular manufacturing principles, the author provides a roadmap for achieving sustainable growth while ensuring environmental justice, underscoring the role of inclusive and innovative policies in overcoming systemic barriers.

As we continue to expand the scope and impact of JELS, we are committed to encouraging interdisciplinary dialogue and fostering research that bridges theory and practice. This issue reflects our dedication to providing a platform for diverse voices and perspectives, advancing our understanding of complex global issues.

We invite our readers to engage with the articles in this issue, reflect on their findings, and contribute to the ongoing discourse through submissions to future issues of JELS. As always, we extend our gratitude to the authors, reviewers, and editorial board members whose hard work and dedication make this journal possible.

We look forward to your continued support as we strive to make JELS a leading academic resource for scholars and practitioners worldwide.

Edib Smolo

Editor-in-Chief

Journal of Economics, Law & Society (JELS)

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Examination of Sukuk Structures in the Turkish Participation Financial System

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ABSTRACT

Following the trends in the world, especially in the Muslim world, where Islamic banking started to emerge, there was a need for Islamic banking in Turkey as well. *Sukuk* is one of the services that has recently become more popular in Turkey due to the legal regulations that enable Islamic banks in the country to issue it and be competitive in the market. This paper tries to examine the applied contracts for the issuance of *sukuk* and recommend some structures by first explaining the path of Islamic finance in Turkey and its services and then *sukuk* regulations and contracts. We find that *murabaha*, *wakalah*, and *ijarah* are the most popular contractual forms among the five approved financial contracts (*ijarah*, *wakalah*, *murabahah*, *mudarabah-musharakah*, and *istisna'a*) by the Capital Market Board of Turkey for the issuance of *sukuk*. As we can see from the *sukuk* structures, the debt-based modes of finance used predominantly in *sukuk* issuance and priced with the same interest-based benchmarks, it seems that the practices of *sukuk* are far from the ideals of Islamic economic principles. Therefore, the *sukuk* issuers should, away from over-usage of debt-based *sukuk*, should move towards more equity-based *sukuk*.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Islamic banking in Turkey is still in the initial developing phase, but the banking sector is generally new. It does not have a long history compared to other European countries. During the Ottoman Empire, the banking sector was not so developed, and most of the banks that were allowed to operate in the late Ottoman Empire were owned by foreigners (Egresi & Belge, 2015). Görmez (2008) states that the first bank of the Ottoman Empire, 'Banque de Constantinople,' was established in 1845 and then followed by other banks in later years. According to him, the purpose of licensing these banks was to make easier money borrowings of the Ottoman Empire from Europe due to the huge expenses of ongoing wars in the empire. Even though the banking sector was not developed in the Ottoman Empire till its late period, it is documented that there were many financial organizations called *cash-waqf* which operated under the principle of interest-free and were created for the purpose of social welfare (Bulut and Korkut, 2019; Saiti et al., 2021). The financial sector in Turkey started to grow as a result of the decision to liberalize the country's economy in the early 1980s (Okumus, 2005). As a result of economic liberalization, the country was opened to the world for new ideas and innovations in respect to finance and all spheres of life. It was the result of this decision that the first financial products based on Islamic law named under Special Finance Houses were introduced to the Turkish financial market.

The process of economic liberalization in Turkey, initiated by the Prime Minister of that time, Turgut Özal, opened the doors for the establishment of interest-free banking by a decree initiated in 1983, which named these banks as Special Finance Houses (SFHs) (Karapinar & Dogan, 2015). Karapinar and Dogan (2015) also point out that the purpose of this initiative was to encourage the cash flow from the oil-rich Middle East countries and also from the domestic market. Asutay (2013) explains that the term ‘bank’ was not used to name these financial institutions or differentiate them from conventional banks. Therefore, SFHs were not under the legal framework of banks, but they were under the rule of the Cabinet of Resolution. They were also affected by the political laicity of the country, so the term Islam was avoided. The SFHs were allowed to operate in Turkey by a government decree number 83/7506 of December 16, 1983, which allowed these institutions to collect funds for investment on an interest-free basis and profit-loss sharing basis (Ali, 2007). The aim of this law was to give opportunity to those who care about Islamic principles and to those who do not invest in conventional banks due to the interest. Thus, with this law, they attracted the money that was under the pillows to bring and invest in the country’s economy. The first SFH opened was Albaraka Turk in 1985, then in the same year Faisal Finans, then in 1989 Kuveyt Turk and other banks like İhlas Finans and Asya Finans were established in the following years (Ozsoy & Yabanli, 2010). The first two SFHs opened were investments from outside Turkey, which shows that the new regulation encouraged foreign direct investment in the country. Especially this new decree encouraged investments from the Middle East and other Muslim investors. Using the advantage of having no interest-free banking in the country, it was a good investment for SFHs and a very profitable business.

Therefore, the number of SFHs increased very fast till the financial crisis in 2001. According to Hayali, Sarili & Dinc (2012), the bad management and fraudulent activities led to the failure of SFHs, especially the bankruptcy of the largest Finance House, İhlas Finance, in February 2001. The bankruptcy of İhlas Finance brought new regulations to strengthen the banking system. Therefore, from December 1999, SFHs became under the Banking Law No. 4389; thus, together with conventional banks, they became under the same legislation that deals and regulates banking activities (Okumus, 2005). Considering the negative impact that İhlas Finance had on deposits, deposits in SFHs became covered by insurance. According to Okumus (2005), this occurred ‘with the Assurance Fund Decree of May 2001, by which current accounts and profit/loss participation accounts of natural persons became defined as deposits to be insured’. The new regulations that made SFHs and conventional banks subject to the same law and under the same umbrella, and by insuring the depositors of SFHs, brought a new scheme of competition in the banking market between these two.

SFHs went through different and very important steps throughout history till they became recognized as banks in 2005. As Egresi and Belge (2015) state in their research, with the banking law No. 5411 in 2005, “special finance house” was replaced with “participation bank”, and both participation and conventional banks operate under the same law. Up to now, ‘participation bank’ is the term used for all Islamic banks whose activities are based on the principles of Islamic Law and based on the interest-free principle. With these changes, participation banks became more competitive, and the doors of rapid increase were opened due to the Muslim population in the country and the interest-free services offered. According to the Bank Association of Turkey 2018 report, currently, there are 6 participation banks operating in Turkey. Since they are operating, they have expanded their activities with different financial services and products and opened new branches all around Turkey.

The paper is organized in the following way: After the introductory section, Section 2 provides an overview of the *sukuk* market in Turkey. Section 3 examines various *sukuk* structures from around the world, while Section 4 focuses on the legal framework supporting *sukuk*. Section 5 analyzes the *sukuk* structures used within the Turkish participation banking system, and finally, Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. THE SUKUK MARKET IN TURKEY

The issuance of *sukuk* in the world has experienced an increase in the number and the amount of issued *sukuk* as reported by the published annual report of the International Islamic Financial Market - IIFM (2020). According to this report, the total global *sukuk* issuance in 2015 was 67.8 billion USD, and this amount continued to increase year by year and it reached its peak in 2019 with an amount of 145.70 billion USD. This was the highest amount of issued *sukuk* since its first *sukuk*. This shows that *sukuk* is becoming more popular among the people and businesses, and also it has become more sophisticated. Due to the pandemic crisis caused by the coronavirus that has covered the whole world, the issuance of *sukuk* has dropped in 2020 to the amount of 139.8 billion USD. The report also shows that the domestic issuance of *sukuk* covers more than the international issuance.

Turkey's journey on *sukuk* started with the first issuance of 100 million USD *sukuk* by Kuveyt Türk Participation Bank on 24.08.2010 after the necessary legal regulations (Sarikatipoğlu, Arif Capkin & Özyiğit, 2015). Then, it has been continued by governmental and other bank issuances. The aim of these regulations that enabled the start of *sukuk* issuance in Turkey was mainly to bring capital to Turkey from other countries, especially from Gulf countries, and to move with the plan of the government to make Istanbul a global center of Islamic Finance. The *sukuk* market has been growing very fast in Turkey, especially in the last few years. Islamic banks in Turkey have a high portion of *sukuk* market share. In addition, they see *sukuk* as a good alternative for collecting funds satisfying the needs of customers, and competing with conventional banks.

As can be seen from [Table 1](#), the first issuance of *sukuk* in Turkish Lira was in 2013, and the total amount of issuance for that year reached 520 million TL. This amount was five times bigger in year 2015, with the amount of 2.5 billion TL. The peak of *sukuk* issuance in TL was in the year 2019, with an amount of 40.4 billion TL, and it slightly decreased to 38 billion TL in 2020. As can be seen, the issuance of *sukuk* in TL has been increasing yearly since its first issuance in 2013, with a slight decline in 2020, which may be due to the pandemic crisis. In addition, [Table 2](#) shows the *sukuk* issuance in USD, and as can be seen, the first issuance was in the year 2010 with the amount of 100 million USD. The USD issuance of *sukuk* in Turkey has fluctuated, and it reached its peak in 2014 with the amount of 1 billion and then declined in the following year. In the last year, considering the pandemic crisis, the amount that was issued was 50 million USD.

Table 1: Sukuk Issuance by Participation Banking Sector (TL)

Year	Amount
2013	520.112.774
2014	870.118.050
2015	2.574.091.000
2016	3.358.613.800
2017	7.208.000.000
2018	20.537.874.047
2019	40.483.695.953
2020	38.027.280.000

Source: Source: Participation Banks Association of Turkey

From [Table 3](#), the total *sukuk* issuance between 2012 and March 2020 can be seen, and the total issuance in TL is above 120 billion TL and around 11 billion USD. Islamic banks have performed much better in domestic issuance of *sukuk*, with 83 billion TL, than the Ministry of Treasury and Finance. But they have performed weaker in abroad *sukuk* issuance with 2.9 billion USD. This table shows that Islamic banks in Turkey are focused on putting their effort to contribute and enlarge the *sukuk* market in the country and to take place among the top issuance countries in the world.

Table 2: Sukuk Issuance by Participation Banking Sector (USD)

Year	Amount
2013	520.112.774
2014	870.118.050
2010	100.000.000
2011	350.000.000
2012	0
2013	500.000.000
2014	1.000.000.000
2015	350.000.000
2016	850.000.000
2017	0

Source: Participation Banks Association of Turkey

Table 3: Total Sukuk Issuance between 2012 - 2020 March

	DOMESTIC (MILLION TL)	FOREIGN (MILLION USD)
Islamic Banks	83.737	2.990
Ministry of Treasury and Finance	36.897	8.000
Total	120.634	10.990

Source: Participation Banks Association of Turkey

3. SUKUK AND TYPES OF SUKUK

Sukuk is the plural name that comes from the Arabic language, referring to financial certificates that can be considered equivalent to conventional bonds (Vishwanath & Azmi, 2009). The singular of *sukuk* is *sakk*, which refers to the English root word cheque, explained as a document that represents the transfer of rights and obligations. *Sukuk* was widely used during the medieval time of Islam for transferring financial obligations derived from trade or business (Ahmed, Islam, Amran; 2019). *Sukuk* is becoming popular among investors, and it serves as a mode by which the ownership of assets is transferred to many investors in the form of securitization (Uluoyol, 2023). AAOIFI defines *sukuk* as “certificates of equal value representing undivided shares in the ownership of tangible assets, usufructs, and services or (in the ownership of) the assets of particular projects or special investment activities.” It is very important to differentiate *sukuk* from company shares and bonds. Shares of a company are of an undefined period of time and represent the ownership in a company, but on the other hand, *sukuk* represents clearly specified assets that are for a defined period of time. With respect to bonds and *sukuk*, bonds generate returns from the debt. However, *sukuk* generates returns based on the assets for which they are issued.

Considering that *sukuk* is a relatively new investment tool and its complexity, there may be many parties involved in the contract, however, Ayub (2007) mentioned the most important parties:

1. The originator or the issuer of *sukuk* – the originator sells the assets to the Special Purpose Vehicle (SPV). They may be governments or big companies that sell their assets and use the generated funds.
2. The SPV is a company or entity created mainly for organizing and managing the issuance of *sukuk*. SPV purchases the asset from the originator and issues *sukuk*, so in this way, funds the purchase.
3. Investment bank – It serves as an agent for collecting funds and leads the agreements against a commission or fee.

4. Subscribers of *sukuk* – these are the parties that invest in *sukuk* by purchasing securities, and these parties may be banks, companies, or individuals.

3.1. Types of Sukuk

3.1.1. Ijarah Sukuk

Ijarah sukuk is one of the most used types of *sukuk* in the world, and from the above list, the first two types belong to the *ijarah sukuk*. *Ijarah sukuk* represents the equal share of ownership of a well-defined underlying asset or service based on the principles of the *ijarah* contract explained in the previous section. This *sukuk* gives the holder of the *sukuk* the right to own the underlying asset, get rent from it, and also dispose of it at any time (Rohmatunnisa, 2008). Ali (2005) has mentioned many important economic aspects of *ijarah sukuk*, like the right and flexibility of lesser to sell the asset; the ownership of the share can easily be moved to another person by selling it. The flow of benefits from the share is not restricted to a specific time of the contract, but it can be at any time depending on the agreed terms. It is not required for the asset to exist at the time of the contract, and also, the contract can be of any time, and it can be combined with the *wakalah* contract as well. Rules and regulations that were explained in the previous chapter in the *ijarah* contract part are valid also for *ijarah sukuk*. At the time of the contract, there should be full knowledge about the asset, price, maturity, and so on. All the details should be clearly specified and mentioned in the contract. One of the characteristics of *sukuk* is that it can be traded in the secondary market, and the same is also true for *ijarah sukuk*. It can be sold in the secondary market without interfering with the lessee's right of use, and the remaining periodic payments are paid to the new holders. In the end, at maturity, there should be a different contract for the repurchase of the asset, and they cannot be mentioned in the same contract at the beginning of the issuance. Kahf (1997) has explained many points which are characteristics of *ijarah sukuk*, like the right of the lessor or the *sukuk* holder to sell the leased asset, as long as it does not prevent the lessee from the usufruct of the asset. The owner can sell or lease the asset independently or collectively with other *sukuk* holders. There is also flexibility in the time of payments of rent, which can be at any time and at any time interval, according to the agreement between the parties. Also, the period of *ijarah sukuk* is not restricted to any period, like short, medium, or long periods. It can be leased for any period as long as the asset remains in existence and can be used as a usufruct.

Figure 1 shows the basic structure of *ijarah sukuk*, and the steps are as follows:

1. The SPV buys the asset from the seller at the request of the customer (lessee), or it may buy the asset directly from the customer.
2. In order to make the payment to the seller, the SPV issues *sukuk*.
3. *Sukuk* holders pay the SPV for the *sukuk* purchases.
4. The SPV distributes the funds to the seller.
5. And the SPV leases the asset to the lessee.
6. The lessee pays regular rental payments to the SPV.
7. The SPV distributes the rentals to the *sukuk* holders.
8. At the maturity, the lessee purchases or repurchases the asset from the SPV.
9. The lessee pays the price of purchasing the asset to the SPV.
10. And the SPV pays the price to the *sukuk* holders.

Figure 1: Structure of Ijarah Sukuk

Source: Authors' own.

3.1.2. Salam Sukuk

As it was explained in the previous chapter, salam is a contract by which money is paid in advance for a commodity to be delivered in the future. For this contract to be valid, all conditions and characteristics of the goods that will be delivered should be clearly mentioned. According to Wilson (2008), salam sukuk is a Shariah-compliant certificate issued for short-term financing, usually for three months, with a defined period of maturity and return when the parties agree to participate in this contract. Compared to other types, Salam sukuk is used for short-term financing. Also, there was debate among scholars about whether it is allowed to trade Salam sukuk in the secondary market, and most of the scholars agree that it is allowed to trade it in the secondary market (Wilson 2004). The basic structure of Salam sukuk is shown in *Figure 2*, and the steps are as follows:

1. The SPV agrees with the issuer for buying commodities issued under *salam sukuk*.
2. The SPV issues certificates of participation or *sukuk*.
3. Investors make the payment to the SPV for certificates.
4. The SPV distributes funds to the issuer.
5. The issuer delivers assets to the SPV at the maturity date.
6. The SPV sells the assets back to the issuer for a higher price than the initial price, or the asset may be sold to another person.
7. The SPV pays the price and the markup to investors.

Figure 2: Salam Sukuk

Source: Authors' own.

3.1.3. Istisna' Sukuk

Istisna' is a financial contract that is made to manufacture goods or commodities, and the payment is allowed to be on the spot for future delivery or to be paid in the future for future delivery. As was mentioned in the *salam* contract, the same is true for *istisna'* with respect to clear specification of terms and commodity characteristics. According to Ahmed, Islam, and Hashim (2020), *istisna' sukuk* are certificates that represent equal value, and the purpose of issuing them is to raise funds for producing commodities or assets that are owned by those who hold these certificates. According to them, the funds from subscribers represent the cost of producing the commodity. This type of Sukuk is very useful for financing huge infrastructures or other kinds of projects. *Istisna' sukuk* can be sold in the secondary market, but they cannot be sold at a different price than the par value because they represent a product that will be produced in the future. **Figure 3** shows the basic structure of *istisna' sukuk*, and the steps are as follows:

1. The SPV issues *sukuk* to raise funds for the project.
2. Investors make the payment and become *sukuk* holders.
3. The SPV delivers money to the contractor or builder to build the asset and to deliver it in the future.
4. When the project is finished, assets are transferred to the SPV.
5. The asset or the project is leased or sold to the end buyer.
6. The end buyer pays for the project.
7. Returns are distributed to the investors or *sukuk* holders.

Figure 3: Istisna'a Sukuk

Source: Authors' own.

3.1.4. Murabahah Sukuk

In the *murabahah* contract section, it was said that *murabahah* is a contract of sale where the bank buys a commodity at the request of the customer and sells it to the customer in deferred payments by clearly mentioning the profit margin as well. On the other hand, *murabahah sukuk* are certificates that represent equal ownership of the asset, and the funds raised by issuing *sukuk* are used for purchasing the asset, thus making *sukuk* holders the owners of the asset (Vishwanath and Azmi, 2009). Vishwanath and Azmi (2009) also state that “*murabahah sukuk* only represents a monetary debt receivable from the client in the form of the *murabahah* price, which is non-negotiable as per the rules of Shari’ah.” Because *murabahah sukuk* represents a monetary debt, they cannot be traded in the secondary market. Since *murabahah sukuk* is based on the *murabahah* financing contract, again, all rules and regulations of the *murabahah* contract apply to *murabahah sukuk*. The basic structure of *murabahah sukuk* is presented in **Figure 4**, and the steps are as follows:

1. There is an agreement between the borrower and the SPV upon the product and the price.
2. The SPV issues sukuk to investors.
3. Investors or sukuk holders pay the money.
4. The SPV, with the money taken from sukuk holders, buys the commodity from the seller or supplier.
5. The supplier delivers the commodity to the SPV.
6. The SPV sells the commodity to the borrower on the spot plus the profit margin, which is known to both parties.
7. The borrower makes regular payments to the SPV.
8. The SPV delivers the payments to the sukuk holders.

Figure 4: Murabaha Sukuk

Source: Authors' own.

3.1.5. Musharakah Sukuk

Musharakah is one of the oldest and most used contracts, which represents the contract where two or more parties combine their forces to complete a project. All parties contribute to the project with capital or land/assets, and the profit/loss shares are defined at the beginning of the contract according to the capital participation in the project. Vishwanath and Azmi (2009) state that *musharakah sukuk* are certificates that show equal ownership issued to raise funds for starting a new project or supporting an existing one. The *sukuk* holders are the project's owners, and these *sukuk* certificates can be traded in the secondary market. Usually, these kinds of projects last from 5 to 7 years, and during this period, the corporation buys shares gradually. In the end, all shares belong to the corporation, and in this way, *sukuk* holders get rid of the shares. Firstly, there is an agreement between the corporation and the SPV, and they agree on the project details, including the participation, profit share, and so on. The corporation also contributes to the project with land or other assets, and the capital is provided by the *sukuk* subscribers. Also, the corporation is appointed as an agent to manage the project, and for this service, they are paid a fee that is separate from the profit-share ratio.

The basic structure is presented in **Figure 5**, and the steps are as follows:

1. The Corporate and the SPV agree to enter into a *musharakah* agreement and agree on the terms and conditions, and the corporate agrees to buy the *musharakah* shares periodically.
2. Corporate contributes to *musharakah* with land or assets.
3. The SPV issues *sukuk* to the investors.
4. *Sukuk* holders make the payment for the *sukuk* shares.

5. The SPV contributes with capital to the *musharakah*.
6. The profit/losses are distributed.
7. The SPV distributes profits to *sukuk* holders and part of the capital.

Figure 5: *Musharakah Sukuk*

Source: Authors' own.

3.1.6. Mudarabah Sukuk

Mudarabah sukuk is a certificate based on the *mudarabah* contract where the capital is offered by one party, and the other party offers efforts and managerial skills for the completion of an existing project or a new one in a pre-determined profit-sharing ratio. According to Vishwanath and Azmi (2009), *mudarabah sukuk* gives their holders the right to get their capital at the end of the project and the annual profit created from the project in the pre-agreed profit share ratio. Again, the same rules and conditions of the *mudarabah* contract are valid and apply to *mudarabah sukuk* as well. The *sukuk* holders or investors are the project's owners, and the project owner is the working partner who spends time and effort on the project. At the end of the project, losses are covered by *sukuk* holders, and in the case of profit, capital is provided to the *sukuk* holders, and then the remaining profit is shared according to the agreed ratio. The basic structure of *mudarabah sukuk* is shown in Figure 6, and the steps are as follows:

Figure 6: *Mudarabah Sukuk*

Source: Authors' own.

1. There is an agreement between the project owner and the SPV on the *mudarabah* contract and all the terms and conditions of the contract.
2. The SPV issues *sukuk* to finance the project.
3. *Sukuk* holders or investors make the payment for participation in the project.
4. The SPV invests the money in the project.
5. At maturity, the project is delivered, or the capital and the profit ratio are delivered to the SPV.
6. The SPV delivers the capital and the profit to *sukuk* holders.

4. DEVELOPMENT OF SUKUK AND LEGAL BASIS

The development of *sukuk* in Turkey started in 2010 with the legal regulations of the Capital Market Board of Turkey (CMB) with the Communiqué Serial III, NO: 43, under the title ‘Principles Regarding Lease Certificates and Asset Leasing Companies’ published in Official Gazette on April 1, 2010 (Ünlü, 2019). This law issued by CMB defined *sukuk* and allowed it to be issued. However, the *ijarah sukuk* was the only type of *sukuk* that could be issued. It was the year 2013 when CMB made some corrections or regulations on the Communiqué related to the issuance of *sukuk*. With the new corrections, there were accepted five forms of *sukuk* can be issued by SPVs separately or in a combined form, which is *sukuk* based on:

1. *Ijarah* contract;
2. *Wakalah* contract;
3. *Murabahah* contract;
4. *Mudarabah-Musharakah* contract; &
5. *Istisna’* contract.

With the recognition of these five forms of *sukuk*, the *sukuk* market in Turkey started to attract investors, and the issuance of *sukuk* increased very quickly. The aim of this regulation, which was made in 2013, was to define the characteristics of *sukuk* and to define the *sukuk* issuing companies or SPVs. The Communiqué on *sukuk* defines each type of *sukuk* and their steps, as discussed and shown in the previous chapter. It also defines the contracts that should be made between the SPV and the other parties.

The *ijarah*-based *sukuk* is defined by the regulation as certificates by which the asset is financed, and the rights on the asset are transferred by the originator to the SPV, so in this way, it is leased to the originator or to the third parties. An agreement must be made between the originator and the SPV for transferring the ownership of the assets to the SPV. In any case of default, the SPV has the power to break the contract of the underlying asset.

The *wakalah*-based *sukuk* is defined as certificates of transferring the income generated from the *sukuk* to the SPV based on the management of the asset or rights as stated in the *wakalah* agreement. In this form of *sukuk* the asset and rights are used for the benefit of SPV. In this type of *sukuk*, an agreement should be made between the originator and the SPB upon the management of the asset without transferring the ownership to the SPV. Conversely, the *murabahah*-based *sukuk* are certificates issued by the SPV for financing the purchase of assets or rights that will be sold at a deferred price, usually to the originator. The assets that are going to be subject to this type of *sukuk* have to be traded in the Istanbul Stock Exchange or other exchange markets.

The *mudarabah-musharakah* *sukuk* are the certificates issued by the SPV in the form of a partnership based on a joint venture. According to the regulation, this form of *sukuk* can be of two types: Where the capital is invested by the SPV and where the capital is invested jointly by the SPV and other partners. On the other hand, the *istisna’*-based *sukuk* are certificates issued for the establishment of a work or a project where the owner of the project is the SPV but for the benefit of the *sukuk* holders or *sukuk* investors.

5. THE SUKUK STRUCTURES USED BY ISLAMIC BANKS IN TURKEY

There are five forms of contracts that *sukuk* issuance can be based on and which are allowed by the Turkish law, and these contracts are *ijarah*, *wakalah*, *murabahah*, *mudarabah-musharakah*, and *Istisna'*. However, when we look at the issuance of *sukuk*, it can be seen that three main forms of contracts are used. These contracts by which *sukuk* issuance is based are *murabahah*, *wakalah*, and *ijarah*. The three governmental banks, Emlak, Ziraat, and Vakıf Participation Banks, issue *sukuk* mostly based on *wakalah* contracts. Albaraka and Kuveyt Participation banks mostly use *murabahah* and *wakalah*, and Turkiye Finans Participation Bank mostly uses *ijarah* contracts in the issuance of *sukuk*. **Figure 7** shows the structure of the *wakalah* contract used by Islamic banks in Turkey to issue *sukuk*.

Figure 7: The Applied Wakalah Sukuk Structure

Source: Authors' own.

The applied steps in the *wakalah sukuk* structure are as follows:

1. The SPV issues *sukuk* to investors and collects funds from them.
2. The SPV delivers several funds to the bank, which operates as a *wakil*.
3. The bank invests the received money in its *murabaha* portfolio and receives profits.
4. The SPV, with the remaining funds, buys commodities (Shari'ah-compliant commodities) on the London Metal Exchange.
5. The SPV sells the commodity to the bank for a deferred payment.
6. The bank sells the commodity on the London Metal Exchange for an immediate payment.
7. The bank pays the face value and the profit to the SPV.
8. The SPV pays the *sukuk* face value and profit to the investors.

The above-shown structure of *sukuk* used by Islamic banks in Turkey is based on the *wakalah* contract, but as it can be seen, it is a combined *wakalah-murabahah* contract. According to the decision made by the Albaraka Turk Participation Bank Shari'ah Board regarding the *wakalah* contract, at least 33% of the funds collected from *sukuk* subscribers by the SPV must be invested in the bank's *murabahah* portfolio. Additionally, up to 67% of the funds can be used to purchase commodities from the London Metal Exchange, which will then be sold to the bank on a deferred payment basis.

The other form of contract used in the issuance of *sukuk* is the *ijarah* contract, shown in **Figure 8**. This form of contract is widely used by Islamic banks not just in Turkey but also in other countries as well. The reason may be that it is easier and the fastest way for banks to achieve fast liquidity. As can be seen from the below-stated steps, there is a sell and buyback application. This form of trade is widely criticized by Islamic scholars because it is not a real trade going on, but it is a way to achieve fast liquidity. The steps applied in this form of contract are as follows:

1. The SPV issues *sukuk* to investors and collects the funds from them.
2. The bank sells the assets to the SPV and gets paid by the SPV.
3. The SPV rents the asset to the bank.
4. The bank makes regular rental payments to the SPV.
5. At maturity, the SPV sells the asset back to the bank and gets the face value of *sukuk*.
6. The SPV delivers the face value of *sukuk* and the profit to the investors.

Figure 8: The applied Ijarah Sukuk Structure

Source: Authors' own.

Figure 9: The Applied Murabaha Sukuk Structure

Source: Authors' own.

The last most used form of contract in the issuance of *sukuk* by Islamic banks in Turkey is the *murabahah* contract. Islamic scholars also criticize this applied form of contract of *murabahah* since

it serves just for raising funds and does not contribute to the real economy. **Figure 9** illustrates the steps in the application of this contract and they are as follows:

1. The SPV issues *sukuk* to investors and collects funds from investors or *sukuk* subscribers.
2. The SPV buys commodities (Shari'ah-compliant commodities, which are usually metals except gold and silver) on the London Metal Exchange.
3. The bought commodity is delivered to the SPV.
4. The SPV sells the commodity to the bank for a deferred payment to be made in the future.
5. Then, the bank sells the commodity on the London Metal Exchange.
6. The bank gets the payment for the sale of the commodity.
7. The bank makes the periodical payments and, at maturity, the face value of *sukuk* to the SPV.
8. The SPV delivers the payments to the *sukuk* holders or investors.

6. CONCLUSION

The concept of Islamic banking in Turkey began in the early 1980s when then-Prime Minister Turgut Özal decided to liberalize the country's economy. Although there had been previous attempts to establish Islamic banks, there was no legal framework to support them at that time. Islamic banking was seen as a way to attract investors from Gulf countries and facilitate the flow of funds from Arab nations to Turkey.

Initially, Islamic banks were classified as Special Financial Houses, and it took time for them to be officially recognized as Participation Banks. Today, there are six Islamic banks operating in Turkey, three of which are government-owned and three are privately owned. These banks provide a variety of financial services and products that operate on an interest-free basis.

Despite currently holding a modest market share of approximately 6%, the future growth potential for Islamic banking in Turkey appears promising. Islamic banks offer a wide range of services and products based on interest-free, and these services are sufficient to fulfill all customers' needs. The new product that is becoming popular among the banks, not just in Turkey but also everywhere in the world, is *sukuk*. *Sukuk* are financial certificates that are similar to conventional bonds, but the main difference is that bonds are based on interest, and *sukuk* are based on real trade or real assets or rights. The first issuance of *sukuk* in Turkey started in 2010 with the legal regulations by which only one type of *sukuk* was allowed to be issued. Later the regulations related to *sukuk* have changed and in total there are five types of *sukuk* that are allowed: *ijarah*, *wakalah*, *murabahah*, *mudarabah-musharakah*, and *istisna' sukuk*. When we check the practice of Islamic banks in Turkey, we can see that the hybrid contract of *wakalah-murabahah* is mostly used, and then also *wakalah* and *ijarah sukuk* are popular.

Recent regulations regarding *sukuk*—covering aspects such as contracts, special purpose vehicles (SPVs), and tax considerations—have paved the way for further development of *sukuk* in Turkey. Data indicates a significant increase in *sukuk* issuance in recent years. This rise in *sukuk* offerings provides Islamic banks with an alternative product to present to customers, featuring higher fixed returns. Consequently, this can help attract new customers and contribute to increasing the market share of Islamic banks.

In recent years, the application and issuance of *sukuk* have significantly increased, effectively serving the purposes of raising funds and providing an alternative financial product to customers, thereby enhancing competitiveness against conventional banks. However, Islamic scholars have

strongly criticized the current methods of *sukuk* issuance, particularly the use of *bay al-'inah* and organized *tawarruq*. For Islamic banks to offer a genuinely Islamic product that is free from doubt, it is essential to eliminate these practices.

As a recommendation from the study, it is evident that the predominantly debt-based modes of finance used in *sukuk* issuance, often priced against interest-based benchmarks, indicate a departure from the core principles of Islamic economics. In other words, the fundamental concept of risk sharing—the heart of Islamic finance—is not adequately reflected in *sukuk* issuances. If *sukuk* issuers rely too heavily on debt-based contracts, they risk disenchanting the general public with Islamic finance. Therefore, *sukuk* issuers should limit their reliance on debt-based *sukuk* and instead transition toward more equity-based options, such as *mudarabah* for governmental or infrastructural projects.

Declarations

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

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Surah Al-Qalam and the Tragedy of the Commons

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines *Surah Al-Qalam* (Chapter of the Pen) from the Qur'an, highlighting its economic and ethical implications through the lens of the 'Tragedy of the Garden' narrative (verses 17–32). The paper challenges traditional *Tafsir* interpretations and draws parallels with Garrett Hardin's '*Tragedy of the Commons*'. Employing the Qur'anic exegesis method *Tafsir-ul-Qur'an bil-Qur'an*, the paper derives authentic Islamic principles such as stakeholder inclusion, sustainability, self-restraint, social responsibility, and cooperation over shared resources. The paper additionally explores contemporary applications of the *Surah*, including environmental conservation, public resource management, and sustainable corporate governance. By integrating modern concepts like game theory and stakeholder theory, the study demonstrates how Qur'anic principles can address current challenges, urging a re-evaluation of classical interpretations to unlock the Qur'an's potential for advancing Islamic economic thought.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This paper conducts a *Tafsir* (exegesis) of the Qur'anic *Surah Al-Qalam* (The Chapter of the Pen) with a particular focus on the story of 'the Tragedy of the Garden' found in verses 17-32.

Unlike classical *Tafasir* (plural of *Tafsir*), this paper seeks to show that the story is comparable with Garrett Hardin's *The Tragedy of the Commons* (1968). As such, the *Surah* calls for the consideration of sustainability, as well as stakeholder and communal rights in economic decision making. Such principles ought also to be embedded in Islamic economics, alongside other principles derived from the story, such as self-restraint, social responsibility, subsistence rights, and cooperation vis-à-vis shared properties.

This paper will begin by exploring the story related to *Surah Al-Qalam* before elaborating on the parallels between it and the *Tragedy of the Commons*. The paper will then elucidate the numerous economic principles that can be derived from the *Surah*, before then applying them to contemporary issues in Islamic economics.

To relate both stories briefly, a group called the 'Companions of the Garden'¹ conspires to harvest all a garden's fruits for their exclusive benefit. But during the night, God destroys the garden. When

1 To avoid confusion in terms, the 'Companions of the Garden' in *Surah Al-Qalam* must be distinguished from the two Gardeners in *Surah Al-Kahf* (18:32-43), and other mentions of 'Companions of the Garden' as referring to the 'Companions of Paradise' throughout the Qur'an more generally (e.g., Qur'an, 59:20). In this piece, when 'Companions' are mentioned, it is only to refer to the 'Companions of the Garden' and not Companions of the Prophet Muhammad, peace be upon him (pbuh).

the Companions arrive, they realize they have been deprived of the garden and its fruits, just as they would have deprived others. In *The Tragedy of the Commons* (Hardin, 1968, pp. 1244) over-herding of animals by individual shepherds causes the degradation of a common pasture. As such, the Tragedy of the Garden mirrors the *Tragedy of the Commons* as the Companions of the Garden set out to maximize their benefit at the cost of others, resulting in the destruction of the common property, much like the shepherds' common pasture.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

*Surah Al-Qalam*² has seen little academic engagement except in the areas of semiotics (Alwi and Parninsih, 2021; Sarlaki and Nazari, 2022) and pedagogy (Muthmainnah, 2021). Despite this, the story contained within the *Surah*, pertaining to the 'Companions of the Garden', relates a parable akin to Garrett Hardin's seminal piece, *The Tragedy of the Commons* (1968), which is an important work regarding sustainability and common property. This Qur'anic 'Tragedy of the Garden', as narrated in *Surah Al-Qalam*, has significant implications for Islamic economics as it similarly calls for considering sustainability, stakeholders, and communal rights.

In *The Tragedy of the Commons*, Hardin (1968, pp. 1244) relates an example whereby the over-herding of a common pasture leads to the pasture's deterioration and, ultimately, its destruction. In this tragedy, the positive marginal utility gained by each herdsman from adding an additional animal to the common pasture encourages every herdsman to add to their herd. The loss to each individual herdsman of adding an additional animal to this pasture is minute. Yet, the accumulative effects of every herdsman doing so result in the degradation of the common land. As such, the unbridled freedom of the herdsmen to do whatever they desire, without consideration of sustainability or the rights of other stakeholders, results in tragedy for the community. That is, the loss of the pasture and, therefore, their communal livelihood and economy.

Stakeholder rights, a key principle derivable from both tragedies, are discussed in the Islamic economic literature. However, they are indirectly derived through other principles such as *Tawhid* (the oneness of God), *Shura* (consultation), *Maslahah* (Public Welfare), 'Adl (Social Justice), *Rububiyah* (direction towards perfection), *Tazkiyah* (purification) (Hasan and Asutay, 2017),³ fairness (Nienhaus, 2003), equitability (Chapra and Ahmed, 2002), property rights, and commitment to contractual agreements (Iqbal and Mirakhor, 2004). This tangentiality leaves a doubt that stakeholder rights and sustainability are not fundamentally Islamic principles, but rather, Islamic economics attempts to mimic laudable principles from conventional economics through its own means. On the other hand, this web of principles can be seen as revealing a stakeholder-shaped lacuna in the foundations of Islamic economics, which requires examination. This paper will show that consideration of stakeholder rights is indeed authentically Islamic, as it is directly derivable from the Qur'an in *Surah Al-Qalam*, thereby providing a solid foundation for the principle in Islamic economics.

The two tragedies also function as a commentary on sustainability. In the Islamic economic literature, sustainability is predicated upon the principles of *Hifz-an-Nasb* (the protection of future generations), *Khilafah* (trusteeship or stewardship of the Earth), *Mizan* (balance), and *Wasatiyyah* (moderation) (Kamali, 2017). This paper will again, as above, provide direct Qur'anic support for this principle through its *Tafsir* of *Surah Al-Qalam*.

Surah Al-Qalam, as discussed in well-known classical *Tafasir*, such as *Tafsir Tabari*, *Tafsir Qurtubi*, *Tafsir Ibn Kathir*, and *Tafsir Ibn Abbas*, is absent in Islamic economic literature. The above *Tafasir*, which rely on statements made by Ibn Abbas and therefore come to the same conclusion, leaves a significant

2 Qur'an, *Surah Al-Qalam*. Available online at: <https://quran.com/68>

3 'Adl, *Rububiyah* and *Tazkiyah* are mentioned with reference to Naqvi (1981, 1994, 2003).

gap for *Surah Al-Qalam* to be explored using different *Tafsir* methodologies that are more acceptable to Shari'ah law applications and, therefore, to *Siyasah ash-Shari'ah* (policy making).

3. METHODOLOGY

In *Tafsir*, particularly the most famous ones (Tabari, Qurtubi, Ibn Kathir, etc.), the Qur'an is often explained through stories. These could be other stories mentioned in the Qur'an, stories pertaining to the *Asbab-un-Nuzul*, i.e., the situation occurring at the time a verse was revealed, or stories pertaining to or narrated by the Prophet Muhammad, (pbuh), (those found in the Hadith literature). These stories are grounded in the primary Islamic sources and are therefore deemed authoritative for the purposes of Shari'ah law.

Other sources of stories, however, are not. Therefore, any story from sources collectively known as *Isra'iliyyat* (i.e., stories of foreign origin, usually from Christian or Jewish sources) or from any other source that does not trace their origin back to the Prophet, (pbuh), or the Qur'an are not considered authoritative for the purposes of Shari'ah law.

The issue with the *Tafsir* on *Surah Al-Qalam*, are that they elaborate the Qur'an using a non-authoritative story. As such, any principles derivable from such *Tafsir* are invalid for the purposes of Shari'ah and, therefore, Islamic economic policy.

An additional issue with the story method of *Tafsir*, is that it distracts from the Qur'an itself, which is dense with information. Rather than relying on external sources, this paper will conduct *Tadabbur* (reflection) of the Qur'an through the Qur'anic text itself, known as *Tafsir-ul-Qur'an bil-Qur'an* (Bhutta, 2018). Utilizing this method means that any principles derived from such a reading are authoritative for the purposes of Shari'ah and, therefore, *Siyasah ash-Shari'ah* (policy making). It also means that the principles derived are authentically Islamic, as they are derived from the Qur'an and not foreign sources. As such, the method employed provides a concrete foundation for Islamic Economic principles.

Once this method has been employed, the derived principles can be compared to other stories, such as Hardin's *Tragedy of the Commons*, to elucidate their meaning for contemporary economic applications.

4. ESTABLISHING STAKEHOLDER AND COMMUNAL PROPERTY RIGHTS IN SURAH AL-QALAM

In *Surah Al-Qalam*, the Tragedy of the Garden involves a group that conspires to take all the fruits from a garden during the early morning hours. Various English translations of the Qur'an describe this group as the 'Owners of the Garden'⁴ and frame the moral of the *Surah* in a light similar to *zakat* (charitable alms - tax), whereby the poor have rights within the wealth of the rich.

Such translations are flawed, as they fail to account for the behavior and statements of the Companions of the Garden. These aspects, as will be explored, clearly reflect that they are not the owners of the property (i.e., the Garden) outright.

In my reading, as I will elaborate further, the Garden can be seen as communal property. That is, as a common, where the local population has equal rights to the fruits of the Garden. Hence, the story has similarities to the *Tragedy of the Commons*, whereby over-extraction leads to the destruction of the commons and the unraveling of local economies. This reading entails a Qur'anic substantiation of communal property rights, sustainability, and stakeholder rights.

⁴ See translations by Dr. Mustafa Khattab, Abdul Haleem, Mufti Taqi Usmani, Abul Ala Maududi, Marmaduke Pickthall, Maulana Wahiduddin Khan, Dr. T.B. Irving, and others.

The translations, however, are rooted in longstanding *Tafsir* traditions and, therefore, deserve an explanation regarding their origin. Such traditional understandings of the *Surah* are founded on the narrations of Ibn Abbas, a Companion of the Prophet, (pbuh), who equates a story to the events of this *Surah*.

According to Ibn Abbas,⁵ a generous man of Ethiopian origin, living not too far from the city of Sana'a in Yemen, would donate a portion of his harvest every year to the poor. However, after his passing, his sons wished to retain the Garden's produce for themselves exclusively, to the detriment of the poor. Hence, the sons conspired to harvest the fruits of the Garden under the cover of darkness so that the poor could not ask for their subsistence at the time of harvest.

While an interesting story, the narrations rely primarily on the statements of Ibn Abbas despite initially appearing to be more diverse. False diversity is a common issue in *Tafsir*, whereby once a story appears in one *Tafsir* it then appears in subsequent *Tafsir* (e.g., Ibn Abbas to Tabari to Ibn Kathir), thereby making the story appear more authoritative than it is. Similarly, a story may be narrated by various authors but originate with the same person, even if that person is not named, thereby making the sources appear more diverse than they are. In this case, the story of Ibn Abbas reaches these *Tafsir* through Sa'id bin Jubayr, As-Suddi, and the more removed Hanad bin Al-Sari, all of whom are named in these *Tafsir* in relation to the story but rely on Ibn Abbas either due to a direct connection in being his student or indirectly as they are known for narrating his collection of Hadith (statements of the Prophet, (pbuh)).

The issue that arises from this is that Ibn Abbas was known not only as a prolific collector of Hadith but also as a collector of *Isra'iliyyat* (stories of foreign origin, usually from Christian or Jewish sources). Such sources are not recognized as authoritative for the purposes of Shari'ah law, despite being potentially useful in contextualizing otherwise uncontextualized Qur'anic verses in the *Tafsir* literature.

Here, it is important to note that none of the narrations of this story connect it to the Prophet Muhammad, (pbuh), but merely narrate it as a story, which is then connected to the *Surah* through Ibn Abbas. As such, this story, while a fitting example, is not necessarily *the* story narrated in *Surah Al-Qalam*, but a story that Ibn Abbas likely believed to be the best fit according to the stories available to him at the time.

This desire to find and record explanations for verses, despite an accurate and reliable one not always existing, is a common feature in early Islamic works, as exemplified by the infamous *Book of Idols* by Hisham ibn al-Kalbi. The problem thereafter is that these sources are treated as reliable and authoritative in traditional works but are more recently being found to be unreliable, thereby creating a clash with the existing and highly regarded literature.⁶

As a general note, it is important to raise the issue of attributing particular stories and details to Qur'anic stories, which are not themselves derived from the text itself nor the statements of the Prophet, (pbuh). In the case of *Surah Al-Qalam*, the story of Ibn Abbas distracts from the underlying Qur'anic message.

It is crucial, therefore, not to become attached to the story narrated by Ibn Abbas as *the* story or to get lost in its details. I will, however, briefly provide the reasons why I do not believe Ibn Abbas's story to be correctly attributable to *Surah Al-Qalam*, and in addition, some benefits stemming from Ibn Abbas's story, nonetheless.

5 Variations of this story are narrated, but rely primarily on statements by Ibn Abbas, and can be found in *Tafsir Tabari*, *Tafsir Qurtubi*, *Tafsir Ibn Kathir* and the eponymous *Tafsir Ibn Abbas*.

6 See Al-Jallad (2022; pp.2-4).

In *Surah Al-Qalam*, the ‘Companions of the Garden’ are literally called ‘Companions’. In the narration of Ibn Abbas, the ‘Owners of the Garden’ are all brothers. Yet, the Qur’anic narrative, which ought to be the most accurate (from a theological viewpoint), does not call them the ‘Brothers of the Garden’ or the ‘Family of the Garden’ or the ‘Inheritors of the Garden’, but instead ‘Companions’, which implies no familial or blood relations, but rather a friendship.

Furthermore, when the Companions arrive at the destroyed Garden, they believe they must be lost.⁷ The possibility of getting lost on the way to the Garden implies that the Garden is far from the homes of the Companions. Therefore, it is unlikely for them to be the owners, as owners traditionally live near the property that they own.

Hence, this paper utilizes ‘Companions’ of the Garden (which is the more literal translation) rather than ‘Owners’ of the Garden, which is the choice of translators relying on Ibn Abbas. Additional reasons why ‘Owners’ is not appropriate shall be presented later.

Nevertheless, for those who are staunchly attached to the narrations of Ibn Abbas, I shall elucidate the benefits of such an interpretation. Firstly, it encourages farmers to feed the poor at the time of harvest, which is also encouraged in *Surah Al-An’am*,⁸ thereby preserving the subsistence rights of the poor. Secondly, *zakat*, which is paid to the poor (by those free of need), is also due on agricultural assets. As such, Ibn Abbas’s story fits in well with the duty of giving to the poor (*zakat*), which is commonly attested to in the Qur’an and *Sunnah* (the practices of the Prophet Muhammad, (pbuh)).

Having said this, the rights of the poor reflected in *Surah Al-Qalam* are not exclusive to the interpretation of Ibn Abbas,⁹ and therefore, the notions above are not lost in my interpretation. Despite the concordance of Ibn Abbas’s story with other Qur’anic notions, these notions are substantially reflected elsewhere in the verses on *zakat*, *sadaqah* (general charitable giving), and feeding the poor. The nuance and lesson of *Surah Al-Qalam*, however, is unique, as it has implications for communal and stakeholder rights, not just the rights of the poor.

This can be elucidated by establishing the ownership rights of the Garden. In verses 17-18 of *Surah Al-Qalam*, the Companions make an oath to themselves that they will harvest all the fruits of the Garden in the early morning. Verses 23-24 then state that once they had gathered in the early morning and were traveling as a group, they whispered to each other so that no poor person would awaken and thereby take fruit from the garden (or otherwise obstruct the group or possibly alert the locality).

The details of these verses substantiate two things: that there was secrecy involved and that the poor had recognized the right of access to the Garden (even if this was merely customary).

Crucially, property owners have no need for secrecy, as they have full rights to pluck the fruits of their orchards in plain daylight. Secondly, if this was indeed private property, then the poor could not simply enter the Garden and take fruits for themselves. As such, these Companions cannot be owners of the Garden in its fullest sense.

Due to the recognized rights of the poor to access the Garden, the Garden could be considered common land, with equal access for members of the locality. Alternatively, the Garden might have belonged entirely to the poor or have been established as a *waqf* (a trust) for their subsistence.

While the poor’s access rights to the Garden might have been considered customary (or even a kind of pre-Islamic *zakat*) as per the Ethiopian who fed the poor in Ibn Abbas’s story, this notion does

7 Qur’an, 68:26.

8 Qur’an, 6:141.

9 Qur’an, 68:24.

not substantially support the idea of the Garden being private property. If such a norm did exist and the Garden was indeed private property, then the poor could have approached the owners of the Garden after seeing a harvest had taken place (as evidenced by the absence of fruits). Furthermore, it can be deduced that the Garden was not enclosed, which would obstruct the viewing of its fruitlessness, as the poor could enter it freely, hence the worries of the Companions.

As such, the secrecy of the Companions would be unnecessary or absurd if they were indeed the owners of the Garden, as their identities would already be known. The implication of their secrecy, therefore, is that the identities of the Companions were not known, as they had no prior association with the Garden through private property entitlements.

As such, the Garden could be considered common land, whereby the Companions have some right to the fruits of the Garden but would nevertheless be transgressors by taking the entirety of the harvest. This is because the rights of the poor are clearly substantiated, and therefore, the Companions cannot be the exclusive owners but must share this Garden with the poor. Alternatively, if the Garden had been established as a *waqf* for the subsistence of the poor, then the Companions would be outright thieves, as they have no right to the Garden at all.

Verse 32, however, implies that the Companions also had some right to the Garden, as the term 'to exchange' or 'to substitute' implies ownership or some right in the original item exchanged. In this sense, the Companions of the Garden can be likened to 'Shareholders,' 'Stakeholders,' or 'Rightsholders' in the Garden, but not as the 'Owners' in absolute terms.

The translation 'Owners' is problematic as it masks the existence of other stakeholders and the explicit rights of the poor as substantiated in the *Surah*. As such, I conclude that the Garden was a common garden due to the absence of absolute ownership, with equal rights for all members of the locality.

5. COMPARING SURAH AL-QALAM TO THE TRAGEDY OF THE COMMONS

It is important to highlight the incredible character arc contained within the story. The Companions begin as conspirators in transgression, undertaking to deprive the poor of the fruits they are entitled to by taking all the fruits for themselves. Perhaps the Companions intended to hoard the food and sell it at a higher price (something which is prohibited in the Shari'ah¹⁰), or perhaps they had no consideration for the food reaching the poor whatsoever.

Either way, when they see the Garden leveled and realize that they have been deprived of the fruits of the Garden, they can empathize with the poor, whom the Companions would have deprived themselves. The Companions remark that they are 'wrongdoers'¹¹ and 'transgressors',¹² thereby acknowledging the rights of others to the Garden that they would have usurped and the wrong that they would have caused these other stakeholders.

The Companions also acknowledge they should have glorified God,¹³ perhaps implying that by appreciating God's blessings through the Garden and the rights of the other creations of God (i.e., human rights), the Companions would have taken only what they needed, leaving the rights of others intact.

The Companions then repent, hoping for a better garden. They have resolved to do better, either in the case of another common garden which they will look after or in general, such that they will

10 Qur'an, 9:34. For further detail on Shari'ah and hoarding see Ghazanfar (2003, p.62).

11 Qur'an, 68:29.

12 Qur'an, 68:31.

13 Qur'an, 68:28.

behave in the hope of the Gardens of Paradise. Indeed, the end of the *Surah*, which functions as a commentary on the story, states that it is the God-fearing that will have the Gardens of Delight.¹⁴ Thus, the Qur'an establishes benefits in this world and rewards in the next life for protecting stakeholder rights.

The remainder of the *Surah*, in conjunction with its introduction, admonishes the pre-Islamic Makkans, particularly the ruling Quraysh elite, concerning how they and people in general cannot and should not do whatever they want without limit or consideration. As the story shows, such behavior leads to deprivation, whereas it is the respect for others' rights that earns true benefit and bliss.

Without the otherworldly promises of eternal bliss. This *Surah* similarly parallels Hardin's *The Tragedy of the Commons*, where the unbridled freedom of individuals conducting themselves without concern for the well-being and rights of others leads to the destruction of communal livelihoods. Thus, the liberal freedom to do whatever one wants must be tempered by the republican freedom from arbitrary infringements upon people's rights.

At the same time, Hardin (1968, p. 1224) sees the *Tragedy of the Commons* as a rebuttal against Adam Smith's 'invisible hand,' which implies that aiming toward one's individual benefit inevitably leads to the greater social good. As exemplified by *Surah Al-Qalam*, such selfishness results in neither benefit for the self nor the wider society.

As Hardin realizes, however, preventing the *Tragedy of the Commons* has imperfect solutions, of which he identifies at least seven. I shall discuss these in relation to Islamic principles:

- **Privatization, Allocation of Rights, and Taxation:** Despite taxation (i.e., charging for access) being one of Hardin's favored solutions (1968, p. 1247), it is problematic as it is 'coercive' (as recognized by Hardin), and because it restricts access for the poorest, as they are least able to pay such taxes. One of the morals of *Surah Al-Qalam* is to protect the rights of the poor. Thus, such a solution is Islamically problematic. Furthermore, privatization and allocating access rights similarly restrict access to various stakeholders. This, again, goes against the moral of the *Surah*, which entails open access and equitable use of the commons.
- **Appeals to Conscience, Statutory Law, and Administrative Law:** Hardin (1968, p. 1246) finds appeals to conscience to be a 'double bind', as voluntary participation in self-restraint still leaves open the possibility for others to destroy the commons through their selfishness instead. Thus, some form of regulation is required to ensure societal compliance. For Hardin (p. 1245), however, statutory law is not sufficiently nuanced to deal with issues of the commons, thereby entailing that such regulation must be dealt with by administrative law. Such a law is problematic for Hardin as it is liable to corruption (p. 1246). In Islamic contexts, administrative law would be akin to the system of *hisbah* (regulation), which, despite being predicated on moral uprightness (Ghazanfar, 2003, pp. 62-64), became rife with corruption during the 10th century onwards (Floor, 1985, pp. 60-62). This does not eliminate the possibility for *hisbah*; however, it implies that limits must be placed on it, and an anti-corruption bureau must be established to prevent its abuse.
- **Abandon the Commons:** Finally, Hardin (1968, p. 1248) suggests abandoning the concept of commons altogether. For Hardin, relinquishing rights to the commons is necessary, as the commons cannot handle the high populations that the world sustains today. Needless to say, *Surah Al-Qalam*, by insisting on the protection of commons, does not espouse this solution.

14 Qur'an, 68:34.

If such solutions are Islamically unacceptable, then an acceptable one must be present for *Surah Al-Qalam* not to be self-defeating. Fortunately, *Surah's* solutions can be elucidated through the relationship of the tragedy of the garden to the Makkans.

The relation of the story in *Surah Al-Qalam* to the Makkans and verse 28 about the glorification of God provides an interesting dimension due to the Makkan control over the Sacred Masjid al-Haram (regarded as the House of God). This Haram has public access rights, so pilgrims may enter and pray. Thus, while managed by the Makkans (particularly the ruling Quraysh tribe), they did not own it. Instead, it is being owned by God.

In settings such as Ethiopia, traditions such as Church Forests still exist today (Emergence Magazine, 2020; Dodds, 2021), and this tradition may relate to when the *Surah* was revealed through the Muslim emigrants to Abyssinia who would have been familiar with such gardens. As such, the Garden in the story may have been a literal 'Garden of God.' Such gardens usually have subsistence rights for the poor or other forms of public access rights.

Therefore, verse 28 of *Surah Al-Qalam* may pertain to the notion that the Companions should have protected the Garden's sacred nature and refrained from violating it. Of course, from an Islamic perspective, the entire Earth can be considered sacred and the property of God, with common rights to all of mankind embedded within. Thus, the *Surah* has wider implications.

For the Makkans, the *Surah* acts as a warning and commentary regarding their custodianship of the sacred Haram and the Zamzam spring, which they ought not to monopolize for private benefit or to the exclusion of others (i.e., the Muslims, as was the case at the time), but should instead manage as communal property (or a *waqf*), with the rights of all protected. Failure to uphold these rights could lead to their deprivation, as can be concluded from *Surah Al-Qalam* and the story of Thumamah ibn Uthal.

Thumamah ibn Uthal was the Chieftain of the Banu Hanifah, formerly allied with the Makkans against the Muslims and one of the largest tribes in Arabia. Thumamah became Muslim after having been captured on his way to Makkah for *Umrah* (the lesser pilgrimage). After converting to Islam and being released from captivity, he and his tribe continued to Makkah for *Umrah*, but received death threats by the Makkans in the Sacred Haram for having become Muslim. This threat of violence was a clear violation of the sanctity of the Haram. In response, Thumamah's tribe cut off Makkah from all trade arriving via the Najd region, causing a serious famine in Makkah and resulting in the leader of the Makkans begging the Prophet Muhammad, (pbuh), for a reprieve, which was then granted (Qadhi, 2023, pp. 293-295). Thus, *Surah Al-Qalam* was particularly prophetic in relation to the Makkans at the time of the Prophet, (pbuh).

Nevertheless, what this reveals is the power of norms. Such norms are socially enforced and can be a powerful tool for enforcing equal access to the commons, as exemplified by the story of Thumamah ibn Uthal. In an Islamic setting, such norms are also imbued with a religious significance as they stem directly from the Qur'an (regarded as the literal word of God). Thus, such norms also carry the penalty of otherworldly punishment for their infringement and can thereby aid in conscientious self-regulation despite the possibility of others infringing upon the commons to one's own detriment. This otherworldly component, which Hardin's secular paradigm could not recognize, importantly reframes the value equation for violating the commons. Even if another group were to violate the commons, despite one's own self-restraint, the short-term benefit may be towards the violators, but the long-term benefit (which includes the afterlife) would be for the selfless.

Worldly violations, however, must also be resolved, as not all persons in even a nominally Islamic society may be God-conscious. Thus, the institution of hisbah is important. However, as previously

mentioned, such an institution must itself be regulated and corruption punished. Indeed, the Qur'anic prescription for corruption is incredibly severe.¹⁵

The Qur'anic solution to the *Tragedy of the Commons*, as presented in *Surah Al-Qalam*, is the best solution as it does not lead to the enclosure or the privatization of the commons. These two solutions were historically enacted in feudal and capitalist economies, significantly reducing public access and benefit (Standing, 2019, ch.1). The Qur'anic response instead preserves the notion and existence of common property itself. Indeed, the enclosure of commons would produce the same result for other stakeholders as if the Companions had been able to take all the fruits for themselves. It is not the optimal or ethical outcome and results in monopolization.

Instead, *Surah Al-Qalam* encourages personal restraint through reflection upon divine providence and the rights of God's creation. The divine origins of common property rights and stakeholder rights more generally create a divinely sanctioned norm that ought to be socially and legally enforced if not self-enforced. Where management is required, as alluded to by referencing the Makkans' control over the Haram, restraint is also encouraged so that the common property is not usurped and so that the rights of all stakeholders are protected and preserved equally. Where it is not (i.e., where corruption persists), strong rectification is required through the legal system (i.e., the Shari'ah courts).

6. ISLAMIC ECONOMIC PRINCIPLES FROM SURAH AL-QALAM

Surah Al-Qalam, through the Tragedy of the Garden, espouses several important principles for Islamic economic theory:

- (1) **Protection of Stakeholder and Subsistence Rights:** The *Surah* establishes the existence of communal property rights, the rights to the poor for subsistence, and, therefore, the concept of stakeholder rights more generally. Thus, Islamic economic policies ought to ensure that they consider all stakeholders in their implementation and ensure the rights of all groups are protected if not adequately compensated for.
- (2) **Encouragement of Social Responsibility and Self-Restraint:** The *Surah* calls for personal restraint despite the opportunity for personal gain, especially when it comes at the expense of others. Such responsibility and restraint help reduce harm to communal assets and wider society (reducing negative externalities). *Surah Al-Qalam*, therefore, provides the foundation for an authentically Islamic Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) framework.
- (3) **Encouragement of Inclusivity, Cooperation, and Open Access:** The notion of the commons, as established in the *Surah*, entails that inclusivity and open access to public or communal goods, particularly for the poor, ought to be developed and maintained. In non-state sectors, the notion of the commons, which repudiates the notion of the 'invisible hand', also invites communities to engage cooperatively to provide services for all and encourages the formation of cooperatives more generally. Here, societal benefit is obtained not through individual self-interest but through social cooperation.
- (4) **Encouragement of Sustainability:** The degradation or destruction of communal assets due to their over-use or abuse entails the need for sustainable policymaking and practices. This can also be seen as an extension of Stakeholder Theory, as future generations can also be considered stakeholders despite not being present today. Ensuring that assets are managed sustainably means that these assets can be used to benefit society over a longer period and, therefore, contribute to a flourishing economy.

15 Qur'an, 5:33

7. CONTEMPORARY APPLICATIONS OF SURAH AL-QALAM

Having established the above Islamic economic principles through the lessons of *Surah Al-Qalam*, this section outlines several contemporary issues where these principles can be applied:

- (a) **Management of the Commons vs. Norms-Based Solutions:** Common land with open access can become seriously deteriorated if over-extraction of resources occurs. The English solution has been privatization or enclosure (Standing, 2019, ch.1). However, this is exactly the behavior that the story in *Surah Al-Qalam* deplors, as it deprives the poor and others of access to the common resource. Management of the commons by the government, local authority, or *waqf*, is a potential alternative. However, management structures for common land are necessarily inefficiencies themselves, as they require maintenance resources, which are taken from the commons or recouped by charging for access to the commons (which thereby restricts access). A successful example, however, is the National Trust in the UK, which manages over 500 properties through charging entry and membership fees.¹⁶ On the other hand, *Surah Al-Qalam* relays a morals and norms-based dimension to commons management. Indeed, historically, common land had rules and norms associated with them that helped maintain order. Protection of the commons by enforcing these rules, rights, and norms via the legal system, even as retrospective justice, ought to be sufficient, provided that the commons and their norms are sufficiently local (Ostrom, 2015, Ch.6). Furthermore, by educating on communal rights, social equality, and human rights, the mentality and upbringing of over-extractors can be reduced.
- (b) **Awqaf (plural of waqf):** The *Surah* has implications for *waqf* properties and common land due to the common features between these. *Awqaf*, which is set up for specified beneficiaries, ought not to be usurped in favor of the private benefit. Furthermore, *awqaf* should be managed sustainably such that the property is preserved to benefit its intended beneficiaries in perpetuity, as *sadaqah jariyah* (i.e., perpetual charity). Usurpers of *awqaf* ought to be prosecuted due to the significant corruption and deprivation this causes to the wider society and economy. However, significant effort also needs to be placed in educating and training *waqf* managers (Bachri et al., 2024), with additional emphasis on how to sustainably invest and protect their assets from local economic shocks (due to historical *awqaf* being invested primarily in local assets).
- (c) **Mosques and the Sacred Haram:** Mosques, despite being originally constructed through human effort and funding, function like *awqaf* and Common land, as they have been designated as God's property with open access rights for His worshippers. The rights of all Muslims to these properties must be preserved fairly and equally. Therefore, Muslims should not be prohibited from Mosques, nor should Mosques be made places of profiteering. The Masjid Al-Haram, being particularly central to Islam due to the *Hajj* (the greater pilgrimage), does require some limitation of attendees and significant management due to the millions of Muslims who desire to attend, and the resultant strain on the locality and the environment this causes (Abonomi et al., 2022). Despite this, such management and limitation must be conducted fairly, equitably, and apolitically (Bianchi, 2017).¹⁷
- (d) **Water and Fuel Rights:** Rivers, seas, and even underground deposits of oil and gas do not necessarily obey the rules of international borders. As such, these waterways and deposits are international commons or, at the very least, involve multiple owners. *Surah Al-Qalam* shows that Muslims should respect the rights of others in shared property.

16 See the National Trust website here: <https://www.nationaltrust.org.uk/>

17 While I disagree with the reforms proposed in this article, it nonetheless highlights issues in the management of the *Hajj*, particularly regarding vulnerable groups and quotas.

Indeed, in Islam, water and fuel are considered commons, alongside pasturing grounds.¹⁸ Thus, depriving others of access to such resources or unfairly over-extracting from the common resource is against the Shari'ah. Thus, countries such as Turkey, Syria, and Iraq, which share the common waterways of the Tigris and Euphrates, should not prevent water from reaching other nations by blocking the river with dams or by over-extracting the water for national agricultural use, such that the river has run dry by the time it hits Basra in Iraq (Khalid, 2020). Such pressures on water access inevitably lead to water conflicts and gross deprivation. Similarly, those with shared gas fields, such as Qatar and Iran, should share such resources equitably and amicably, as is fortunately the case (Kamrava, 2017). As such, the *Surah* has international implications for Muslim countries. Muslim states should cooperate with each other, particularly in relation to common resources, setting up agreements and institutions to manage them sustainably for the common interest and thereby preventing destitution and war.

- (e) **Environmental Rights:** Pasture for grazing is considered common land; however, the entirety of nature can be considered similarly. Many nations around the globe have national reserves and parks, some of which cross national borders, which is particularly beneficial as many animals are then free to roam uninterrupted, preserving the natural ecosystem. The planet, including the air we breathe, the waterways, and the soil, are to the common benefit of mankind. Pollution of such resources harms a significant number of people, and therefore, the environmental commons must be protected and over-extraction prohibited. Climate change is a clear consequence of violating the environmental commons and has devastating consequences such as widespread droughts and famine (Devi, 2022). Pollution of the waterways can cause outbreaks of disease and pandemics (Qadri and Faiq, 2019), and the pollution of the soil can similarly harm health. As such, Muslim countries and governments should cooperate and enforce regulations that preserve the environmental commons rather than promote policies that only further their national interest against the rights of others.
- (f) **Government Property and Public Land:** Government-owned properties and land, including natural resources, should be used for the common benefit of the public. This is because the public is a stakeholder in these properties, holding rights within them. The land could be rented out to provide income for public services, but this must be done prudently, and the privatization or enclosure of public and common land should be avoided. This is because it reduces or eliminates stakeholders' and future generations' access to these properties. Furthermore, privatization can lead to negative impacts on sustainability due to poor investment in long-term infrastructure in favor of short-term benefits to shareholders, as in the case of UK water and sewerage companies (Usher, 2023). Unfortunately, corruption is also a significant possibility in the public land management space (Nguyen and Nguyen, 2023). As such, corruption ought to be prevented by an independent bureau for state accountability and transparency with sufficient oversight over public asset management.
- (g) **Communal Rights, Consultation, and Compensation:** To ensure justice, decisions should always be made with consideration of local stakeholders and the rights, both individual and communal, of the people that it would affect. Unilateral action, despite often being superficially conducted in the name of the greater social and economic welfare, should not be permitted, as this will inevitably infringe on the rights of those affected. Indeed, decisions ought to be democratic and consultative (Kamali, 2013, pp. 157-158). Furthermore, compensation must be made to stakeholders for any detriment caused to them, even in the presence of greater societal benefit.

18 Hadith in *Sunan Ibn Majah*, graded *Sahih*, Available online at: <https://sunnah.com/ibnmajah:2473>

- (h) **Maqasid Al-Shari'ah (Objectives of Islamic Law):** The Objectives of Islamic Law are often framed in relation to individual needs or rights, particularly *Hifz-Al-Mal* (the Protection of Wealth). *Surah Al-Qalam*, however, highlights the need to view the *Maqasid* from a societal perspective also. Therefore, shared, common, public, and communal property rights must also be protected under *Hifz-Al-Mal*. Sustainability is also a key consideration for protecting the use of future generations' wealth (particularly the environmental commons). This sustainability is important to consider as Lineage (*Nasl*) is another objective of Islamic Law, alongside preserving Life (*Nafs*), Religion (*Din*), and the Intellect (*'Aql*). Promoting public health through spending on hospitals or educational campaigns can also be seen as societal implementations of the *Maqasid* regarding the Protection of Life (*Nafs*) and Lineage (*Nasl*). Similarly, the promotion of public education can be viewed as preserving the Religion (*Din*), and Intellect (*'Aql*). These broader perspectives regarding the objectives of Islamic Law are important for the renewal of Islamic economics and for adapting Islamic policy-making to contemporary concerns.
- (i) **Corporate Governance and Sustainability:** Societal rights and commons, including the environment and public health, must be protected. Corporate governance, therefore, needs to account for all stakeholders in its decisions and for any negative externalities and social impacts it may have, such that it does not infringe upon any collective rights or needs. Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) concerns are a key part of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). For Islamic businesses to fulfill the teachings of *Surah Al-Qalam*, they must engage in this ESG approach to CSR, which is already a key feature in conventional business practice. Fortunately, there are a variety of CSR models available in the Islamic Economic literature, with further models being developed for Islamic Banks (Hanic and Smolo, 2022).
- (j) **Prisoners' Dilemma, Game Theory, and Cooperation:** *The Tragedy of the Commons* and the Tragedy of the Garden are examples of Poundstone's Prisoners' Dilemma (1992). Two prisoners can choose to cooperate, providing mutual benefit for both; one can defect, thereby increasing benefit to themselves at the cost of the other, or both can choose to defect, causing both serious harms. Regarding the commons, competition between stakeholders inevitably leads to the destruction of the commons, or individual transgressions can deprive others of their rights. Thus, the sustainable situation is one in which all users of the commons cooperate with one another. This cooperation, or *ta'awun* in Arabic, is a key and positive feature of Islamic economics (Farooq, 2019). A cooperative game theory approach can be applied as part of the Islamic economic method and Islamic policy making. By examining Islamic economic law in this light, it can be more appropriately applied to contemporary issues.
- (k) **Cooperatives:** In banking, defection (i.e., non-cooperation in game theory) is often represented by risk-shifting through fixed-return products (usually those bearing interest) or defaults. A less defective model would be inspired by cooperation through products that utilize profit-and-loss sharing or through cooperative banks. This cooperation, or *ta'awun*, is a key feature of Islamic economics and the foundation of cooperative banking (Farooq, 2019). Thus, Islamic cooperative banking is an important avenue for the sector to explore. Cooperative models have also been used successfully in the housing sector to provide affordable rents and can be further supported by state policy (Ferreri and Vidal, 2021). Thus, cooperatives could become a key tool in providing affordable goods and embedding communal rights.
- (l) **State Spending:** The state treasury can be considered as a public asset or commons. Despite being managed by the government, the funds are derived from the people's wealth (via taxes) and, therefore, should be spent to their benefit. Spending in a way that only benefits some groups to the exclusion of others or usurping public funds for personal

benefit would be contrary to the message espoused in *Surah Al-Qalam*. Unfortunately, many Muslim-majority countries, as exemplified by Pakistan, spend state funds to asymmetrically benefit some groups over others, such as their militaries or elites (Kırşanlı, 2024). Ensuring anti-corruption bureaus are sufficiently empowered, as well as the presence of strong institutions that protect the rule of law, such as independent judiciaries, are essential to prevent corruption. Using public funds both responsibly and sustainably is important for a country's economic success, and state spending should seek to maximize its effectiveness by planning for the long-term and most universal effect rather than planning for short-term, political, or personal gains.

- (m) **Zakat and Subsistence Rights of the Poor:** Despite putting emphasis on communal rights, *Surah Al-Qalam* also espouses the rights of the poor to subsistence. A key institution that ensures food security is *zakat*, as evidenced by the success of *zakat* funds in Malaysia (Abdul Manap, 2019). *Zakat* is, unfortunately, underutilized and under-collected, with few Muslim states collecting *zakat* centrally. *Zakat* has significant potential and must be explored as part of Islamic economic policy.

8. CONCLUSION

Surah Al-Qalam is one of the more accessible *Surahs* for readers due to its linearity. This accessibility is similarly espoused by the *Surah*, alongside preserving stakeholder rights, social responsibility, and sustainability. The Qur'an's narrative of the Tragedy of the Garden has significant implications for Islamic economics and international relations, highlighting the optimality of restraint and the importance of sustainability and cooperation.

While the implications of *Surah Al-Qalam* in these policy areas have only been discussed in a summarized form, further elaboration should be undertaken on these issues from a Game Theory, Maqasid, and Stakeholder Theory perspective to further the application of Islamic economic teachings to ameliorate Islamic policy making. Fortunately, significant inroads have already been made in the arena of Corporate Social Responsibility. However, resolving the issue of corruption is a significant roadblock to fully implementing Stakeholder Theory in various Muslim-majority countries, with more needing to be done to strengthen judicial institutions.

Nevertheless, another lesson of this paper is that the reinterpretation of the Qur'an, considering developments and insights since its revelation, can elucidate hidden and important meanings that have been buried under the historical guesswork of its earliest interpreters. These early works should be commended for their efforts and insights but should not be viewed as the only possible interpretations or the most authoritative without proper investigation and consideration of alternatives. Failing to conduct such reinterpretation locks the full potential of the Qur'an and, therefore, the full potential of Islamic economics behind the assumption that improvement is impossible. It is upon the shoulders of giants that humanity has achieved its current successes, but this success is equally due to those who built upon and revised the efforts of those who came before.

Importantly, such re-examinations, as advocated above, allow for the re-embedding of Islamic values into contemporary Islamic economic theory, which often appears to mimic contemporary conventional practices. Future research should re-examine the Qur'an for those areas in Islamic economic theory that appear to be less substantiated (or tangentially so) from an Islamic viewpoint. This will provide an authentic foundation for Islamic economics and a framework of Qur'anically derived principles that can guide Islamic policy making. Further research should also be conducted on utilizing norms, game theory, and cooperatives as methods for Islamic policymakers so that Islamic economics might be better implemented.

Declarations

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Islamic Finance as a Crisis-Resilient Framework: Insights from the Global Financial Crisis

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ABSTRACT

The Global financial crisis (GFC) or “the crisis” exposed significant weaknesses within the global financial system, largely stemming from financialization activities. This research paper explores the potential of Islamic finance (IF) principles to prevent financial crises while offering a more stable and equitable financial framework. A qualitative approach was adopted, involving interviews with various professionals in the IF field to explore the ethical and practical distinctions between conventional finance and IF. Key findings reveal the resilience of Islamic banks during the crisis can be attributed to their adherence to Shari’ah principles, which prohibit interest (riba), excessive uncertainty (gharar), and speculative activities (maysir). The study emphasizes the advantages of asset-backed financing and profit-sharing models, which align financial activities with the real economy, thereby fostering long-term stability. By highlighting the practical benefits of the ethical framework underpinning IF, this research contributes to the broader discourse on financial crisis prevention.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In July 2007, as the world stood on the brink of a major financial crisis, Citigroup CEO Charles Prince famously remarked, “When the music stops... things will get complicated. But as long as the music is playing, you’ve got to get up and dance” (Nakamoto & Wighton, 2007). This statement epitomized bankers’ awareness of their unsustainable practices, as well as their disregard for the risks associated with such behaviors, which ultimately culminated in the Global Financial Crisis (GFC). Financial crises have become increasingly frequent. Stiglitz (2003) notes over 100 crises in the preceding 35 years. Some of these crises have had catastrophic consequences. One such example is the GFC, which was triggered by a housing bubble and left the world questioning how it could have occurred. Initially, the crisis was attributed to regulatory failures, complex financial products, unethical behavior, and excessive risk-taking (Melvin & Taylor, 2009; Helleiner, 2011). However, other research links financial crises to interest and inflation (Crotty, 2009; Kennedy, 1995). The collapse resulted in bankruptcies, widespread job losses, and a multi-trillion-dollar bailout (Lewis et al., 2010; Acharya & Richardson, 2009; Coffee, 2009).

Historically, Abrahamic religions have either restricted or outright prohibited the charging of interest (usury) (Looft, 2014). However, only Islam continues to enforce such a prohibition today. Interestingly, Islamic banks were shown to be less affected by the crisis, suggesting their principles might offer greater financial stability (Baber, 2018; Al-Zumai, & Al-Wasmi, 2016; Farooq & Zaheer, 2015; Hussien et al. 2019; Elasrag, 2010; Diaw, 2015; Kaye & Hassan, 2011). Consequently, Islamic

banking has emerged as a credible alternative to conventional banking, gaining recognition and expanding globally (Ahmed, 2010). Islamic principles, such as the prohibition of interest and promotion of ethical investment, could reduce the severity and frequency of financial crises by instilling greater discipline within the financial system (Hassan & Kayed, 2009).

This paper examines the potential of IF as a viable alternative to conventional finance in fostering economic stability and resilience against future financial crises. Specifically, it investigates how IF principles, which operate under a distinct set of ethical guidelines and regulatory frameworks, might provide a more stable financial environment than conventional finance. This study aims to identify key features that could shield economies from similar downturns in the future. To conduct this investigation, a qualitative case study approach is employed, drawing insights from both existing literature and primary data collected through interviews. The research includes professionals from Islamic banks in Bosnia and Herzegovina and Qatar—two regions with active IF sectors that provide relevant perspectives for this inquiry. Additionally, perspectives from an IF expert and a member of a Shari'ah Supervisory Board (SSB) are incorporated to provide a comprehensive view of IF principles in practice. This qualitative approach facilitates a nuanced exploration of how IF operates under stress, particularly when conventional financial institutions face instability.

The central research question guiding this study is: How do Islamic financial principles contribute to financial stability and resilience, as demonstrated during the Global Financial Crisis? By addressing this question, the paper explores the structural and ethical foundations of IF and assesses its practical effectiveness in crisis prevention. Understanding the mechanisms that contributed to the resilience of IF during the financial downturn can provide valuable insights into its role in promoting a more resilient global financial system.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the literature on financial crises and IF, Section 3 outlines the methodology, Section 4 presents the results and discusses the findings, and Section 5 concludes with implications for future financial systems.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

IF is rooted in the principles derived from the Quran and the Sunnah, collectively known as Shari'ah, or Islamic law (Hussain et al. 2016). While Islamic banking was fully implemented only in the last century, its theoretical origins date back to the seventh century (Iqbal & Mirakhor, 2013; Kahf, 2003; De Jonge, 1996). IF gained momentum in the mid-20th century, with its first practical implementation through Egypt's "Mit Ghamr Savings Bank," which avoided interest (riba) and focused on profit-sharing (Siddiqi, 1981; Lewis & Algaoud, 2001). The establishment of the Islamic Development Bank in 1973 further accelerated the global expansion of Shari'ah-compliant financial institutions (Ahmed, 2009). Currently, the global IF industry has experienced significant growth, with assets surpassing \$3.3 trillion in the first half of 2023 (Sambidge, 2023). The industry continues to expand at an annual rate of approximately 10%, a trend projected to persist through 2024 (Damak, et al., 2023; Sambidge 2023). IF's resilience, especially in the aftermath of the GFC, has further solidified its relevance (Kayed & Hassan, 2011).

2.1. The Financial Crisis of 2008

The GFC, extensively studied with over 14,800 articles in Scopus, is often described as the most severe economic crisis since the Great Depression (Helleiner, 2011; Lewis et al., 2010). Triggered by the burst of the U.S. housing bubble, the crisis led to widespread mortgage defaults, severely impacting financial institutions heavily exposed to risky and speculative financial products such as mortgage-backed securities (MBSS) and collateralized debt obligations (CDOs) (Helleiner, 2011).

These products were globally traded, spreading the crisis across borders (Helleiner, 2011; Acharya & Richardson, 2009; Wignall & Atkinson, 2009).

A critical issue was the reliance on over-the-counter (OTC) derivatives, privately negotiated between buyers and sellers. This lack of transparency masked substantial hidden risks (Helleiner, 2011). Speculative, complex, and non-transparent financial products lay at the core of the crisis (Coffee, 2009; Helleiner, 2011; Nelson & Katzenstein, 2014; Chapra, 2008; Hassan & Kayed, 2009; Ahmed, 2010).

Deregulation and regulatory failures exacerbated the crisis. Self-regulation frameworks allowed banks to underestimate risks and increase leverage through off-balance-sheet entities (Acharya & Richardson, 2009; Coffee, 2009; Helleiner, 2011; Wignall & Atkinson, 2009). Misaligned incentives, fueled by equity-based compensation, encouraged short-term gains and high-risk behavior motivated by greed (Coffee, 2009; Acharya & Richardson, 2009; Wignall & Atkinson, 2009; Stiglitz, 2003; Nelson & Katzenstein, 2014; Lewis et al., 2010).

The primary causes of the crisis were regulatory failures, speculative financial products, and greed (Wignall & Atkinson, 2009; Jickling, 2009; Lewis et al., 2010). The crash resulted in a global recession and widespread bank insolvencies that necessitated a \$2 trillion bailout (Luo & Wang, 2023; Helleiner, 2011; Coffee, 2009; Acharya & Richardson, 2009). To prevent future crises, enhanced regulation and a greater focus on ethics have been recommended (Franzoni & Allali, 2018; Lewis et al., 2010). This paper explores how IF, which aligns with these recommendations, could serve as an alternative approach.

2.2. Islamic Finance for Crisis Prevention

IF provides a distinct approach to financial management, emphasizing ethics and risk-sharing as tools to prevent financial crises. The GFC, characterized by excessive risk-taking and speculation, exposed the vulnerabilities of conventional finance (Acharya & Richardson, 2009; Jickling, 2009). In contrast, IF prohibits practices such as *riba*, *gharar*, and *maysir*, all of which contribute to financial instability (Usmani, 2002). Scholars argue that IF, adopted more broadly, could serve as a global alternative to conventional finance, reducing the likelihood of crises (Aglionby, 2009; Chapra, 2008; Kayed & Hassan, 2011).

By requiring that financial transactions be tied to tangible assets and real economic activities, IF reduces speculative activities and prevents asset bubbles from forming. For example, Warde (2010) observed that IF institutions demonstrated resilience during the GFC due to their adherence to these principles. Additionally, profit-and-loss sharing (PLS) ensures fair risk distribution between investors and entrepreneurs, promoting stability.

However, practical implementation remains a challenge. Critics like El-Gamal (2006) and Hassan & Kayed (2009) argue that certain IF products, such as *murabahah*, mimic conventional financial instruments, resembling interest-bearing loans rather than genuine risk-sharing investments. Such products technically comply with *Shari'ah* but fail to uphold the ethical principles that provide stability. This reduces the potential benefits of IF, emphasizing the need for products that align fully with Islamic principles.

Iqbal and Miakhor (2011) highlight that IF's risk management framework addresses moral hazards and conflicts of interest that contributed to the crisis by emphasizing transparency and accountability. However, the absence of standardized regulatory frameworks leads to inconsistent product structures, weakening the distinct advantages of IF (Khan & Bhatti, 2008). To enhance its efficacy, international standards must be established, and product design must prioritize authentic Islamic principles.

The comparative resilience of Islamic banks during the GFC, attributed to conservative lending and avoidance of speculation, supports the potential of IF to prevent future crises (Siddiqi, 2009). However, this resilience may also be due to factors like smaller size and limited global exposure.

Elasrag (2010) clarifies that Islamic finance is not an entirely separate financial system but a framework designed to structure financial transactions so they remain closely connected to real economic activities. By focusing on tangible assets and ethical considerations, IF counters the effects of financialization, which prioritizes short-term profits over long-term stability (Davis & Kim, 2015). As a result, IF promotes long-term economic sustainability (Melvin & Taylor, 2009).

Interest in IF has grown beyond Muslim-majority countries since the GFC. As financialization reshapes economies, the demand for ethical and stable financial systems has increased. Non-Muslim countries like the UK, Luxembourg, and Hong Kong are adopting IF practices to enhance financial stability (Warde, 2010; Wilson, 2009). However, integrating IF into conventional systems requires regulatory adjustments and addressing socio-political barriers such as Islamophobia. The success of IF depends on developing Shari'ah-compliant products that meet diverse market needs (Hassan & Lewis, 2005).

In summary, IF offers a promising framework for preventing financial crises through ethical behavior, risk-sharing, and transparency. However, its effective implementation requires standardized regulatory frameworks and an authentic application of Shari'ah principles. Future research should focus on governance and regulatory enhancements to solidify IF's role in promoting global financial stability.

2.3. Financialization

The GFC is often attributed to the excessive financialization of the economy and the rampant securitization of debt. Financialization, defined as the increasing dominance of financial motives, markets, actors, and institutions in shaping the economic landscape, has profoundly impacted economic and social systems (Epstein, 2005; Davis & Kim, 2015). This shift fueled economic instability and amplified systemic risks, as evidenced by the widespread use of derivatives and mortgage-backed securities during the crisis (Sawyer, 2013; Freeman, 2010; Lapavistas, 2011; Lucarelli, 2012; Deutschmann, 2011; Plys, 2014). These financial instruments, while innovative, severed financial transactions from the real underlying economy, leaving the financial system vulnerable to systemic shocks.

Critics argue that financialization fosters a culture of short-termism and speculation at the expense of long-term productive investment, exacerbating global inequalities and stalling productivity growth. The shift from real economic activities to financial activities has been widely criticized for contributing to income inequality and forming financial bubbles (Tridico & Pariboni, 2018; Miah & Suzuki, 2015; Davis & Kim, 2015). Financial institutions, driven by profit maximization, have prioritized speculative activities over supporting real economic growth. For instance, the principle of maximizing shareholder value, highlighted by Lazonick and O'Sullivan (2000), has driven corporate downsizing and cost-cutting measures, worsening income inequality and marginalizing workers.

Securitization, an enabler of financialization, involves bundling illiquid assets like mortgages into tradeable securities, amplifying risk across the financial system (Davis & Kim, 2015). While it can improve liquidity and diversify risk under ideal conditions, its misuse—evident in the subprime mortgage market—introduced significant systemic vulnerabilities. By allowing financial institutions to offload risk from their balance sheets to global investors, securitization obscured accountability and transparency. Subprime mortgages were securitized into complex instruments, leading to widespread overvaluation and eventual market collapse (Acharya & Richardson, 2009).

The GFC exposed the dangers of over-reliance on financial markets and weak regulatory frameworks, prompting calls for stronger financial regulation and exploring alternative economic models (Tridico & Pariboni, 2018). The systemic failures prompted calls for stronger financial regulation and exploring alternative economic models (Davis & Kim, 2015). IF offers a robust counter to financialization by grounding financial transactions in tangible assets and prohibiting speculative instruments.

IF principles explicitly ban *riba*, *gharar*, and *maysir*, creating a framework prioritizing equity, risk-sharing, and transparency (Ahmed, 2011). These principles act as a natural regulatory mechanism, ensuring financial activities contribute to productive economic outcomes while avoiding the systemic risks inherent in financialized systems. Studies, such as Chapra (2008), emphasize that adherence to IF principles can curb speculative and high-risk financial activities, mitigating the risks of financial crises. By focusing on ethical, asset-backed transactions, IF promotes long-term stability and sustainability, offering a viable alternative to the destabilizing effects of financialization.

2.4. Ethical finance and Corporate Social Responsibility theory (CSR)

Carroll (2009) defines Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) as the ethical responsibility of businesses to develop policies, make decisions, and undertake actions that benefit society while balancing the interests of various stakeholders, including employees, customers, suppliers, communities, and shareholders. Since its emergence in the mid-20th century, CSR has evolved significantly, transitioning from focusing on basic philanthropic activities to becoming an integral component of corporate governance and strategic management (Carroll, 2009). Carroll's work stipulates that CSR encompasses both ethical and business dimensions, serving as a reflection of a company's commitment to operate responsibly beyond mere compliance with laws and regulations (Carroll, 2009).

Carroll's CSR pyramid provides a hierarchical view of corporate responsibilities, with economic obligations forming the foundation, followed by legal, ethical, and philanthropic responsibilities (Carroll, 1991). While economic responsibilities remain primary, other scholars stress the ethical dimension of CSR, arguing that corporations bear inherent ethical responsibilities that extend beyond profit generation (Berkey, 2021). Berkey (2021) highlights the significant impact corporations have on individuals' economic and social conditions, suggesting a strong overlap between business ethics and political philosophy. This reinforces the idea that CSR should not be limited to voluntary actions but should also include ethical obligations that promote justice and social well-being.

The GFC serves as a stark reminder of the consequences of neglecting ethical principles and CSR in corporate decision-making. Characterized by unethical behaviors such as a lack of transparency, excessive risk-taking, and exploitative practices, the crisis revealed systemic risks associated with prioritizing short-term gains over ethical accountability. A significant aspect of the crisis was the interest-bearing loans. Looft (2014) critiques such practices, noting that borrowing money at interest without risk-sharing creates an exploitative relationship, particularly disadvantaging vulnerable borrowers.

The GFC underscored the importance of robust ethical frameworks and CSR in financial institutions, highlighting the need for policies that ensure fairness, reduce inequalities, and promote accountability (Carroll, 2009). By incorporating these principles, businesses can mitigate systemic risks and foster a more equitable financial system.

IF principles inherently align with CSR by prioritizing ethical investments, social welfare, and community well-being—key aspects of CSR (Hanic & Smolo, 2023). The ethical obligations embedded within CSR and IF serve as a counterpoint to financialization (Miah & Suzuki, 2015). IF practices, such as PLS and asset-backed financing, discourage speculative behavior while aligning with CSR goals of equitable and sustainable business practices. By requiring financial transactions to be tied

to real economic activities, IF fosters stability and promotes societal well-being. Therefore, IF not only addresses systemic risks but also operates as a form of institutionalized CSR, promoting ethical business practices as part of its foundational framework.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research approach

This study employed a qualitative case study approach with an inductive methodology to explore the role of IF in crisis prevention in interest-based economies. Unlike quantitative research, qualitative research focuses on words rather than numbers, making it ideal for examining complex, subjective, and nuanced issues that are not easily measured or quantified (Bell et al., 2019). While extensive literature exists on IF's role in financial crises, the qualitative approach allowed for a deeper investigation into how Islamic principles intersect with conventional economic dynamics to enhance resilience. This approach allowed us to investigate how Islamic principles intersect with economic dynamics, offering insights into crisis resilience. Using an inductive approach allowed the researchers to remain open to new ideas that emerged during data collection, which was crucial for capturing novel perspectives. Throughout the process, care was taken to minimize researcher bias and maintain objectivity throughout the analysis by asking neutral and non-leading questions.

3.2. Research Design

A case study of the GFC was conducted to determine whether IF offers a viable alternative for crisis prevention. This approach facilitated an in-depth examination of real-world experiences, making it ideal for understanding the complex dynamics of financial crises (Bell et al., 2019). Semi-structured interviews were chosen as the primary data source to gain detailed insights, complemented by secondary data from existing literature.

Data analysis was carried out systematically to ensure validity and reliability. Once collected, the data was organized using axial coding to identify relationships between themes, facilitating a nuanced analysis. Recurring themes from the interviews were compared with themes from the literature to ensure consistency and accuracy.

3.3. Data Collection Method

The study focused on IF institution's operational during the GFC. Participants included representatives from two banks, one in Bosnia and Herzegovina and another in Qatar. Additionally, one member of an SSB from the Middle East and a financial expert based in Poland were interviewed, bringing the total number of participants to seven. To preserve anonymity, respondents are referred to using generic identifiers throughout the analysis. Data collection was carried out through semi-structured interviews via Zoom. Participants were selected based on their extensive experience in IF, with all respondents having at least 10 years of professional expertise, including during the crisis. Open-ended questions were employed to encourage diverse perspectives and in-depth insights, with the interview questions provided in the appendix. All interviews were recorded with consent and transcribed for accuracy. Snowball sampling was employed to identify additional participants, broadening the range of expert opinions.

3.4. Data Analysis

Transcriptions were done using AI software and carefully proofread to ensure accuracy. The data was categorized systematically into themes and subcategories to facilitate in-depth analysis. Axial

coding was used to identify relationships between themes, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the data.

3.5. Validity and Reliability

Validity reflects the accuracy and truthfulness of the study's findings, ensuring the research measures what it intends to measure (Bell et al., 2019). Semi-structured interviews, while effective for gathering detailed insights, have limitations as they rely on respondents' statements and recollections. These recollections may sometimes be influenced by subjective interpretations, potentially introducing bias. Bias could, in turn, reduce the validity of the results. To mitigate this risk, data collected from interviews was cross-referenced with secondary sources, such as books on IF, official guidelines, and previous studies. Thus, the method of cross-examination through triangulation was used to enhance the accuracy of statements (Bell et al. 2019). Triangulation improves the robustness and validity of results, allowing the researcher to identify consistencies and inconsistencies across different sources by integrating multiple perspectives, methods, and sources of data to cross-validate findings, thereby minimizing the risk of bias or error that may arise from any single method, which can often be subject to specific limitations or researcher biases (Erzberger & Perin, 1997; Hammerton & Munafò, 2021). This approach minimized the risk of bias or error from any single method, strengthening the empirical foundation and credibility of conclusions.

Although semi-structured interviews are less reliable than structured ones, reliability was enhanced through the consistent use of an interview guide and inter-observer consistency during data coding. Each researcher independently coded the data, and then compared results to identify and address discrepancies, ensuring that findings were consistent.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The interviews provided valuable insights into the stabilizing role of IF principles in mitigating financial crises. A systematic analysis of the transcripts revealed recurring themes, including the importance of ethical and asset-backed financing, which contrasts with the speculative practices in conventional finance that contributed to the GFC. Interviewees emphasized the role of profit-sharing and risk-sharing models in IF, which promote stability and equitable wealth distribution. Transparency, accountability, and adherence to Shari'ah principles were also highlighted as crucial for fostering trust and resilience in financial institutions. Most participants concurred that if IF principles had been implemented globally, the GFC could have been averted. They further emphasized that integrating IF principles into the global financial system could create a more resilient and stable economic landscape. This section presents and discusses these findings.

4.1. Integrating IF Ethics into CSR: Advancing Ethical, Transparent, and Sustainable Financial Practices

The findings underscore the ethical framework of IF as a critical component aligning with CSR principles. IF's integration of ethics into financial practices surpasses CSR's often voluntary and self-regulatory nature (Claassen, 2015). Unlike CSR, which may result in superficial compliance without substantive impact, Islamic ethics mandates obligatory adherence to principles such as transparency, fairness, and social welfare, making these non-negotiable elements of financial transactions. These principles provide a compelling counter-narrative to the financialization and rampant securitization that were central to the GFC. Furthermore, this embedding of ethics addresses gaps in traditional CSR approaches, ensuring that ethical considerations are an intrinsic part of financial decision-making.

Participants emphasized key prohibitions in IF, including those against *riba*, *gharar*, and *maysir*, as well as involvement in harmful industries. These principles were repeatedly linked to reducing speculative activities and promoting financial stability. For instance, one interviewee noted that the prohibition of *riba* anchors financial transactions in real economic activities, mitigating speculative risks and preventing debt-driven financial crises. Similarly, the elimination of *gharar* fosters transparency and trust in financial contracts. As one participant highlighted, “By eliminating excessive uncertainty, IF promotes transparency and trust in financial transactions, which are key to maintaining financial stability.” These findings align with prior research suggesting that IF principles promote fairness, transparency, and social justice, fostering a more resilient and equitable financial system (Smolo & Mirakhor, 2010; Siddiqi, 2006).

The analysis also highlighted the role of asset-backed financing as a critical differentiator of IF. By mandating that all transactions be tied to tangible assets, IF reduces speculative behaviors and excessive risk-taking, fostering stability and mitigating risks associated with unregulated securitization (Miah & Suzuki, 2015). Participants observed that this requirement grounds financial activities in real economic value, aligning with sustainable development goals. As one interviewee remarked, “IF’s requirement for asset-backed transactions ensures that financial activities are grounded in real economic value, thereby reducing the likelihood of financial bubbles.” This alignment with real economic activities mitigates risks associated with financialization, where speculative motives often overshadow productive investments (Miah & Suzuki, 2015). By promoting transparency, asset-backed financing builds trust and ensures that all parties understand the underlying assets and risks. This transparency ultimately leads to more responsible decision-making, an imperative mentioned by a further interviewee: “Islamic finance must be a socially responsible player in the market.”

Finally, integrating Islamic ethics within CSR frameworks could serve as a model for promoting genuine ethical engagement across the financial sector. This integration could mitigate CSR’s shortcomings, providing a structured, values-based approach that mandates ethical compliance and limits exploitative practices. Moving forward, adopting aspects of Islamic ethics—such as risk-sharing, transparency, and real-economy alignment—into CSR could promote a more resilient and socially responsible financial system, expanding the concept of corporate accountability beyond voluntary commitments and toward a framework of compulsory, socially oriented practices. Moreover, integrating Islamic ethics within CSR frameworks was proposed as a model for addressing CSR’s structural limitations. Unlike CSR’s selective application based on organizational goals, IF requires adherence to ethical principles across all financial dealings, ensuring consistency and societal accountability. This structured approach could enhance CSR’s effectiveness by embedding ethical imperatives into financial systems. Participants frequently highlighted the potential for IF’s risk-sharing, transparency, and real-economy alignment to inform a more resilient and socially responsible financial sector. One expert summarized this integration, stating, “The ethical framework of IF not only promotes financial stability but also ensures that financial activities are aligned with societal values and sustainable development goals.”

These findings suggest that IF’s legally binding, structurally integrated ethics can enhance CSR’s impact by providing a comprehensive, values-driven financial model. Risk-averse principles such as the prohibition of interest and excessive uncertainty create a predictable and stable financial environment, as noted by one participant: “The inherent resilience of IF, with its emphasis on ethical practices and risk aversion, promotes long-term stability and could have mitigated the impact of the crisis.” Additionally, PLS mechanisms align interests between financiers and entrepreneurs, fostering responsible financial behavior and reducing defaults.

4.2. Profit-Sharing Models: Balancing Human Nature and Financial Stability in IF

Profit-sharing models, such as *mudarabah* and *musharakah*, were identified as pivotal in aligning stakeholder interests and fostering financial stability. These models distribute risks equitably between financiers and entrepreneurs, thereby discouraging excessive risk-taking. Participants consistently emphasized the ethical and collaborative nature of these contracts. One expert stated, “Profit-sharing mechanisms like *mudarabah* and *musharakah* align the interests of investors and entrepreneurs, reducing the incentive for excessive risk-taking that was prevalent in the conventional system during the crisis.”

Mudarabah contracts, where losses are borne solely by the financier unless caused by negligence, encourage careful management and accountability among entrepreneurs. *Musharakah*, on the other hand, requires all parties to share risk and reward proportionately, fostering transparency and mutual benefit. These findings align with the literature, highlighting the potential of risk-sharing models to build a culture of trust and collaboration, which is crucial for long-term stability (Smolo & Mirakhor, 2010). An interviewee emphasized, “*Musharakah* ensures that both investors and entrepreneurs have skin in the game, promoting a balanced approach to risk and reward.” Another participant further emphasized, “The ethical foundation of profit-sharing models in IF builds a culture of trust and mutual benefit, essential for long-term financial stability.” *Mudarabah* and *musharakah* contracts promote collaboration, transparency, and mutual benefit, offering a stable and ethical alternative to conventional financial practices.

However, the study also identified practical challenges in implementing profit-sharing contracts. Scholars have critiqued certain IF products, such as *murabahah*, for resembling conventional loans more than true risk-sharing mechanisms (El-Gamal, 2006; Kayed & Hassan, 2011). Participants acknowledged this limitation, noting that financial pressures sometimes lead institutions to adopt practices that compromise the ethical ideals of IF. For instance, while risk-sharing contracts are ideal, market dynamics and financial exigencies occasionally result in practices that mirror conventional finance.

Despite these challenges, the principles underlying profit-sharing models offer significant advantages over conventional financial practices. By embedding risk-sharing and equitable profit distribution into financial products, IF addresses moral hazard and aligns stakeholder incentives, thereby reducing systemic risks. As one expert remarked, “PLS arrangements in IF create a more resilient financial system by promoting responsible risk-taking and aligning the interests of all parties involved.”

4.3. Regulatory Environment

A central theme from the interviews was the role of real asset-backed investments in mitigating speculative risks and fostering market stability. Participants consistently emphasized the SSB as a pivotal mechanism for ensuring that Islamic banks operate within the bounds of Islamic law, prioritizing fairness and avoiding investments in industries deemed harmful to society.

Participants underscored the importance of a robust regulatory framework rooted in Shari’ah compliance. One participant noted, “The rigorous Shari’ah compliance and oversight in IF create a robust regulatory environment that could have prevented the widespread adoption of high-risk financial products seen in the crisis.” Another highlighted the additional layer of scrutiny provided by SSBs, stating, “The presence of Shari’ah boards helps maintain ethical standards and prevents the introduction of high-risk financial products.” Transparency and accountability were repeatedly identified as cornerstones of Shari’ah compliance, ensuring that financial activities are conducted fairly and ethically. As one participant explained, “Transparency and accountability are

cornerstones of Shari'ah compliance, ensuring that all financial activities are conducted in a fair and ethical manner.”

While the SSB provides stringent oversight, participants identified challenges in applying Shari'ah principles consistently across global markets. A recurring concern was the lack of standardized regulatory frameworks, which creates inconsistencies in Shari'ah compliance and complicates cross-border transactions. One participant observed, “The absence of standardized regulatory frameworks can lead to differences in Shari'ah compliance, making it difficult for IF institutions to operate seamlessly across regions.” The diversity in regulations across countries creates challenges for the global IF industry, leading to inconsistencies in Shari'ah compliance and hindering cross-border transactions.

To address these challenges, participants emphasized the need for a unified global regulatory framework. Collaboration among international organizations such as the Islamic Financial Services Board (IFSB) and the AAOIFI was proposed as essential for enhancing the credibility of IF and fostering global financial stability. As another participant stated, “Harmonized regulatory standards would enhance the credibility of IF, making it more attractive to both Muslim and non-Muslim investors.”

The SSB also acts as a strict governing mechanism, with authority to nullify contracts that violate Shari'ah standards, thereby enhancing accountability, as noted by a participant: “The Shari'ah board has authority to terminate the venture's contracts regardless of the stage of the business.” However, participants stressed the importance of harmonizing SSB standards across countries to strengthen the global application of IF principles. Despite these challenges, IF's emphasis on ethical investments, profit-and-loss sharing contracts, and real asset-backed transactions offers a resilient model for preventing financial crises and promoting long-term stability.

The study's findings align with Warde (2010), who underscores the need for authentic Islamic products that resist commercial pressures to mimic conventional financial practices. Participants noted that IF institutions were minimally impacted by the global financial crisis, reinforcing the effectiveness of Shari'ah-compliant practices. As one participant remarked, “The minimal impact of the crisis on Islamic banks has reinforced the effectiveness of Shari'ah-compliant practices, leading to increased interest and adoption in the post-crisis period.”

A study by Tabash and Dhankar (2014) showed that Islamic banks in Saudi Arabia maintained higher liquidity ratios during the GFC, showing their capacity to meet sudden withdrawal demands. Specifically, the Liquid Asset Ratio (LAR) of Islamic banks in Saudi Arabia, which reached 33.96% in 2007, indicated a robust level of liquidity just before the crisis. Although there was some impact in 2008 due to the uncertain financial market conditions, the effect on Islamic banks was minor compared to conventional banks. An ANOVA analysis further showed that Islamic banks experienced no statistically significant change in liquidity before, during, and after the crisis, underscoring their stability. This shielded them from the severe liquidity issues faced by many conventional banks during the crisis (Tabash, Dhankar, 2014). The literature supports these findings, suggesting that adopting IF principles could enhance the stability and resilience of conventional banks (Hasan & Dridi, 2011).

The post-crisis period has seen a reevaluation of financial practices, with innovations in Shari'ah-compliant products and stronger regulatory frameworks to enhance stability. One interviewee observed, “The post-crisis period has been marked by significant innovation in IF, with institutions developing new products that align with Shari'ah principles and address market demands.” Overall, the global financial crisis spurred further adaptation and growth in IF, highlighting its potential for promoting long-term financial stability and preventing future crises.

Additionally, the GFC underscored the systemic risks of financialization and the need for alternative economic models. IF, with its focus on ethical compliance and risk aversion, provides a values-driven framework that prioritizes societal well-being over speculative profits. As highlighted, the rigorous Shari'ah compliance embedded in IF not only promotes financial stability but also ensures that financial practices align with long-term economic and social justice objectives. This positions IF as a viable model for addressing the vulnerabilities of financialization, fostering a more resilient and equitable global financial system.

4.4. Systemic Resilience

The interviews highlighted the inherent resilience of IF, rooted in its risk-averse and ethical principles, as a key factor in promoting long-term stability. One participant noted, "The inherent resilience of IF, with its emphasis on ethical practices and risk aversion, promotes long-term stability and could have mitigated the impact of the 2008 financial crisis." IF's focus on risk-sharing and ethical guidelines minimizes speculative bubbles and financial instability. Another interviewee added, "The avoidance of interest and excessive uncertainty in IF creates a more predictable and stable financial system." PLS mechanisms further align interests, reducing defaults and enhancing stability. The strict regulatory oversight and Shari'ah compliance requirements also contribute to this resilience, ensuring transparency and accountability. Islamic banks' minimal impact from the crisis reinforced the effectiveness of Shari'ah-compliant practices, leading to increased global interest in IF. As one participant stated, "The minimal impact of the 2008 crisis on Islamic banks has reinforced the effectiveness of Shari'ah-compliant practices, leading to increased interest and adoption in the post-crisis period." This post-crisis period has seen a reevaluation of financial practices, with innovations in Shari'ah-compliant products and stronger regulatory frameworks to enhance stability. As another interviewee noted, "The post-crisis period has been marked by significant innovation in IF, with institutions developing new products that align with Shari'ah principles and address market demands." Overall, the crisis spurred further adaptation and growth in IF, highlighting its potential for promoting long-term financial stability and preventing future crises.

4.5. Summary of the Results

The findings of this study demonstrate the potential of IF principles to provide a resilient, ethical, and sustainable alternative to conventional financial practices. By embedding values such as transparency, risk-sharing, and alignment with real economic activities into financial transactions, IF addresses the systemic vulnerabilities exposed during the GFC.

Participants highlighted that IF's prohibitions against interest (*riba*) and excessive uncertainty (*gharar*) and speculation (*maysir*), along with its emphasis on asset-backed financing, foster stability, reduce speculative risks, and enhance trust in financial systems.

Moreover, unlike the often voluntary nature of CSR, IF mandates ethical adherence, ensuring that financial activities align with societal values and sustainable development goals. This structured approach addresses gaps in traditional CSR practices, providing a foundation for long-term financial resilience and equitable growth.

The analysis of profit-sharing models further illustrates how IF aligns stakeholder interests and mitigates excessive risk-taking, fostering a collaborative and stable financial environment. While practical challenges remain—such as the occasional drift toward conventional practices and the lack of standardized global regulatory frameworks—the benefits of IF principles in promoting ethical behavior and financial stability are undeniable.

The role of SSBs was also highlighted as critical in maintaining ethical standards and ensuring compliance with IF principles. However, the study identified the need for greater harmonization

across regulatory frameworks to enhance the global applicability of IF practices. Collaborative efforts among international organizations like the IFSB and AAOIFI are essential to establish unified standards, strengthening the credibility and appeal of IF globally.

Thus, this study affirms the transformative potential of IF in reshaping global financial systems. By prioritizing ethics, transparency, and stability, IF offers a viable pathway toward a more resilient and socially responsible financial future. The challenges identified—while significant—present opportunities for innovation, collaboration, and the continued evolution of Shari'ah-compliant practices in addressing the complexities of the modern financial world.

5. CONCLUSION

This research highlights the transformative potential of IF principles in fostering a more resilient and ethical financial system, particularly in preventing financial crises. By examining IF principles and their implementation during the GFC, the study underscores how ethical investments, asset-backed financing, and prohibitions on interest, uncertainty, and speculation contribute to greater financial stability. The interviews with IF experts provided valuable insights, reinforcing the idea that IF principles can significantly reduce the risks of financial crises. This study contributes to the academic discourse by advocating for a shift toward ethical banking practices that can better withstand economic shocks.

This study faced several limitations that should be acknowledged to contextualize its findings. First, the small sample size of participants, drawn from a limited number of IF institutions, restricts the generalizability of the results. While the qualitative case study approach allows for in-depth exploration, relying on a small group of experts may only partially capture the diversity of perspectives within the global Islamic finance industry. Additionally, the interview-based data collection posed challenges, as it relied on participants' recollections and subjective interpretations, which could introduce biases. Efforts were made to mitigate these issues through cross-referencing secondary data and employing triangulation techniques, but these measures cannot entirely eliminate the limitations inherent in qualitative research. Future studies with larger, more geographically diverse samples could enhance the robustness and applicability of the findings. Furthermore, the qualitative case study approach is not inherently generalizable, the findings provide a valuable critique of the capitalist financial system and suggest IF as a sustainable alternative.

These insights have practical implications for crisis prevention, including establishing standardized regulatory frameworks that integrate Islamic finance (IF) principles globally. Additionally, fostering collaboration with conventional banking systems to incorporate ethical practices—such as risk-sharing, transparency, and a focus on real economic activities—could enhance financial stability and resilience. Regulatory authorities should actively promote IF adoption as a crisis-resilient framework, particularly through policies encouraging ethical investment and asset-backed financing in non-Muslim-majority countries. While Islamophobia presents a significant challenge to the global acceptance of IF principles, consistent positive financial metrics can help mitigate negative perceptions. Furthermore, conventional banking should transition away from non-asset-backed financing, often contributing to speculation and economic instability.

Future research should explore the challenges of implementing IF in non-Muslim-majority countries, where socio-political, regulatory, and cultural barriers may hinder its adoption. Key areas to explore include adapting Shari'ah principles within secular legal frameworks, overcoming misconceptions and Islamophobia, and developing regulatory structures that harmonize IF with existing financial systems. Additionally, research should investigate strategies for increasing awareness and acceptance of IF among non-Muslim stakeholders, including the potential for education and

advocacy to dispel misconceptions. Examining the long-term economic impacts of integrating IF principles into conventional banking systems in these regions could also provide valuable insights, particularly regarding the scalability and sustainability of IF as a global financial model.

This study affirms the potential of IF to reshape global financial systems. By prioritizing ethics, transparency, and stability, IF offers a viable path toward a more resilient and socially responsible financial future. Challenges, while significant, present opportunities for innovation and collaboration, ensuring the continued evolution of Shari'ah-compliant practices in addressing modern financial complexities.

Declarations

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

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APPENDIX 1

Table 1 below shows the interview questions that were asked during our interview process.

Table 1: Interview Questions

Theme	Question
1. Background and Experience	1. To begin, can you briefly introduce yourself, what you currently do and what motivated you to pursue a career in this area?
	1. What were your initial reactions to the unfolding events of the 2008 financial crisis?
	1. To what extent did the 2008 financial crisis impact your bank or the Islamic banking sector in general?
1. Perceptions of the 2008 Financial Crisis	1. What strategies or measures did the Islamic bank implement in response to the 2008 financial crisis to ensure financial stability and business continuity?
	1. Did Islamic financial institutions respond differently to the challenges posed by the 2008 financial crisis compared to conventional banks?
1. Role of Islamic Finance Practices	1. In your opinion, could Islamic finance principles/tools have alleviated the effects of the 2008 financial crisis, and if so, to what extent?
	1. Do ethical and socially responsible banking practices play a role within Islamic finance?
1. Response Strategies and Adaptations	1. Do regulatory and governance frameworks within Islamic banking institutions significantly differ from those of conventional banks?
	1. How did regulatory frameworks and oversight mechanisms governing Islamic finance institutions influence the response to the 2008 financial crisis?
1. Lessons Learned and Future Outlook	1. Reflecting on the 2008 financial crisis, what are the most notable lessons learned within the Islamic banking sector?
	1. Looking ahead, what do you foresee as the trajectory of Islamic finance, especially considering ongoing global economic challenges and the rise in Islamophobia?
	1. From your viewpoint, what lessons can other financial institutions, both Islamic and conventional, gain from the 2008 financial crisis?
1. Personal Reflections and Insights	1. Do you believe Islamic banking principles could have prevented the crisis?
	1. What personal insights or experiences from the 2008 financial crisis or any other financial crisis over the past couple of years have shaped your perspective on Islamic finance and its role in promoting financial stability?
	1. Is there anything else you would like to share or discuss regarding your experiences during the crisis and their implications for Islamic finance?
1. Theories	1. Given the ongoing debate surrounding financialization, what role would you attribute to financialization in contributing to the 2008 financial crisis? Specifically, how do you perceive the impact of excessive financialization on economic stability during that period?

Source: Author's own.

Adapting to Change: Financial Institutions Among Bosnian Muslims in the Austro- Hungarian Era (1878-1918)

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the establishment of modern financial institutions among Bosnian Muslims during the Austro-Hungarian occupation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (1878–1918). It explores how traditional Islamic financial practices were challenged and reshaped under the pressures of modern European administrative and economic systems introduced by the Austro-Hungarian authorities. Key areas of focus include the establishment of new banking institutions and the adaptation of local communities to emerging economic paradigms. By analyzing historical documents, economic policies, and cultural responses, the article sheds light on the intersection of faith, tradition, and modernity during a period of significant socio-economic transition. It argues that Bosnian Muslims navigated these changes through a combination of resistance, negotiation, and innovation, ultimately leaving a lasting imprint on the financial landscape of the country.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In the 19th century, the Ottoman Empire (OE) entered a turbulent period. *Tanzimat* (period of reform) brought many changes in the social landscape, but OE was still struggling financially. Although different strategies were implemented to prevent further deterioration, such as tax reform and changes in monetary policy, they did not succeed. Therefore, OE was compelled to ask for a loan from its allies in the Crimean War (the United Kingdom and France) in 1854. This practice was continued in the following decades until 1875, when bankruptcy was declared (Ozekicioglu & Ozekicioglu, 2010).

Parallel with the bankruptcy declaration, a serious political challenge for OE emerged in the Bosnian Vilayet in the summer of the same year. Namely, Christian peasants from southern parts of Bosnian Vilayet (Herzegovina) started an uprising called the Herzegovina Uprising. The main reason was the poor socio-economic conditions of peasants, whose situation was worsened by the heavy tax burden imposed by the government because of the empty treasury. This uprising had local character but international implications. Soon, it triggered several other uprisings and wars in the Balkan Peninsula, known as the Great Eastern Crisis. In our context, this event is significant since it had a decisive influence on later political developments. In June 1878, the Congress of Berlin was convened to improve the decisions of the Treaty of San Stefano (Buhin, 2012).

According to Article XXV of the Treaty of Berlin, Austria-Hungary (A-H) gained permission to occupy Bosnia and Herzegovina:

“The provinces of Bosnia and Herzegovina shall be occupied and administered by Austria-Hungary. The government of Austria-Hungary, not desiring to undertake the administration of the Sanjak of Novi-Pazar, which extends between Serbia and Montenegro in a South-Easterly direction to the other side of Mitrovica, the Ottoman administration will continue to exercise its functions there. Nevertheless, to assure the maintenance of the new political situation and freedom and security of communications, Austria-Hungary reserves the right of keeping garrisons and having military and commercial roads in the whole of this part the ancient vilayet of Bosnia. To this end, the governments of Austria-Hungary and Turkey reserve to themselves to understand the details.”

A-H had a strong argument for occupation, which was staunchly supported by the United Kingdom and Germany and later accepted by representatives of other countries. OE showed its incompetence in governance; the autonomy of Bosnia and Herzegovina was not feasible, and only a neutral and robust country as A-H could bring order and sustainable peace. Namely, A-H wanted to execute pacification and “civilization” missions in neighboring countries since there was a source of constant insurgencies that could disrupt the *status quo* between European powers. However, this “noble” mission of A-H was primarily directed by its geopolitical interests (Buhin, 2012).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Article XXV of the Berlin Congress stipulated the occupation of Bosnia and Herzegovina. On the last day of Congress, OE and A-H were also obliged to reach a mutual agreement concerning occupation details. After exhausting negotiations, the Novi Pazar Convention was signed in 1879. The most important articles of this convention were: Sultan’s sovereign rights over Bosnia and Herzegovina would not be violated; Ottoman money will remain in circulation; name of the Sultan will be mentioned in Friday prayers; use of the Ottoman flag at certain places and occasions will be allowed; freedom of religion will be granted; revenue generated in Bosnia and Herzegovina will be spent in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Imamović, 2007). A-H signed this convention only because of a previous agreement in Berlin. A-H violated nearly every article of this convention over time to reduce OE’s influence.

Most importantly, the convention did not mention the provisional occupation agreed upon in Berlin. The article, which stipulated the Sultan’s sovereign rights over Bosnia and Herzegovina, gave a trace of hope that one day Ottomans would regain control of „their temporary occupied territory.” However, measures undertaken by A-H showed that its primary goal was not a temporary pacification mission but rather permanent occupation and annexation (Buhin, 2012).

Because of its specific legal status, the case of Bosnia and Herzegovina intrigued many jurists worldwide. Opposing viewpoints were presented regarding the question: To whom does sovereignty belong? No consensus was reached, but “authors agreed that the legal status of Bosnia and Herzegovina is undetermined and that even represents a legal anomaly” (Imamović, 2007, p. 21). The legal status of Bosnia and Herzegovina within the A-H posed a great challenge and a source of potential conflict between Austria and Hungary. The consensus was reached, and joint administration over Bosnia and Herzegovina was declared (Buhin, 2012).

A-H occupation was especially challenging for Bosnian Muslims, who were integrated into the Ottoman feudal system for several hundred years. In 1878, they had to face a new reality. They have become a minority, and their future was uncertain under new circumstances. No significant political-cultural initiative was recorded in that period by them. The movement for religious-educational autonomy (*Pokret za vakufsko-mearifsku autonomiju*) that emerged in 1899 was the first sign of political initiative (Imamović, 2007).

This movement transformed itself into a political party in 1906, namely the Muslim People’s Organization (*Muslimanska narodna organizacija*). In 1908, the Muslim Progressive Party (*Muslimanska*

napredna stranka) was established. It had similar goals to the Muslim People's Organization, but it employed a different strategy. Intellectuals from this party designated themselves as progressive Muslims, and they were against confrontation with A-H. They supported the revival of cultural, social, and economic aspects of Bosnian Muslims, ensuring their full participation in public life. In contrast to the Muslim People's Organization, which cooperated with the Serbian political factor, they promoted cooperation with Croats. The founder of the Muslim Progressive Party was Ademaga Mešić (Imamović, 2007).

A-H was apprehensive about potential national mobilization among its governed populations. It perceived strong financial institutions as potential sources of income for future separatist activities. Therefore, A-H prohibited the establishment of any bank whose name included adjectives like "Muslim," "Serb," or "Croat" until 1903. This restriction was lifted after introducing liberalization measures in 1903 (Nametak, 2018).

Marković (1938) argues that banking in Bosnia and Herzegovina during the A-H occupation had an economic and political background. Thus, the banking sector underwent a significant ebb and flow in a relatively short period of 40 years. According to Vujović (2015), banking in occupied Bosnia and Herzegovina represented precedence in Europe because of clear national attribution. More precisely, banking followed the same "tribal" path as establishing any other organization by local people at that time. The period from 1903-1914 was a period of an economic renaissance. During this period, 50 money offices were founded: Serbian, Muslim, Croat, and mixed (Kosier & Ristić, 1924). The following table provides an overview of domestic and foreign money offices in 1914:

Table 1: Overview of foreign and domestic financial institutions in 1914

OWNERSHIP	NO.	SHARE CAPITAL	RESERVE	DEPOSIT	TOTAL
Serbian	26	10,000,000	5,000,000	8,000,000	23,000,000
Croatian	10	3,000,000	600,000	3,000,000	6,600,000
Muslim	8	4,000,000	800,000	3,500,000	8,300,000
Mixed	6	1,500,000	500,000	3,200,000	5,200,000
Domestic	50	18,500,000	6,900,000	17,700,000	43,100,000
Foreign	4	20,000,000	8,000,000	60,000,000	88,000,000
Domestic+Foreign	54	38,500,000	14,900,000	77,700,000	131,100,000

Source: Author's own representation based on Kosier & Ristić (1924, p. 12)

We can notice an apparent disproportion in the table above. Namely, only four banks from A-H had twice as much capital as 50 domestic money offices: 88,000,000 Kronen (K) compared to 43,100,000 K. So, foreign capital was dominant and played a crucial role in the country's development.

3. METHODOLOGY

We will use several methods to explain our research: case study, historical, and comparative methods, respectively. The case study method explores the specific subject from a particular research area. In this study, we will focus on one specific group of people- Bosnian Muslims- the exact time-turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, and the specific subject issue of establishing modern financial institutions.

Then, we will use the historical method. A historical method is a procedure that is based on various documents and evidence can find out exactly what happened in the past it happened and, if possible, how and why it happened (Zelenika, 2000).

A historical method, which consists of a systematic set of principles and rules, is designed to effectively aid in collecting original material from the past. It helps to critically evaluate and present this material as a synthesis, typically in written form, of the results obtained (Garraghan, 1946). Garraghan (1946) argues that a historical method consists of three operations:

- Search for the material and sources of information for research (heuristics);
- Evaluation of material and sources from the view of evidence-based value (criticism);
- Formally stating the results of heuristics and criticism. This operation involves compiling a set of historical data and presenting them (usually in writing) in the form of objective truth and value (synthesis: historical reasoning).

The historical method has several specific characteristics: evidence used in this method is mostly indirect; this evidence must be interpreted; the researcher needs to reconstruct the past, which can be difficult as the current knowledge of the researcher affects the form of a notion of the past; researchers are expected to discover the actual mechanism (usually causal) that will help him to give meaning to the mass of evidence (Karčić, 2013).

Research of past events focuses on historical phenomena, being inherently retrospective. We will gather information chronologically to examine the origins, causes, and effects of events from various sources.

4. FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS

4.1. First Muslim Credit Cooperative

A group of self-designated progressive Muslims gathered around Ademaga Mešić established the First Muslim Credit Cooperative on 02.05.1906 in Tešanj with a founding capital of 500,000 K (Juzbašić, 2002). The Director of the First Muslim Credit Cooperative was Ademaga Mešić; Ibrahim Kučukalić was president, and Zija-beg Đonlagić was vice president. The Board of Directors consisted of prominent members of the Muslim community from Tešanj and other cities in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The executive council is comprised of five people, including one non-Muslim. At the very beginning of its operations, the First Muslim Credit Cooperative had 64 shareholders who owned 2,412 shares, respectively. At the end of the financial year 1906, the number of shareholders was reduced to 33. In 1908, there were changes in the management structure, and Zija-beg Đonlagić became the president (Galijašević, 1999). This was a logical step since Zija-beg Đonlagić went to Vienna in 1908, where he completed a banking course in the German language (Narodna uzdanica, 1939).

Interestingly, almost two years before its establishment, the intention for the foundation of such an institution was proclaimed. The proclamation is presented as glad tidings to Muslims in Bosnia and Herzegovina. It is argued that the existence of credit cooperatives is of the utmost importance. Namely, old-fashioned trade was not feasible since money could not be kept in cash anymore. One share cost 200 K, and 1 K was a weekly contribution, so even the poorest community members could become members in 4 years in the worst-case scenario. It is important to mention that the agitation for establishing a Muslim bank was continuously present in the newspapers. One such is published in *Musavat* in early 1908:

For a long time, there has been talk of us Muslims establishing our own bank, and many claim that efforts are underway to bring this vision to life as soon as possible. However, so far, these discussions have amounted to little more than empty words and well-meaning wishes. We still do not see our community taking this matter seriously, nor do we believe it will gain widespread acceptance anytime soon.

Those who are most capable of leading this initiative, particularly the wealthiest among us, have shown little interest or urgency. Seemingly indifferent to the future of their children or the well-being of the community, they remain passive while their brothers are compelled to turn to external financial institutions. These institutions, often run by outsiders, exploit our people, trapping them in their financial webs and draining their resources.

It is unreasonable to expect these foreign institutions, operated by non-Muslims and often by foreigners, to show the same respect, compassion, or understanding for our people that we would show for each other. Such institutions have no stake in developing or uplifting our trades and crafts. Muslim merchants and artisans can rarely secure the amount of credit they rightfully deserve based on their work and assets. Instead, foreign lenders only provide loans that align with their interests, leaving our entrepreneurs at a disadvantage.

This imbalance allows foreign businesses to outcompete ours with ease. Armed with greater access to credit and resources, they dominate markets, overshadowing and marginalizing our traders. Consequently, our people are left to depend on those who do not have their best interests at heart, while significant Muslim-owned capital lies idle, serving no purpose.

Consider the wealth held in the form of gold, pearls, and various valuables, often owned by women. This capital sits unused and, according to Sharia, incurs a 2.5% zakat obligation annually. If this wealth were actively invested—for instance, by converting it into shares of a Muslim bank—it would not only generate significant profits for the investors but also benefit the broader community. An active bank would fuel growth in Muslim commerce and industry, leading to higher wages and increased charitable contributions, far exceeding the obligatory 2.5% zakat.

Jewelry and ornaments do not enhance a woman's intelligence or beauty, but if their value were mobilized into productive investments, they could transform our economic prospects. By establishing a bank, this dormant wealth could be turned into a powerful tool for community development.

We urge our Executive Committee to take immediate action and lead this initiative. If they commit to establishing a Muslim bank, they can and will succeed. The time to act is now—when it is most urgently needed. As the saying goes, *iron must be forged while it is hot*.

In an article titled “*Our economic revival*”, an in-depth analysis of the challenging situation of Muslims was explained. The “conspiracy” of foreign capital was cited as a significant threat. The idea of a credit co-operative was thoroughly presented. One month before its establishment, several reasons for creating the First Muslim Credit Cooperative were outlined. Initially, it was emphasized that the institution secured all necessary licenses for a successful launch of its operations.

Additionally, the financial aspects of participation were explained. The strategic plan to relocate the headquarters to Sarajevo was also presented, with high hopes that the Muslim community would support this initiative. The founders aimed to provide a common benefit to both Muslim individuals and the wider Muslim community, as this would prevent usurers from carrying out their harmful practices. In the middle of April 1906, an appeal was sent to fellow Muslims in Bosnia and Herzegovina to support this institution.

Dear brothers and friends!

All progressive nations strive and work to improve their economic conditions by their means, free themselves from foreign influence, and strengthen their financial and moral position. Unfortunately, our dear homeland, proud Bosnia and Herzegovina does not yet have a single Muslim money office. All existing financial institutions are in the hands of foreigners. Muslim merchants, *bays*, *aghas*, artisans and peasants are forced to

knock on their doors. Our famous proverb pronounces: “A stepmother can never be like a mother.” Many Muslim *bays*, *aghas*, and peasants went bankrupt because we did not have a Muslim money office; their houses and lands were sold at a fair price. If Muslim money offices were established, there would be far less harm. We, Muslims of Tešanj, have decided to establish the first Muslim money office headquartered in Tešanj. For the time being, we set out to establish this institution as a credit cooperative that requires small, if not negligent contributions, so that even the poor can easily become members of the cooperative. The initial plan is to move headquarter to Sarajevo with the branches in Tešanj and other places if support is provided by our fellow Muslims. One share will cost 200 K, and it will be paid in the following way: by paying 20 K initially including 1 K of processing fee; the rest of 180 K will be paid in weekly installments (1 K every week) if it is not possible to pay all at once. Undersigned interim committee pleads every fellow Muslim and friend of Islamic progress to become a member of our credit cooperative. Even before this appeal went public, prominent Muslims and non-Muslims bought a significant number of shares, which assures us that the future of this cooperative is secured. We again plead to your patriotism, hoping that you will pay attention to this noble movement and join these patriotic sentiments in the interest of Islam and Islamic progress. Receive brotherly and friendly greetings (*salam*)!

Founders of the First Muslim Credit Cooperative

Ademaga Mešić Zija-beg Đonlagić

Hasan-aga Turalić Ahmed-aga Galijašević Hamza-aga Mešić

Under the advertisement section in the *Sarajevski list*, a brief explanation of the credit cooperative’s operational work and planned business activities was stated.

No. 5643

At the District Court in Banja Luka, “First Muslim Credit Cooperative with the limited liability” or “*Erste islamitische Credit-Genossenschaft mit beschränkter Haftung*” headquartered in Tešanj, has been listed in the register of the commercial companies. This credit cooperative has been established according to regulations presented in the first constitutive assembly on 02.05.1906, approved by the Joint Ministry of Finance decree on 12.06.1906., no. 6337/Bosnia and Herzegovina, to Provincial government of Bosnia and Herzegovina on 27.06.1906., no.106.721/II-V.

This credit cooperative has a task of improving the financial position of its members by offering favorable loans to them as well as cultivating the habit of saving; it will accept saving deposits from everyone; it will base its business activities on conclusions of the general assembly (§5.), and it will engage primarily in the following business activities:

- a. offering different types of credits;
- b. agency services in purchase/sale to third parties;
- c. deposit with a favorable interest rate;
- d. receiving regular weekly savings from its members. (§18.)

Members of the cooperative guarantee for liabilities of the cooperative only to the amount to which they subscribed (§255. of Commercial law).

Public statements of the cooperative will be published in the magazine Behar in Sarajevo and other magazines in the country.

District Court

Banja Luka, 14.12.1906.

A call for participation in the first general assembly was published in *Behar* in February 1907. Assembly was held in the premises of the city reading room in Tešanj with the following agenda:

1. Management report and proposal for net profit distribution.
2. Supervisory Board report.
3. Balance sheet approval.
4. *Absolutorium* division.
5. Agreement on net profit distribution.
6. Modification of the rules:
 - a. Relocation of headquarters from Tešanj to Sarajevo.
 - b. Opening of branches in Tešanj, Bijeljina and other places in Bosnia and Herzegovina according to the needs.
7. A proposal that the cooperative changes its legal form to a joint-stock company as “First Muslim Credit Bank” (*Prva muslimanska kreditna banka*).
8. Any other business (AOB).

Figure 1: Call to the first general assembly of the First Muslim Credit Cooperative

Source: *Behar* (1907, no.19, p. 228)

It is interesting to note that a call for the assembly was written in *arebica* (the Bosnian language with Arabic alphabets) beside Latin script. In July 1907, the First Muslim Credit Cooperative advertised the vacant position of an accountant who would also become branch manager in Bijeljina.

Requirements for the position were:

- Knowledge of double-entry bookkeeping.
- Expertise in writing balance sheet statements.
- Proficiency in the German language.
- Knowledge of banking operations.

Also, it is emphasized that First Muslim Credit Cooperative wants to fill this position as soon as possible and that salary is subject to negotiations, but in any case, it will be determined according to the applicant's expertise.

One year later, a call for participation in the second general assembly was published in the *Sarajevski list*. The place of the meeting was the same as the previous year, but the agenda was slightly different:

1. Management report and proposal for net profit distribution.
2. Supervisory Board report.
3. Balance sheet approval.
4. Absolutorium division.
5. Agreement on net profit distribution.
6. Election of Management and Supervisory Board.
7. Modification of the rules because of headquarters relocation to Sarajevo.
8. Discussion on the branch in Bijeljina.
9. A proposal that the cooperative changes its legal form to a joint-stock company as "First Muslim Credit Bank" (*Prva muslimanska kreditna banka*).

Figure 2: Balance sheet & income statement of the First Muslim Credit Cooperative (1906)

Prva muslimanska kreditna zadruga (sa ograničenim jamstvom) u Tešnju.			
Račun bilance.		Račun dobitka i gubitka.	
Aktiva.		Rashod.	
Gotovina	K 18226—	Kamati:	
Mjenice u listnici	223734'28	uložaka	K 104'54;
Dužnici u tekućem računu	24201'84	reeskompitiranih mjenica	1328'30; K 1432'84
Našastar	K 3023'80;	Troškovi, poštarine, brzojavi, ogriev, rasvjeta, tiskanice i ini troškovi	1900'34
5% odpis za pol godine	173'80; " 2850—	Plaće	1740—
Utemeljiteljni troškovi	4778'96;	Kućna kirija	400—
Opis	2000—; " 2778'96	Porez	102'96
Suma	K 271791'08	Odpisi:	
Passiva.		od utemeljiteljnih troškova	K 2000—; " 2173'80
Glavnica: na 2412 upisanih udjela uplaćeno do konca godine 1906.	K 99981—;	od našastara	" 173'80; " 2173'80
33 udrugara sasvim isplatili		Čist dobitak	3169'22
357 udjela i višak sa 5% ukamačen	46592—; K 146573—	Suma	K 10919'16
Uloži: na štednju sa kap. kamatima	14117'70;	Prihod.	
U tekućem računu	32121'97; " 46239'67	Kamati od mjenica po odbitku prenosnih kamata	K 5169'67
Vjerovnici u tekućem računu	855—	Kamati tekućeg računa	" 503'15
Reeskomp kod novčanih zavoda	72103—	Provizije:	
Redovita pričuvna zaklada	9—	bankovnog odjelenja	K 821—;
Prenosni kamati	2842'19	robnog odjelenja	" 2002'34; " 2823'34
Čist dobitak	3169'22	Uplaćene upisnine	2423—
Suma	K 271791'08	Suma	K 10919'16
Za ravnateljstvo:			
Ademaga Mešić m. p., predsjednik; Zijabeg Gjonlagić m. p., stalni dnev. povjer.; Julio pl. Vuković m. p., uprav.			
Ispitano i sa glavn. i pomoćnim knjigama suglasno i točno pronajeno:			
Za nadzorno vijeće:			
Abid ef. Sadiković m. p., pročelnik; Ahmetaga Avduzajmović m. p.; Dr. Halidbeg Hrasnica m. p.; Ejubaga Bajraktarević m. p.; Samuel Schwarz m. p.			

Source: Bošnjak (1907, no.8, p.4)

According to Commercial law from 1883, credit cooperatives, banks and other financial institutions are registered as commercial companies. Therefore, they have a right to perform various business activities and banking operations. First Muslim Credit Cooperative utilized this opportunity provided by law. We can notice in one advertisement in 1911 that the First Muslim Credit Cooperative had its commodity department (*robno odjeljenje*), which dealt with the import and export of various goods. It is also evident that the cooperative accepts deposits and pays back 5% of interest. According to the balance sheet and income statement at the end of the fiscal year 1906, First Muslim Credit Cooperative had a net profit of 3,169 K.

At the end of the fiscal year 1907, First Muslim Credit Cooperative had a net profit of 12,248 K, which almost quadrupled compared to the previous year. On 31.12.1908, First Muslim Credit Cooperative generated 26,177 K of net profit, thus confirming that the trust in its operational work gained momentum.

Figure 3: Liquidation announcement of the First Muslim Credit Cooperative

Source: Sarajevski list (1912, no.261, p.7)

However, in March 1911, the general assembly decided to liquidate the First Muslim Credit Cooperative, and the District Court in Banja Luka confirmed this decision in October 1912. The reason for liquidation was not poor performance, because we saw an increase in profit in 3 consecutive years. Namely, one of the goals set in the first general assembly anticipated the gradual transformation of this credit cooperative into a bank. Thus, after six years of operations, the abovementioned credit cooperative transformed itself into a Muslim Merchant and Agricultural Bank (Imamović, 2007). According to the final balance sheet in 1912, the First Muslim Credit Cooperative deposited 322,528 K in the Muslim Merchant and Agricultural Bank.

4.2. Muslim Merchant and Agricultural Bank

As we already noted, the Muslim Merchant and Agricultural Bank (*Muslimanska trgovačka i poljodjelska banka*) resulted from transforming the First Muslim Credit Cooperative in 1912 (Imamović, 2007). The bank did not change only its name but also its legal form (from limited liability company to joint-stock company). Founding capital was 500,000 K. Founders decided to retain 80% of the shares, so only 20% of shares were available to the public (Galijašević, 1999). In the first year of operation, interest revenue was 47,592 K, and net profit was 45,072 K.

Figure 4: Income statement of Muslim Merchant and Agricultural Bank (1912)

Račun gubitka i dobitka za 31. decembra 1912.									
Gubitak					Dobitak.				
	K	h	K	h		K	h	K	h
Za trošak, porez, plaće, otpise i t. d.			9.509	42	Prihod kamata.			47.592	48
Za čisti dobitak			45.072	55	Providba			6.989	49
			54.581	97				54.581	97

Source: Sarajevski list (1913, no.5, p.7)

A call for participation in the first general assembly was published in *Sarajevski list*. The assembly was scheduled for 25.01.1913 at 10 a.m. with the following agenda:

1. Management report and proposal for net profit distribution.
2. Supervisory Board report.
3. Absolutorium division.
4. Agreement on net profit distribution.
5. Change of statute §§ 6., 37., 45. and 46. AOB;

In 1915, net profit was only 47 266 K, probably because of the World War I (WWI). In 1920, the bank wanted to increase its capital to 1,000,000 K, so the call to shareholders and the public was issued. In 1936, a loss was recorded, but the Kingdom of Yugoslavia did not provide a bailout. The liquidation date remains unknown.

4.3. Muslim Central Bank

4.3.1. Political dimension of establishment

The establishment of the Muslim Central Bank (*Muslimanska centralna banka*) cannot be understood without considering the dynamics of the Muslim political sphere. Banking in Bosnia and Herzegovina had a political background, so it was not a “pure” economic issue. Before we describe the bank and its operations, we will give a brief overview of the political circumstances that shaped the foundation of the Muslim Central Bank. Muslim People’s Organization (MPO) and Muslim Progressive Party (MPP) were Bosnian Muslims political parties in the A-H rule over Bosnia and Herzegovina. However, these two parties had divergent opinions on all important questions concerning Bosnian Muslims. Since MPO led the movement for religious-educational autonomy, it enjoyed support from the Muslim masses. In 1908, the MPO refused to recognize the annexation of Bosnia and Herzegovina by A-H, while the MPP supported this act. The MPP tried to fill the political vacuum that arose due to the MPO isolation and, thus, position itself as a leading party of Bosnian Muslims.

Moreover, only a few months before the first elections for the Diet of Bosnia and Herzegovina in 1910, the MPP renounced its pro-Croatian policy and even changed its name to Muslim Independent Party (MIP - *Muslimanska samostalna stranka*). Intrigued by this act and faced with the fact that it would not participate in upcoming elections if A-H sovereignty over Bosnia and Herzegovina was not accepted, the MPO recognized annexation in February 1910 (Imamović, 2007).

It is important to note that a joint coalition of these two parties was considered but failed, as in many cases before. The MPO won elections convincingly and took all places in Diet ensured for Muslims. Esad Kulović from the MIP won one mandate, but he relinquished it later because he did not want to confront 23 Muslim representatives from the MPO in Diet alone. In this period, Esad Kulović positioned himself as a *de facto* leader of progressive Muslims. He asked the MPP to renounce its pro-Croatian policy in return for his election to party organs. Ademaga Mešić was against it, but he had to comply with Esad's conditions. Esad Kulović was a mayor of Sarajevo, and his party support was paramount (Imamović, 2007).

Disagreement between Ademaga Mešić and Esad Kulović got a new dimension only a few months later. In April 1910, the assembly of the MIP decided to establish the Muslim Central Bank. Esad Kulović was elected as the president of the bank committee, while Ademaga Mešić became its member. However, this committee had many challenges, primarily because of disagreements between Ademaga Mešić and Esad Kulović. Namely, Esad Kulović wanted MIP to establish its bank, but Ademaga Mešić endorsed a joint Muslim bank. This disagreement about the bank's vision and mission should be understood in the context of political negotiations about the unification of MPO and MIP into a single party, which took place at the same time. Esad Kulović staunchly opposed the union, while Ademaga Mešić supported it. In a decisive party meeting in June 1911, Ademaga expressed his view on a joint Muslim bank:

If a joint bank is established to represent the entire Islamic community, regardless of political differences, it will garner moral and material support from Muslims in this country. However, if it is created as a partisan institution, it will fail to provide the benefits a unified institution could offer. There is an urgent need for such a bank to be established as soon as possible. In the economic realm—arguably the most critical aspect of our existence—we face threats from adversaries surrounding us on all sides. Moreover, it is evident that the government is not favorably inclined towards us, as it does not protect our interests as it should, in accordance with its rights and obligations. Trade and craftsmanship are slipping from our hands daily, and we are falling behind in every sphere of life. This alone underscores the necessity of creating a significant Islamic financial institution. All progressive and developed nations establish their financial institutions to advance economically, and such institutions have proven to be vital for political, social, and cultural progress. Today, every advanced nation has its own financial institutions, and those without them cannot hope to progress in any area of life. A striking example is the Turkish Empire, which, just a year ago, sought a loan from France. In exchange, the French demanded concessions in railway construction, industrial development, and control over customs as collateral. Turkey would have faced such humiliation had it not been for loans extended by Germany and our monarchy. If Turkey had its own financial institutions, it would not have needed to rely on the French, Germans, or Austrians. While Turkey does have the Ottoman Bank, it is not a domestic institution in essence. Despite its local name, it was founded with foreign capital—mainly French and British. Similarly, in Bosnia, we also have major financial institutions, but they, too, operate on foreign capital rather than our own Muslim resources. Therefore, I reiterate the urgent necessity of establishing a domestic Islamic financial institution. It is vital that we set aside political divisions and refrain from involving party politics in economic endeavors. Instead, we must unite and work collectively to achieve this goal.

The speech of Ademaga Mešić was greeted by all members of the meeting, except Šaćir Pandža, who supported the initiative of Esad Kulović. On 02.07.1911, a group led by Ademaga Mešić unanimously

condemned the initiative of Esad Kulović, who enjoyed the support of Halid-beg Hrasnica. Namely, both worked on the project of a small money office with a founding capital of 600,000 K. In their proclamation, Ademaga's group vehemently attacked them:

If there is no other benefit of our unification negotiations other than establishing the joint bank, that outcome would be enough because our economic independence would help us gain strength. It is not harsh to say that it is a crime to stand against this bank by undermining negotiations or establishing "mini party's banks," which will become nothing other than prey to foreign parasites that have taken away our economic strength until now. What to say then for those who oppose the foundation of joint Muslim bank, because that step would contribute to the political unity of Muslims in Bosnia and Herzegovina. What cynicism they show! One who does not possess enough moral strength and patriotic Islamic sentiment to subordinate his petty ambitions and personal gains for the cause of the progress of Muslims should be stigmatized by people and deprived of their support in public life. What else could it be other than petty ambitions and personal benefits, which stand in the way of unity of brothers of the same religion who find themselves in a difficult situation? Muslims in Bosnia and Herzegovina can only benefit if political unity is achieved and a joint bank is established; they have nothing to lose.

One month later, political unity was achieved. MPO and MIP merged into United Muslim Organization (*Ujedinjena muslimanska organizacija*). Halid-beg Hrasnica was against it, and he offered his resignation (STAV, 2017).

So, after more than one year of intra-party fights on political unity and the purpose of the Muslim bank, Ademaga Mešić won the argument, thereby facilitating the groundwork for establishing this institution.

4.3.2. Statute

On the very first day of 1912, the statute of the future Muslim Central Bank and the names of founders were published in the *Sarajevski list* as depicted in figure 5:

It is essential to mention that a discussion on the statute emerged in the bank committee meeting in April 1910. Namely, Esad Kulović and Halid Hrasnica were assigned to look into statutes of leading banks in Bosnia and Herzegovina in order to prepare one for the Muslim Central Bank. At the meeting in May 1911, Esad Kulović introduced a bank statute, but according to his preferences (600,000 K of founding capital, 6 000 shares).

In the statute (Fig. 5), all relevant details related to the operations of the future bank are given. In the very beginning, it is emphasized that this statute is created according to rules prescribed by Commercial law. In 20 articles, the primary business operations of the bank are explained. Further, the founding capital of 3,000,000 K is approved by issuing 30,000 shares, each costing 100 K. Price of the share could be paid in installments (10 K immediately, 20 K latest by two months after constitutive assembly, 70 K in the future according to the instruction of the management). The plan was for the bank to start its operations after 900,000 K is collected.

Below the statute is the list of founders. The list consists of 25 people, most of them being Muslim members of the Diet (*sabornici*). We also find a few landowners and merchants on the list. The Mayor of Sarajevo is also undersigned together with the director of *waqf* (endowment) and veterinarian.

Figure 5: Statute of Muslim Central Bank

Društvena osnova

Muslimanske Centralne Banke za Bosnu i Hercegovinu

(dioničarskog društva) u Sarajevu.

Podpisani osnivaju po propisima trgovačkog zakona za Bosnu i Hercegovinu — dioničarsko trgovačko društvo pod imenom „Muslimanska Centralna Banka za Bosnu i Hercegovinu“ (dioničarsko društvo) sa sjedištem u Sarajevu.

Ovo se društvo sastavlja na neograničeno vrijeme.

U skladu sa zakonom spadaju: da trguje novcem i papirima od vrijednosti, da pristuplje kapitalu, da unaprijedi i kreditom potpomaže zemljoradnju, trgovinu, obrt i industriju, da podize i vrši promet sa nepokretnostima, da izdaje i u promet stavlja papire od vrijednosti.

Prema tome će društvo:

1. primiti novac na priplod i štednje;
2. osmišljati i izdati i tražiti, isto tako varante, izručene državne obveznice, srebrne, kupone itd. Mjenice, koje bude društvo osmišljalo, mogu biti sa gruntnom osiguranjem ili bez njega; mogu glasiti na dan ili na strani valuti, ali ne smiju glasiti na duži rok od šest mjeseci. Na njima moraju biti najmanje dva solventna potpisna, ali ravnateljstvo može dozvoliti iznimke;
3. davati zajmove na državne papire i druge papire od vrijednosti, koje ravnateljstvo nagje da se sigurni;
4. davati zajmove na tekuće račune (Conto-Corrent) na podlozi ili hipotekne ili drugih papira od vrijednosti koje ravnateljstvo nagje da se sigurni ili na podlozi kojeg drugog osiguranja;
5. davati zajmove na robu, zlato, srebro i dragocjenosti; s ovom gruntnom posla (zalaganjem) moći će društvo otpočeti po prethodnom odobrenju nadležne vlasti;
6. kupovati i prodavati svakovrsne papire od vrijednosti, devize, kovani novac, robu, sirovine i druge predmete za tuži račun;
7. kupovati i prodavati na vlastiti račun papire od vrijednosti, koji nose interes i koje ravnateljstvo nagje da se sigurni, kao i obveznice, koje glase na glavnica ili amortizne iznose sa posrednom ili neposrednom državnom garancijom;
8. baviti se s transportnim i špedicionim poslovima;
9. davati zajmove na nepokretnosti uz gruntno osiguranje;
10. vršiti sve bankove i mjenjačke poslove kao i svakovrsne uplate i naplate za tuži račun;
11. davati kredit pojedincima zemalja, zemljoradnicima i zemljoradničkim zajednicama u svrhu unapređenja njihove privrede, na podlozi hipotekne, ručnog zaloga, ili kojeg drugog osiguranja;
12. osnivati, organizovati i rukovoditi kreditna i privredna društva i udruženja, zadruge i saveze, konorzije i druge ustanove i poduzeća u interesu poboljšanja i podizanja zemljoradnje, poljske i šumarske privrede, obrade i prometa sa zemljoradničkim i šumarskim proizvodima, davati im i nabavljati kredit, nještovati u takvim poduzećima, posredovati moguću pomoć i za njih;
13. kupovati i prodavati nepokretnosti za svoje potrebe;
14. kupovati i prodavati nepokretnosti i druge predmete zemljoradnjačke i šumarske privrede, zakupljati ih, administrirati, parcelirati i kantonirati;
15. primiti na čuvanje razne ostave;
16. posredovati kod sklapanja trgovačkih poslova za tuži račun i na tuže ime;
17. osnivati, financirati i rukovoditi stovarišta i skladišta za robu i sirovine, za postrovanje zemljoradnje, industrije i obrta;
18. podizati i posredovati kod podizavanja hipotekarnih zajmova;
19. osnivati i financirati druga oživana, industrijalna i druga privatna poduzeća;

20. konačno društvo se može baviti i drugim poslovima, koji su u saglasju sa ciljem i značajem društva, i koje glavna skupština zaključio, a zemaljska vlada odobri.

Društvo ima pravo sve ove poslove vršiti samostalno i samo za svoj račun, a isto tako sve poslove preduzimati i izvajati u svezi s drugim bankama, društvima ili sličnim zavodima u zemlji, ili izvan područja Bosne i Hercegovine.

Kad će društvo otpočeti i u kom će opsegu raditi navedene poslove, i kada će s kojim poslom prestati, odlučuje ravnateljstvo.

Isključeni su svi diferencijalni poslovi i spekulacija na burzi za račun društva.

Temeljna glavnica društva predviđa se na šest milijuna kruna.

Za sada se od ove temeljne glavnice izdaje iznos od tri milijuna kruna, razdijeljen u trideset hiljada dionica po jedna stotinu kruna nominalne vrijednosti.

Dionice društva glase na ime, a kuponi na domaćinoće.

Uplata ovih dionica osigurava se upisom, a dioničarom postaje samo onaj, koga društvo primi, te bude upisan u knjigu dioničara. Prema tome potpisani osnivajući imaju pravo po potrebi pojedine upise dionica sasvim otkloniti, kao i upisani broj dionica za pojedine upisnike smanjiti, a nijesu dužni navesti razlog, zašto su to učinili. Za prenos dionica na drugu osobu, potrebno je pismeno odobrenje ravnateljstva.

Prije započeka rada ima se svaka dionica uplatiti sa trideset kruna (30) i to: deset kruna prilikom upisa, a dvadeset kruna poslije konstituirajuće glavne skupštine u roku od dva mjeseca računajući od dana, kada upis dionica bude zaključen tako, da društvo otpočne rad sa uplaćenom glavnicom od K 900,000 (devet stotina hiljada kruna). Ostalih K 70 (sedamdeset kruna) što ih treba uplatiti za svaku upisanu dionicu, plaćaju se prema razvrtku posla, kada to ravnateljstvo odredi i pronađe potrebnim.

U ime trojka oko osnivanja otpada na svaku dionica po jedna kruna, koja se imade odmah kod upisa uplatiti.

Na uplaćene iznose izdaju se upisnicima potvrde pod brojem, koji odgovara broju upisanih dionica, a pošto dionice budu potpuno uplaćene, izdaju se dioničarima stalne dionice, kad povratu potvrde.

Ko od upisnika odnosno dioničara zakasni sa uplatom, plaćaju se zakasniljenje šest posto (6%) kamata na nepoloženim svotom od dana propisanog roka za uplatu, do dana uplate. Ko ne položi uplatu za šezdeset dana, gubi upisom stečeno pravo na uplatu, koje je do tada položio, kao i na prinos za trojkove osnivanja, ali jamči i dalje u smislu § 158. trgovačkog zakona za Bosnu i Hercegovinu. Dioničari, koji zakasne s uplatom više tri puta pozvani na uplatu pisanim službenim lista bos-herc. zemaljske vlade, i to treći put barem četiri nedjelje prije zapornog roka od šezdeset dana (§ 176. trg. zakona), te će se svaki put obavijesti brojevi dionica, dionično potvrda, za koje nije uplata položena na propisani rok. Kad isteže zaporni rok od šezdeset dana, dionične se potvrde na dionice, koje ne budu uplaćene, uništavaju, a na njihovo se mjesto izdaju nove potvrde sa istim brojem, i stavljaju se u promet. Uplata za poništene potvrde, kao i višak, koji se dobije preko uplaćene vrijednosti za prodane nove dionice, snosi se u pričuveni zaklada (rezervni fond).

Izdavanje zajmova za svoje vlastite dionice, društva je sasvim zabranjeno, a svoje vlastite dionice kupovati za svoj račun, društva je dozvoljeno samo u onom slučaju, ako glavna skupština zaključio da smanji dioničku glavnica.

Dalja emisija do šest milijuna kruna izvršavaju se prema zaključku glavne skupštine društva uz odobrenje nadležne vlasti, a koliko je ovo odobrenje potrebno zbog proširenje u tekstu društvenih pravila.

Upisivanje dionica zaključuje se kroz tri mjeseca računajući od dana, a koji bude ova osnova obilježena.

U Sarajevu, dne 1. januara 1912.

<p>Ademaga Mešić potpisnik iz Tuzla</p> <p>Mahmudbeg Fadilpašić narodni potpisnik iz Sarajeva</p> <p>Ragibbeg Džinić narodni potpisnik iz Hercegovine</p> <p>Fehim ef. Čurčić potpisnik iz Sarajeva</p> <p>Dr. Safvetbeg Bašagić narodni potpisnik iz Sarajeva</p> <p>Rifatbeg Sulejmanpašić narodni potpisnik iz Hercegovine</p> <p>Pašabeg Kulenović narodni potpisnik iz Kairo-Vakufa</p> <p>Mujaga Kurtagić narodni potpisnik iz Vitepska</p>	<p>H. Salihaga Kućukatić narodni potpisnik iz Brčka</p> <p>Hasan ef. Smalibegović narodni potpisnik iz Tuzla</p> <p>Ševkija Gluhic narodni potpisnik iz Tuzla</p> <p>Ahmed Mehmedbašić narodni potpisnik iz Sarajeva</p> <p>Mustajbeg Mutevelić narodni potpisnik iz Sarajeva</p> <p>Bećir Mehmedbašić narodni potpisnik iz Mostara</p> <p>Suljaga Vajzović narodni potpisnik iz Bosanske</p> <p>Omer ef. Čirkinagić narodni potpisnik iz Plovanja</p> <p>Čamil Karamehmedović narodni potpisnik iz Trebnja</p>	<p>Dr. Hamdija Karamehmedović narodni potpisnik iz Sarajeva</p> <p>Mustajbeg Halilbašić narodni potpisnik iz Sarajeva</p> <p>Ahmedaga Henda potpisnik iz Sarajeva</p> <p>Semsibeg Salihbegović gradski načelnik iz Sarajeva</p> <p>Asimaga H. Šabanović vještovodnik i inženjer iz Sarajeva</p> <p>Sulejmanbeg Sulejmanpašić vještovodnik iz Sarajeva</p> <p>Hamdibeg Džinić vještovodnik iz Vitepska</p> <p>Šerif Arnautović vakefski direktor iz Sarajeva</p>
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Source: Sarajevski list (1912, no.11, p.6)

4.3.3. Subscription of shares and official establishment

The call for the subscription of shares was open for three months until 31.03.1912. However, this call was extended since Ademaga traveled abroad during this period. Thus, we can see that Ademaga played a crucial role in the nascent phase of this institution.

Ademaga sold 1,000 shares (total 30,000) on the very first day of a call. The most extensive support came from the middle and lower-middle-class in Sarajevo and Krajina. That is unsurprising because even before the bank was founded, Ademaga vowed to travel all around Bosnia and Herzegovina to convince Muslims to buy the Muslim Central Bank shares.

So, the first six months of 1912 were used to promote the bank and subscriptions of shares. According to Ademaga's statement from March 1912, *"almost all shares are sold, and the bank will start its operations as soon as possible."*

A general constitutive assembly was held on 07.07.1912. According to the Joint Ministry of Finance decree on 31.07.1912, the name (Muslim Central Bank) and the legal form (joint-stock company) were approved.

The bank officially launched its operations on 02.09.1912. Mahmud-beg Fadilpašić was chosen as president, while Ademaga Mešić and Rifat-beg Sulejmanpašić were chosen as vice presidents.

Opening the bank was considered a milestone for the Muslim community in Bosnia and Herzegovina, while the negative role of usurers and small money offices was emphasized. Further, Muslims were called to provide support for a bank by either buying shares of this bank or taking loans.

In one article, an analysis of bank operations and its mission is discussed. It is argued that the bank gained trust in a relatively short time despite the financial crisis. Namely, only three months after its establishment, the Muslim Central Bank loaned more than 500,000 K. The Muslim Central Bank was the youngest bank compared to its counterparts (Serbian and Croatian banks). Thus, from an economic point of view, Muslims have been latecomers, too. Taking this into account, the bank's primary mission was to *"attract Muslim capital and use it for the benefit of Muslims because it is well-known that Muslims are the most backward when it comes to economic matters."*

The opportunity for growth was seen in cooperation with the Provincial government, which granted a concession to sell and export coal to all "national" banks. However, an enormous opportunity was seen in money coming from the optional ransoming of serfs since Muslims were mainly landowners. Consequently, the Muslim Central Bank aimed to play a crucial role as a protector of Muslim economic interests, particularly for those who were inexperienced, as their lack of knowledge could result in losing money and land if their funds were not deposited in the bank.

According to the decree of the Provincial government on 22.02.1913, no. 20594/III-3, the Muslim Central Bank was accredited as an institution for the deposit of orphan money (money of minors).

4.3.4. Assemblies

A call to participate in the first general assembly was published in the Sarajevski list. The assembly was held on the premises of the bank on 10.05.1914. Business results of 1913 were analyzed, and subsequent election of 4 members to Management and Board of Directors.

The second general assembly was held on 09.05.1915. It was emphasized that the outbreak of WWI did not have a significant effect on the bank's operations.

The third general assembly meeting was conducted on 29.04.1916. Once again, it was emphasized that war circumstances did not substantially influence the bank's activities. Also, the director of the Croat Central Bank was elected in Management, so we can understand this step in the context of strategic political cooperation between Croats and Muslims, which A-H supported. A dividend of 5% was distributed to shareholders in contrast to 4%, which was the case in previous years. Interestingly, Ademaga Mešić showed up in the lieutenant uniform at the assembly, where he called Muslims to express loyalty to A-H through a subscription of war bonds. The fourth general assembly was convened on 12.05.1917. During this assembly, the establishment of pension funds for bank employees was discussed. At the fifth general assembly held on 04.05.1918, it was agreed to increase the bank's share capital from 3,000,000 K to 5,000,000 K.

Figure 6: Call to the first general assembly of the Muslim Central Bank

Source: Sarajevski list (1914, no.79, p.8)

4.3.5. Government support

As we have already mentioned, the government intended to keep the *status quo* regarding political and economic situation in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Since Muslims lagged behind their countrymen in economic development, there was a fear that the existing balance could be disrupted. Therefore, the existence of the Muslim bank and its successful operations were of the utmost importance to A-H.

Provincial governor Oskar Potiorek and Joint Minister of Finance Leon Bilinski played a significant role in supporting this nascent institution of Bosnian Muslims. First, they mapped out strategic cooperation between the Muslim Central Bank and the Austrian Länderbank. They were also working on establishing a specific mortgage office for Muslim landowners with the financial support of the above-mentioned Austrian bank since the Muslim Central Bank did not have its own mortgage office. However, this initiative failed (Juzbašić, 2002). In return, the Muslim Central Bank agitated for the A-H government among Bosnian Muslims. This is best exemplified in the case of war loans. Namely, the Muslim Central Bank requested Bosnian Muslims to show their loyalty and economic patriotism to A-H. From 1914 to 1917, the Muslim Central Bank sold over 10,000,000 K government war bonds.

4.3.6. Operations of the Bank

The following table gives an overview of the bank's operations in 5 years. As we can see from the table above, net profit and deposits increased every year in this period. The net profit/share capital ratio also experienced a steady increase. The share capital was constant for four years (c. 1,500,000 K). This was probably due to war.

Table 2: Net profit, share capital and deposit of Muslim Central Bank (1913-1917)

YEAR	NET PROFIT	SHARE CAPITAL	NET PROFIT/SHARE CAPITAL	DEPOSIT
1913	36,060 K	515,143 K	7%	1,400,000 K
1914	126,245 K	1,485,235 K	8.5%	1,500,000 K
1915	219,866 K	1,516,317 K	14.5%	3,088,465 K
1916	257,484 K	1,497,000 K	17.2%	5,261,133 K
1917	262,133 K	1,497,902 K	17.5%	7,403,316 K

Source: Author's own representation based on Biser (1918, no.11 & 12, pp. 189-190)

Usually, profits were distributed according to the following pattern: 10% for reserve requirements, 10% to Management, and the rest according to conclusions of assembly, e.g., dividends, board of directors, pension fund, and humanitarian causes (Galijašević, 1999).

However, 1918 brought a strategic change. In the context of expansion strategy, the District Court in Sarajevo approved establishing the branch office in Tuzla on 23.02.1918. The plan to increase share capital to 5,000,00 K was announced in the context of post-war expectations since the bank wanted to strengthen its financial position to play a vital role in reconstruction and development. A call to the subscription of an additional 20,000 shares (each worth 100 K) was published on 28.09.1918. There was no option for installment payments.

Also, existing shareholders had priority in buying new shares. The subscription period lasted from 1.10.1918 to 15.12.1918. The share capital of 2,000,000 K was collected in this period, so the bank entered 1919 with 5,000,000 K. In 1920, deposits were more than 11,000,000 K. In 1923, the Muslim Central Bank merged with the Croat Savings Bank into Union Bank (Imamović, 2007).

Figure 7: Income statement of Muslim Bank in Banja Luka (1913)

Rashod.		Račun gubitka i dobitka				Prihod.			
	K	h	K	h		K	h	K	h
Upravni troškovi:					Mjenični kamati . . .			103.973	87
beriva, stanarina, tis-					Kamati tekućeg računa			18.336	71
kanice, ogrijev, raz-					Proviđba . . .			28.806	31
svieta, nadzorna pri-					Prenos dobitka iz godine			1.015	60
stojba, porez, sreska					1912				
bolesnička blagajna,									
nagrada, biljegovne									
pristojbe, pristojbe na									
kamate štedovnih ulo-									
žaka, općinski namet									
			23.905	26					
Kamati štedovnih uložaka			24.798	08					
Kamati recskonta . . .			52.130	92					
Otpis namještaja . . .			1.054	72					
Prenos dobitka iz godine									
1912	1.015	60							
Čisti dobitak	49.227	91	50.243	51					
			152.132	49				152.132	49

U Banjoj Luci, dne 31. decembra 1913. P/20 1-1

Ravnatelj: Viktor Prohaska v. r. Za knjigovodstvo: Besim Alihodžić v. r.

Predsjednik: Ragibbeg Džinić v. r. Ravnateljstvo: Potpredsjednik: Hamzaga Husedjinović v. r.

Source: Sarajevski list (1914, no.11, p.8)

4.4. Muslim Bank in Banja Luka

This institution started its operations on 15.11.1911. In total, 2,000 shares were issued (each worth 100 K), so that share capital was 200,000 K. The bank's director was Ragib-beg Džinić, who was also a member of the Diet and one of the founders of the Muslim Central Bank. Viktor Prochaska was appointed as managing director. By decree of the District Court in Banja Luka on 10.01.1913, the opening of the bank's branch office in Prijedor was approved.

The net profit of the Muslim Bank in Banja Luka was 49,227 K at the end of 1913 (*Figure 8*). During the first year of the war (1914), the total share capital of 200,000 K was successfully collected.

Figure 8: Income statement of Muslim Bank in Banja Luka (1914)

Rashod.		Račun dobitka i gubitka.				Prihod.			
		K	h	K	h			K	h
Upravni troškovi: beriva, poštarine i brojavi, biljezi, telefon, stanarina, rasvjeta, ogriev, novine i oglasi, podvornička odijela, esignarnja, milodari, nadzorna pristojba, porez, nagrade, općinski namet, poslovne knjige, tiskalice i pisaci pribor, putni troškovi i dnevnice, sreska bolesnička blagajna, biljegovne pristojbe, pristojbe na kamate štedovnih uložaka, popravci na nekretninama i namještaju, razno				32.472	40	Prenos dobitka iz godine 1913.		2.380	04
Kamati na štedovne uložke				31.320	45	Mjenični kamati		122.065	26
Kamati reeskonta				63.671	81	Kamati tekućeg računa		21.350	39
Otpisi: od nekretnina		1.220	39			Kamati od vrijednosnih papira		120	—
od namještaja		1.081	70	2.302	09	Providba		37.510	46
Prenos dobitka iz godine 1913.		2.380	04						
Čisti dobitak		51.259	36	58.639	40				
				183.406	15			183.406	15

U Banjoj Luci, dne 31. decembra 1914.

Viktor Prochaska v. r. upravljajući ravnatelj.

Stjepan Horvat v. r. nadknjigovođa.

Ravnateljstvo:

Hamzaga Husedjinović v. r. Podpredsjednik:

Predsjednik: Ragibbeg Djinić v. r.

Source: Sarajevski list (1915, no.66, p.5)

In 1914, the net profit was 51,259 K, as shown in *Figure 9*. This was an incremental increase in profits in comparison to 1913.

At the same time, although the war and post-war period were highly challenging, the bank's share capital quadrupled until 1920. Moreover, at the extraordinary general assembly convened on 31.03.1920, it was decided to increase share capital from 800 000 K to 2,000,000 K by issuing 12,000 shares (each worth 100 K).

4.5. First Muslim Bank in Brčko

The First Muslim Bank in Brčko (Prva muslimanska banka u Brčkom) was the very first bank established by Bosnian Muslims. Share capital amounted to 200,000 K. Abdaga Kučukalić became president, while Mujaga Pašalić was appointed as director. The bank officially launched its operations in 1908. However, the bank's promotion started one year earlier. In February 1907, an appeal was published in the magazine Bošnjak. Initially, it was argued that non-Muslims had already taken all necessary steps to establish similar institutions. Also, the impact of these institutions on economic progress and society was emphasized. Further, the rationale behind the establishment of Muslim banks was explained. Ultimately, Muslims were asked to support their future bank by buying shares. It was decided to issue 2,500 shares (each worth 100 K), so that total share capital amounted to 250,000 K. Meanwhile, the net profit in 1916 was 42,014 K.

Figure 9: Income statement of the First Muslim Bank in Brčko (1916)

Gubitak		Račun dobitka i gubitka na dan 31. decembra 1916.				Dobitak	
	K	h	K	h		K	h
Kamati:					Prenos dobitka od god. 1915.		9.091 37
Prenosi, povraćeni, na stež. uloške i tekući račun			75.372	43	Kamati i razna provi- zija	134.784	86
Troškovi:					Kamati vrijed. papira	4.150	—
Plaće, dnevnice, tiska- nice i razno			17.958	05	Prihod od nekretnina	1.200	—
Porez			9.783	21			
Razne pristojbe			2.097	73			
Otpisi:							
od nekretnina	1.000	—					
od namještaja	1.000	—	2.000	—			
Čisti dobitak			42.014	61			
			149.226	03		149.226	03

Source: Sarajevski list (1917, no.27, p.4)

4.6. First Muslim Merchant Bank in Bijeljina

The First Muslim Merchant Bank in Bijeljina (Prva muslimanska trgovačka banka u Bijeljini) was founded in 1910. The share capital was 200,000 K and the net profit in 1913 was 25,809 K, as shown in Figure 10.

4.7. Muslim Credit Bank in Foča

The Muslim Credit Bank in Foča (Muslimanska kreditna banka u Foči) was founded in 1911. The share capital also amounted to 200,000 K.

Constitutive assembly was held on 19.05.1911. The Joint Ministry of Finance adopted its statute on 18.07.1911 by decree no. 10.605. Based on that, the District Court in Sarajevo approved the registration of the bank in the commercial register on 12.09.1911. In total, 4,000 shares were issued (each worth 50 K). In October 1911, the Muslim Credit Bank in Foča advertised vacant branch manager and trainee positions in Goražde.

Figure 10: Income statement of the First Muslim Merchant Bank in Bijeljina (1913)

Račun gubitka i dobitka na 31. decembra 1913.									
Gubitci.				Dobitci.					
	K	h	K	h		K	h	K	h
Kamati:					Prenos dobitka iz god. 1912.			301	76
na štedovne nloške . . .	5.139	57			Kamati na mjenice i tekuće račune . . .			51.346	65
na reskont . . .	21.395	07			Provizija . . .			15.271	42
na tekuće račune . . .	827	92	27.562	66	Razni prihodi . . .			686	87
Troškovi:									
Plaće, najamnina, porez, tiskanice, pristojbe i razni troškovi . . .			12.966	61					
Otpisi:									
od utemeljujućih troškova . . .	450	—							
od namjestaža . . .	718	26	1.168	26					
Cisti dobitak . . .			25.809	27					
			67.506	70				67.506	70

Source: Sarajevski list (1914, no.46, p.7)

4.8. Muslim Savings Banks

4.8.1. Muslim Savings Bank in Banja Luka

It was founded in 1911. The share capital was 200,000 K. Hamdi-beg Džinić was elected as president.

4.8.2. Muslim Savings Bank in Bijeljina

It was founded in 1911. The share capital was 100,000 K. Alibeg Pašić was elected as president.

4.8.3. Muslim Savings Bank in Stolac

It was founded in 1911. The share capital was 100,000 K. Hasan Šehić was president, and the managing director was Ivo P. Tedeschi. Interestingly, Hasan Šehić was a Muslim cleric (*efendija, imam*).

4.8.4. Muslim Savings Bank in Zenica

It was founded in 1909. The share capital was 60,000 K. The President was Osmanaga Mehmedić, while the managing director was Kosta Petrović. In 1916, this saving office was liquidated.

4.8.5. Muslim Savings Bank in Foča

In one ad published in the magazine *Bošnjak*, we see that this saving office had operated already in 1907. It offered 5% interest on deposits. However, we also noticed that this savings office started its liquidation process in January 1913. A deadline of 6 months was given to creditors of the Muslim Savings Office in Foča to claim their receivables.

4.9. Muslim Credit Cooperatives

The First Muslim Peasant Cooperative (*Prva muslimanska seljačka zadruga*) was founded in Šije near Tešanj in 1910. The Constitutional assembly was held on 15.04.1910. Its president was Suljo Kruško.

The Cooperative had over 100 members. It also charged interest on loans and paid interest on deposits (Galijašević, 1999).

It is also noteworthy to mention the following credit cooperatives: Muslim Peasant Credit Cooperative in Ćurevo near Foča (1911), Muslim Savings Credit Cooperative in Kula Fazlagića near Gacko (1911), and Islamic Credit Cooperative for Craft, Commerce and Industry in Čajniče (1912).

5. CONCLUSION

This research investigated the establishment of modern financial institutions during the A-H rule. To provide a genuine report of the period in which this process happened, a short overview of circumstances in the late Ottoman Bosnia and Herzegovina was presented. With the A-H occupation, a new epoch for Bosnian Muslims has started. A cultural and political revival followed the initial disorientation of Muslims at the beginning of the 20th century. The rivalry between Muslim political factors and the general backwardness of Muslims had a tremendous effect on the economic revival. The personality of Ademaga Mešić, the leader of so-called progressive Muslims, takes the greatest credit for establishing modern financial institutions. As an experienced merchant, he understood the importance of credit as a catalyst for economic development. The establishment and evolution of financial institutions like the First Muslim Credit Cooperative, the Muslim Merchant and Agricultural Bank, and the Muslim Central Bank in Bosnia and Herzegovina reflect the aspirations of the Muslim community to enhance their economic independence amidst challenging social, political, and economic circumstances in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. A-H also played a constructive role in developing these institutions after liberalization measures took place in 1903.

The emergence of Islamic modernism coincided with the establishment of modern financial institutions in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Arguments used for the adoption of interest-based banking were to move forward, to progress, to not lag behind the civilized world, to be children of the time, to save land and capital, to fight against foreign capital, and to step into a secure future. Consequently, the whole process of establishing modern financial institutions was a rather reactive and defensive step. Ultimately, these institutions symbolized a significant step toward economic empowerment and resilience for the Bosnian Muslims in Bosnia and Herzegovina. They embodied the broader struggle for financial independence, social upliftment, and cultural solidarity during a transformative era in the country's history. Their establishment laid a foundation for future financial endeavors and demonstrated the potential of collective action in overcoming systemic economic challenges.

Declarations

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Harmonizing Economic Growth with Environmental Justice: Circular Manufacturing Pathway

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ABSTRACT

The global challenge of harmonizing economic growth with environmental sustainability has become a critical issue, particularly within the manufacturing sector. This paper explores the potential of circular economy principles as a pathway to achieving a sustainable manufacturing transition that not only promotes economic development but also ensures environmental justice. By analyzing the synergies and tensions between economic growth, environmental sustainability, and social equity, the paper highlights the role of circular manufacturing in creating resource-efficient, low-waste systems. Key findings show that while circular manufacturing holds substantial potential for enhancing economic growth, job creation, and industrial competitiveness, significant barriers remain, including economic costs, technological gaps, and political and social resistance. Moreover, achieving environmental justice in this transition is essential to ensure that marginalized communities are not disproportionately affected by pollution and waste. The paper emphasizes the need for innovative policies, collaborative governance, and inclusive strategies to overcome these challenges and design equitable supply chains and manufacturing systems. Future research should focus on scaling circular practices across industries, addressing regional disparities, and developing technologies that further reduce the environmental footprint of manufacturing.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Digitalization in manufacturing will be fueled by disruptive technologies as part of a broader ecosystem shift. Businesses worldwide are undergoing digital transformation, which is transforming manufacturing for the future. Digital designs, fabrication, use, operation, and after-sales servitization are driving this change in manufacturing, which also includes the management of manufacturing supply chains and the transformation of factory operations and processes. Organizations can accomplish what was previously only a dream by combining advanced modeling and simulation, data collection, analysis, and reporting, as well as advancements in manufacturing and imaging. The Internet of Things (IoT) was made possible by the combination of sensors and software that enables devices to communicate with one another.

One of the biggest worldwide issues of our day is balancing environmental sustainability with economic growth. Economic systems still primarily rely on resource-intensive, linear production models that worsen environmental degradation, despite the fact that many countries have made commitments to switch to renewable energy and lower their carbon footprints. The Grantham Research Institute asserts that switching to low-carbon energy sources and circular economy principles is necessary to decouple economic growth from greenhouse gas emissions in order to achieve

sustainable growth (GRICCE, 2024). This strategy synchronizes economic activity with the world-wide objectives of preserving natural resources and reducing climate change.

A key driver of economic expansion, the manufacturing sector also contributes significantly to waste, pollution, and greenhouse gas emissions. Many of these effects are frequently felt by marginalized communities, who face financial hardships and health hazards. By guaranteeing an equitable distribution of environmental benefits and burdens, incorporating environmental justice into manufacturing practices helps to address these disparities. To protect vulnerable communities and workers, for instance, programs like the European Union's Just Transition Mechanism offer financial and technical assistance to areas most impacted by industrial shifts (EC, 2024).

The Circular Economy provide revolutionary ways to address the twin objectives of environmental justice and economic growth. These concepts decrease waste and prolong the life of materials by rethinking systems to give priority to resource efficiency, reuse, and recycling. Key practices such as industrial symbiosis—where waste from one process becomes a resource for another—demonstrate the potential of circular models to align economic productivity with sustainability objectives. The United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) emphasizes that implementing these strategies can enhance global competitiveness while meeting environmental goals (UNIDO, 2024).

This paper aims to explore the intersection of economic growth, environmental justice, and circular manufacturing. It addresses the following key questions:

1. How can circular economy strategies mitigate environmental inequities in manufacturing regions?
2. What are the economic and environmental benefits of adopting circular models?
3. What collaborative approaches among policymakers, industries, and communities can accelerate this transition?

By examining selected case studies, analysing policy frameworks, and presenting innovative practices, this research aims to provide actionable insights for fostering equitable and sustainable industrial growth.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Manufacturing offers opportunities that add value to the nation and benefit society more broadly, rather than just producing goods or production. It frequently entails a great deal of innovation (increasing research and development, productivity), and it also produces highly skilled, high-paying jobs. Manufacturing, “with its strong role on exports and import substitutions,” can help rebalance the economy, according to economic theory (Mohamed, 2021). The same data can be utilized internally within the manufacturer's organization to optimize processes related to products and services. While the behavioural insights team can find additional user-related prospects, the product design team may benefit from the usage patterns and analytics of the product to further optimize features and design. Above all, the digitization of physical goods can create a way to interact and provide feedback after the initial product or service is sold. This strengthens the bond between the two parties and increases client loyalty and trust.

Lastly, remotely-connected products enable easier tracking throughout the lifetime of the product, its resale activities and project its eventual retirement, possibly to be exchanged for an upgraded model. The closure of production to ‘end-of-life’ cycle is especially important as we deal with high digital waste and the advent of the Circular Economy.

2.1. Economic Growth and Environmental Sustainability

Economic growth, which is frequently gauged by indicators like GDP, industrial output, and job creation, has long been regarded as a country's top priority. This expansion has historically been linked to patterns of resource extraction, production, and consumption that usually ignore social inequalities and environmental constraints. The advantages of economic expansion were not always shared equally, and marginalized groups—particularly those in low-income areas or among indigenous populations—were disproportionately affected by environmental deterioration. These communities have been disproportionately affected by industrial operations like mining, manufacturing, and waste disposal, which has resulted in what is now known as environmental injustice (Maru, 2023). Because polluting industries are frequently found in areas with less political clout or financial means to oppose them, there is a greater risk of air and water pollution, exposure to toxic waste, and other environmental hazards.

Proponents of environmental justice call for a paradigm change that does not put economic expansion ahead of the environment or marginalized communities (Global Witness, 2022). In order to guarantee that no community experiences disproportionate environmental harm as a result of economic activity, the idea of environmental justice places a strong emphasis on the equitable distribution of environmental benefits and burdens. This viewpoint contradicts conventional economic growth models, which have frequently disregarded the costs of advancement to society and the environment.

The “Sustainability Window” approach (Figure 1), which establishes the acceptable limits of economic growth required to preserve environmental stability while attaining social equity, is one of several theoretical frameworks that have been used to study the relationship between economic growth and environmental sustainability. This model, which is based on the theory of sustainable development (Purvis et al, 2019), combines economic, social, and environmental indicators to examine possible trade-offs and synergies and provide policymakers with useful information (Luukkanen et al, 2024). Because of resource-intensive production techniques, economic development and environmental objectives have frequently clashed in the past.

Figure 1: Determining the Sustainability Window in a case where the actual GDP output is within the Sustainability Window ($GDP_{min} < GDP_1 < GDP_{max}$).

Source: Luukkanen et al, (2024).

Nonetheless, synergies are becoming more and more apparent, especially in industries implementing cutting-edge green technologies. Data from the World Economic Forum, for example, shows

how developments in carbon capture, sustainable energy storage, and circular economy techniques are changing the growth paradigm by lowering environmental impacts and promoting economic innovation (WEF, 2024).

2.2. Environmental Justice in Manufacturing

Regardless of race, socioeconomic status, or geographic location, environmental justice guarantees equitable treatment and meaningful participation of all individuals in environmental decision-making. It includes addressing worker safety, community health effects, and pollution disparities in the manufacturing context. Protecting underprivileged populations that are disproportionately harmed by industrial operations is part of this (Fabozzi et al, 2022).

The varying effects of manufacturing on communities are demonstrated by case studies from industrial areas. For instance, by offering targeted financial and structural support, programs such as the European Union’s Just Transition Mechanism (Figure 2) demonstrate the potential to mitigate negative effects on vulnerable populations (Desai, 1994). Similar initiatives are being carried out all over the world, with manufacturing hubs prioritizing cleaner production methods and greener technologies.

Figure 2: European Union’s Just Transition Mechanism

Source: European Commission (2024).

2.3. Circular Economy Framework

The Circular Economy is a revolutionary approach to economic growth that emphasizes sustainability and resource efficiency. Its foundation is based on three fundamental ideas: minimizing waste and pollution, preserving materials and products, and restoring natural systems. This model promotes regenerative systems that put sustainability and longevity first, challenging the conventional linear economy. Manufacturing waste outputs are being greatly reduced by increasingly popular practices like closed-loop recycling and industrial symbiosis (Hoffrén, 2001; Fabozzi et al, 2022).

Through programs like modular design, which makes products easy to repair and recycle, the manufacturing industry has successfully adopted circular principles. For instance, the implementation of industrial symbiosis in Scandinavian nations shows how waste from one industry can be used as a resource for another, maximizing resource utilization and minimizing environmental effects (Desai, 1994; Hoffrén, 2001).

By combining these ideas, it creates a fundamental comprehension of the interrelated opportunities and problems at the nexus of circular manufacturing, environmental justice, and economic growth.

2.4. Circular Manufacturing

A strong substitute for conventional linear production systems is provided by circular manufacturing, which is a component of the larger circular economy model. Resources are taken, used, and then thrown away as waste in a linear economy, frequently with little regard for the effects on the environment and society. Instead of throwing away materials and products, circular manufacturing aims to close the loop of product life cycles by reusing, recycling, and refurbishing them. In order to better align with the concepts of environmental justice, this model seeks to minimize waste, reduce resource consumption, and lessen environmental impacts (see Figure 3).

By encouraging sustainable business practices that generate long-term value rather than immediate profits, circular manufacturing contributes to economic growth. For instance, manufacturers can develop closed-loop systems that lessen dependency on virgin materials by designing products that are easily disassembled for recycling or reused. In the long run, this lowers expenses because companies save money on waste disposal and the purchase of raw materials, in addition to conserving natural resources. Additionally, circular practices can open up new markets and encourage innovation, which will result in the creation of jobs in industries like waste management, recycling, and remanufacturing. Therefore, incorporating circular principles into manufacturing processes can promote sustainable economic growth while minimizing environmental impact and ensuring more equitable distribution of economic benefits.

Figure 3: Circular manufacturing where materials are reused, repurposed, and recycled.

Source: <https://ctitool.com/circular-economy-materials/>

Through increasing resource efficiency and encouraging innovation, circular manufacturing makes a substantial contribution to economic growth. It could produce a significant amount of economic value (Siderius & Zink, 2022). For example, adopting circular practices in industries like cement and steel could cut the world's material demand by as much as 20% by 2050, which would save money in the long run and ease environmental strains (IEA, 2020). Furthermore, it is projected that circular initiatives will generate millions of jobs worldwide, with 4.8 million new jobs in Latin

America and the Caribbean by 2030, primarily in the reuse, repair, and recycling sectors (Calisto Friant et al, 2023). By implementing circular economy roadmaps, cities like London and Amsterdam anticipate thousands of new jobs and significant economic benefits, proving the scalability and profitability of this approach (GRICCE, 2024).

3. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative methodology to investigate how circular economy tactics can balance environmental justice and economic growth in manufacturing sectors. Environmental economics (Fabozzi et al, 2022), socio-ecological systems theory (Siderius & Zink, 2022), and circular economy models (Think2030, 2024) are all incorporated into the analytical framework.

The method was chosen to address the multifaceted nature of the research questions, and the chosen case studies and policy analyses offer contextual knowledge that captures the intricacies of putting circular strategies into practice and their effects on society. This strategy is in line with sustainability research best practices, which place an emphasis on integrating various viewpoints and data sources to produce useful results.

Although qualitative research employing policy and case study analysis is a potent methodology, there are a number of possible drawbacks. Case study results are frequently context-specific and might be difficult to extrapolate to different contexts. This is because every case is different and depends on its circumstances. Different political, social, and economic contexts impact policy decisions, making it difficult to extrapolate findings to other jurisdictions or periods of time. Evaluation and criticism of policies can be subjective, particularly if the interpretation of the objectives or results of the policy is influenced by ideological or value-based preferences. It can be challenging to separate the direct effects of policies from other influencing factors because they frequently interact with external variables. Both methods involve synthesizing complex information, which can lead to oversimplification or omission of critical variables, especially when involving space or time constraints.

4. THE INTERSECTION OF ECONOMIC GROWTH, ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE, AND CIRCULAR MANUFACTURING

It is necessary to support programs that link local innovation projects under public initiatives with the technical expertise of industries and research at universities. Although manufacturing generates value from raw materials, material innovation still plays a major role in manufacturing technology, science, and economic policy because it supplies the “work” for manufacturing. The most inventive areas in the manufacturing sector are successful because of both factors. Certain industries have demonstrated exceptional potential to be positioned as leaders of cyber-physical systems (CPS) initiatives, particularly the automotive and smart city sectors. It is becoming increasingly clear that the new data-enhanced manufacturing requires a skilled workforce as the production floor transitions to CPS and a more integrated IoT environment. The next-generation intelligent manufacturing model could be halted by the lack of qualified personnel.

Governments must constantly retrain workers and continuously entice young, adaptable individuals to pursue STEM (science, technology, engineering, math) and data science courses in order to meet the demand for a highly skilled and talented workforce. Authorities can concentrate on luring and utilizing mobile talent through special international work visas in areas where there is an urgent, severe labour shortage in new manufacturing environments. Technology transfer is another policy that may be taken into consideration, particularly when it comes to training current employees to analyse Big Manufacturing Data. It is possible to implement supplemental programs like apprenticeships, ongoing vocational education, and worker cross-training.

Table 1: Selected Case Studies on Economic Impact from Circular Manufacturing

1. Cost Reduction through Resource Efficiency
<p>Case Study: Signify (formerly Philips Lighting) – Circular Light-as-a-Service Model. https://www.signify.com/ Philips offers “light-as-a-service,” where customers lease lighting systems instead of purchasing them outright.</p> <p>Process: Philips retains ownership of the equipment, ensures its maintenance, and takes responsibility for refurbishing and recycling components at the end of their lifecycle.</p> <p>Economic Impact: Customers reduce upfront capital expenditures.</p>
2. New Revenue Streams
<p>Case Study: Renault’s Circular Economy Business Units https://www.renaultgroup.com/en/our-commitments/environment-circular-economy/ Renault’s circular manufacturing initiatives at the Choisy-le-Roi plant generate revenue through the remanufacturing and resale of automotive parts.</p> <p>Process: Components like engines and gearboxes are collected, reconditioned, and resold at lower prices compared to new parts.</p> <p>Economic Impact: (i) Significant savings in production costs (up to 40% less compared to manufacturing new parts). (ii) Revenues generated from secondary markets for refurbished parts. (iii) Reduced material costs by reintroducing recycled content into the supply chain.</p>
3. Job Creation
<p>Case Study: Patagonia’s Worn Wear Initiative. https://wornwear.patagonia.com/ Customers can trade in old gear, which is then repaired and resold or recycled into new products.</p> <p>Process: Skilled technicians repair damaged clothing, while design teams innovate to increase product durability.</p> <p>Economic Impact: (i) Jobs created in repair centres and retail outlets. (ii) Expanded customer base attracted by sustainable and affordable refurbished products. (iii) Revenue diversification by monetizing previously unsellable items.</p>
4. Enhanced Competitiveness and Brand Value
<p>Case Study: Unilever’s Sustainable Packaging Initiatives. https://www.unilever.com/sustainability/plastics/ Unilever uses recycled and recyclable materials in its packaging to align with circular economy principles.</p> <p>Process: Investment in recycling infrastructure and partnerships to source post-consumer plastics.</p> <p>Economic Impact: (i) Reduced material costs from using recycled plastics. (ii) Increased brand loyalty and market share among environmentally aware consumers. (iii) Regulatory compliance leading to cost savings by avoiding fines and penalties.</p>
5. Risk Mitigation and Supply Chain Resilience
<p>Case Study: Apple – Daisy Recycling Robots https://www.apple.com/sg/newsroom/2022/04/apple-expands-the-use-of-recycled-materials-across-its-products/ Techniques include combining multiple wet-cycle processes, using ozone gas, and recycling water.</p> <p>Process: Valuable materials like cobalt and aluminum are extracted and reused in manufacturing new devices.</p> <p>Economic Impact: (i) Lower raw material costs due to reduced reliance on virgin materials. (ii) Stabilized supply chains by reducing vulnerability to geopolitical risks associated with mining. (iii) Significant cost savings in waste management and material sourcing.</p>
6. Increased Innovation
<p>Case Study: Interface – Modular Carpet Design. https://shop.interface.com/SEA/en-SG/carpet-tile/ The company works with the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) to ensure sustainable forestry and uses wood waste in furniture production.</p> <p>Process: Carpets are designed to be easily recyclable, and customers return used tiles for refurbishment or recycling.</p> <p>Economic Impact: (i) Reduced costs for customers by extending the usable life of installations. (ii) Continuous innovation in materials and processes enhances Interface’s market leadership. (iii) Expanded market share due to the environmentally friendly business model.</p>

Source: Author’s own.

The interaction of circular manufacturing, environmental justice, and economic growth offers both possibilities and difficulties for developing just and sustainable systems. Industrialization and resource extraction have historically been associated with economic growth, frequently at the expense of social justice and environmental health. But in recent years, there has been a movement

toward more sustainable methods, like circular manufacturing, which could bring environmental justice and economic growth together. Circular manufacturing provides a way to rethink the design, production, and consumption processes in order to foster equitable and inclusive outcomes for communities and the environment in addition to accelerating economic development.

4.1. Economic Impacts of Circular Manufacturing

Circular manufacturing not only contributes to environmental sustainability but also creates significant economic benefits by reducing costs, driving innovation, and opening new revenue streams. **Table 1** above presents key economic impacts supported by real-world case studies.

4.2. Social Impacts: Ensuring Environmental Justice

Circular manufacturing must consider the social aspects of production, though, if it is to be genuinely in line with environmental justice. This involves making certain that all communities, especially those that have historically been marginalized, can benefit from the circular economy. Creating economic opportunities and jobs in communities that have been impacted by environmental degradation is a crucial part of this. In underprivileged areas, for instance, the development of green manufacturing technologies or the expansion of recycling facilities can stimulate economic growth and local job opportunities (see **Table 2**).

Additionally, circular manufacturing provides a means of involving communities in decision-making procedures, guaranteeing that their opinions are heard in the development and application of sustainable practices. Upcycling projects and local recycling programs are examples of community-based initiatives that can enable locals to actively participate in waste reduction and environmental improvement. These programs support the local economy and advance environmental justice, fostering a cycle of sustainability, economic opportunity, and empowerment.

4.3. Environmental Outcomes

Circular manufacturing reduces environmental impact by conserving resources, lowering greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, reducing pollution and conserving resources. It requires collaboration between stakeholders, including governments, businesses, and consumers, to ensure effective implementation. Below are some key environmental outcomes from circular manufacturing, supported by case studies, as described in **Table 3**.

As demonstrated by these case studies, companies integrating circular practices experience environmental, economic, and reputational benefits. In the long term, scaling circular manufacturing could transform industries and significantly reduce the environmental pressures of traditional linear manufacturing systems. Practices such as recycling construction materials and reusing wastewater in industrial processes contribute to lower emissions and improved resource efficiency (Siderius & Zink, 2022; Tukker et al, 2023).

5. POLICY FRAMEWORKS AND GOVERNANCE MECHANISMS

Global economic dynamics have an impact on the evolution of manufacturing, which is fuelled by sophisticated machinery and intricate procedures. These days, to create “smart” and advanced products, they use interoperable digital technologies like artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, and robotics. As a result, these jobs now demand higher skill levels, which will pay more but lead to new fields. By comprehending these changes in manufacturing, nations can develop their own capacity for innovation and sector specializations for new development opportunities. They will gain from economic expansion and high worker wages if they do this.

Table 2: Selected Case Studies on Social Impact from Circular Manufacturing

1. Job Creation and Workforce Development
<p>Case Study: Renault's Refactory in Flins, France. https://www.renaultgroup.com/en/our-company/locations/refactory-flins-2/</p> <p>Renault established the Refactory to integrate circular economy practices, including remanufacturing car parts, recycling materials, and repurposing electric vehicle batteries.</p> <p>Impact: Generates employment in repair, recycling, and remanufacturing industries. It also provides opportunities for skill enhancement in sustainable practices.</p> <p>Social Outcomes: (i) Created new jobs in specialized fields, with a projection of employing 3,000 workers by 2030. (ii) Training programs enhance workers' expertise in advanced technologies like battery refurbishment and sustainable mobility solutions. (iii) Partnerships with local educational institutions support workforce development.</p>
2. Community Empowerment
<p>Case Study: Interface's Net-Works Program https://eom.org/oxford-case-studies/interface-inc/</p> <p>Interface collaborates with coastal communities to collect discarded fishing nets, recycling them into carpet tiles.</p> <p>Impact: Engage local communities in sustainable practices, improving economic stability and collective environmental stewardship.</p> <p>Social Outcomes: (i) Provided supplemental income to over 2,200 households. (ii) Empowered communities to clean up coastal areas, enhancing health and tourism. (iii) Encouraged the adoption of sustainable business models within the community.</p>
3. Equitable Access to Resources
<p>Case Study: Fairphone – Ethical Electronics https://www.fairphone.com/en/impact/fair-materials/</p> <p>Fairphone designs modular smartphones for easy repair and longer lifespans.</p> <p>Impact: Makes refurbished and recycled products more affordable, promoting equity in resource access.</p> <p>Social Outcomes: (i) Increased affordability of sustainable technology, promoting accessibility. (ii) Supported ethical supply chains by sourcing conflict-free materials and fair labor practices. (iii) Raised consumer awareness of the social and environmental costs of electronics production.</p>
4. Health Improvements
<p>Case Study: Apple's Daisy Robot for E-Waste Recycling https://www.apple.com/sg/newsroom/2019/04/apple-expands-global-recycling-programs/</p> <p>Apple uses robots to disassemble devices and recover valuable materials, minimizing e-waste.</p> <p>Impact: Proper waste management through circular practices reduces exposure to harmful substances in vulnerable communities.</p> <p>Social Outcomes: (i) Reduced health risks associated with informal recycling methods involving toxic exposure. (ii) Improved urban living conditions, especially in regions disproportionately affected by e-waste. (iii) Set higher safety standards for global recycling practices.</p>
5. Fostering Sustainability Awareness
<p>Case Study: Patagonia's Worn Wear Program. https://wornwear.patagonia.com/</p> <p>Techniques include combining multiple wet-cycle processes, using ozone gas, and recycling water.</p> <p>Impact: Influences consumer and societal behaviour toward sustainable lifestyles.</p> <p>Economic Impact: (i) Promoted a culture of reuse and repair, challenging fast-fashion norms. (ii) Engaged communities through workshops and events on sustainable consumption. (iii) Created networks of environmentally conscious consumers and advocates.</p>
6. Reduction in Social Inequalities
<p>Case Study: Waste-to-Wealth Initiative in Accra, Ghana https://thevaultzafrica.com/investment-world/waste-to-wealth-exploring-opportunities-in-ghanas-recycling-industry/</p> <p>An UN-backed project trains informal waste collectors to process plastic waste into marketable materials.</p> <p>Impact: Circular initiatives often involve partnerships with underserved communities, creating economic opportunities and reducing disparities.</p> <p>Social Outcomes: (i) Improved livelihoods for waste pickers through stable incomes. (ii) Reduced waste in urban areas, leading to healthier living conditions. (iii) Fostered collaboration between local governments, businesses, and communities.</p>

Source: Author's own.

Table 3: Selected Case Studies on Environmental Outcomes from Circular Manufacturing

1. Reduction in Resource Extraction
<p>Case Study: Renault’s Closed-Loop Automotive Manufacturing. https://www.renaultgroup.com/en/news-on-air/news/circular-economy-what-if-cars-were-to-become-our-main-resource/</p> <p>Process: Renault’s Choisy-le-Roi plant specializes in remanufacturing engines, gearboxes, and injection pumps using reclaimed materials.</p> <p>Impact: The facility recycles 43% of vehicle parts by weight and uses 80% less energy and 88% less water compared to manufacturing new parts.</p> <p>Environmental Benefits: Reduced raw material extraction and significantly lower carbon emissions.</p>
2. Decreased Waste Generation
<p>Case Study: Interface’s Carpet Recycling Program. https://www.interface.com/US/en-US/sustainability/recycling.html</p> <p>Process: The company uses old carpets to produce new ones through its ReEntry recycling program. Nylon fibres are extracted, and the backing material is processed for reuse.</p> <p>Impact: Since the program began, Interface has diverted over 350 million pounds of carpet from landfills.</p> <p>Environmental Benefits: Reduction in landfill waste, conservation of natural resources, and decreased lifecycle emissions.</p>
3. Lowered Greenhouse Gas Emissions
<p>Case Study: Patagonia’s Worn Wear Initiative. https://wornwear.patagonia.com/</p> <p>Process: Customers can trade in old gear, which is then repaired and resold or recycled into new products.</p> <p>Impact: Over 100,000 garments have been repaired, significantly lowering demand for new raw materials and production energy.</p> <p>Environmental Benefits: Reduced carbon footprint due to lower production energy requirements and extended product lifecycle.</p>
4. Prevention of Toxic Emissions and Pollution
<p>Case Study: Apple’s Recycling Robots – Daisy and Liam. https://www.apple.com/sg/newsroom/2018/04/apple-adds-earth-day-donations-to-trade-in-and-recycling-program/</p> <p>Process: These robots can disassemble 200 iPhones per hour, recovering materials like gold, silver, aluminium, and cobalt without releasing toxins into the environment.</p> <p>Impact: Apple reduced mining activities for rare earth metals, which are often associated with toxic emissions and environmental degradation.</p> <p>Environmental Benefits: Prevented environmental pollution from improper e-waste disposal and reduced mining-related emissions.</p>
5. Conservation of Water and Energy Resources
<p>Case Study: Levi Strauss’s Water<Less® Program https://www.levistrauss.com/2019/03/25/world-water-day-2019-saving-h2o/</p> <p>Process: Techniques include combining multiple wet-cycle processes, using ozone gas, and recycling water.</p> <p>Impact: Since 2011, Levi’s has saved over 4.2 billion litres of water and reused 9.6 billion litres in its manufacturing.</p> <p>Environmental Benefits: Conservation of freshwater resources and reduced water pollution from dyeing processes.</p>
6. Biodiversity Preservation
<p>Case Study: IKEA’s Sustainable Forestry Practices https://www.ikea.com/global/en/our-business/sustainability/ikea-forest-positive-agenda/</p> <p>Process: The company works with the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) to ensure sustainable forestry and uses wood waste in furniture production.</p> <p>Impact: In 2020, IKEA achieved 98% sustainability in its wood supply chain, including recycled content.</p> <p>Environmental Benefits: Reduced deforestation, preservation of habitats, and enhanced carbon sequestration.</p>
7. Reduction of End-of-Life Environmental Impact
<p>Case Study: The Ellen MacArthur Foundation’s Circular Economy Pilot Projects. https://circulareconomy.europa.eu/platform/sites/default/files/knowledge_-_circular_business_models_for_the_environment.pdf</p> <p>Process: A pilot project in Amsterdam reused construction and demolition waste for building new structures.</p> <p>Impact: Reduced landfill waste and conserved raw materials.</p> <p>Environmental Benefits: Lower lifecycle emissions and minimized environmental disruption from construction waste.</p>

Source: Author’s own.

In addition, comprehensive legislative and regulatory frameworks are required in order to successfully combine environmental justice, economic growth, and circular manufacturing. By establishing unambiguous sustainability standards and offering incentives to companies that implement circular practices, governments can play a crucial role. Companies may be encouraged to design products with reuse and recyclability in mind by policies like extended producer responsibility (EPR) laws, which mandate that manufacturers assume responsibility for the full lifecycle of their products, including post-consumer waste (UNIDO, 2024).

Furthermore, the creation of green public procurement regulations can encourage businesses to embrace circular practices by increasing demand for products made sustainably. By funding the required infrastructure, such as recycling centres, repair hubs, and reverse logistics systems, governments can also help facilitate the shift to a circular economy.

Regulations must guarantee that the advantages of circular manufacturing are shared fairly in order to uphold environmental justice. This entails giving disadvantaged communities access to the economic opportunities brought about by the circular economy in addition to shielding them from the detrimental effects of industrial activity. For instance, governments can stimulate economic growth and create jobs in historically underserved communities by focusing investments on green industries in underserved areas.

5.1. International Policies Supporting Circular Manufacturing

Global climate agreements like the Paris Agreement and international frameworks like the EU Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) are essential for promoting circular manufacturing. As a component of the European Green Deal, the EU CEAP places a strong emphasis on resource reuse, waste reduction, and sustainable product design within the EU economy. It suggests legislative measures for sustainable product policy while focusing on high-impact industries like textiles, electronics, and plastics. In order to coordinate global efforts, this action plan also seeks to lower material consumption and advance a “Global Circular Economy Alliance.”

In a similar vein, circularity in industrial practices is promoted by the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 12 on responsible consumption and production. These frameworks guarantee worldwide agreement on resource efficiency by offering direction for incorporating sustainability into economic policies (EC, 2023).

5.1.1. Legal Instruments for Promoting Environmental Justice

In order to achieve environmental justice, legal mechanisms that address industrial externalities are essential. While rights-based strategies place a higher priority on fair resource distribution and shield marginalized communities from disproportionate environmental harms, regulations such as the EU’s Industrial Emissions Directive place limits on pollutants from manufacturing activities. Many nations, for instance, have enacted environmental justice laws to guarantee community involvement in decision-making processes and to enforce equitable industrial facility siting (EC, 2023).

A number of important laws and directives have been established by the European Union (EU) with the goal of advancing justice and environmental protection. These laws set the stage for policies that strike a balance between social justice and environmental concerns, preventing vulnerable communities from suffering disproportionately from environmental harm. Some of the core legal instruments include:

I. The European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) and Environmental Rights

An important legal framework that promotes environmental justice is the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), which was ratified by the Council of Europe. Although environmental concerns are not specifically addressed by the convention, the ECHR has interpreted it as falling under the purview of human rights. Notably, the right to a healthy environment has been construed as part of Article 8 of the ECHR, which protects the right to respect for private and family life. This has resulted in historic decisions in support of citizens who contend that environmental degradation jeopardizes their livelihoods or health.

II. The Aarhus Convention

One of the most important international agreements on environmental justice in Europe is the Aarhus Convention,¹ which is officially known as the “Convention on Access to Information, Public Participation in Decision-making and Access to Justice in Environmental Matters.” The convention, which was adopted in Aarhus, Denmark, in 1998, aims to empower citizens by giving them the right to access environmental information, take part in environmental decision-making, and seek justice when their rights are infringed.

Because it promotes accountability, transparency, and participation in environmental governance, the Aarhus Convention is essential to environmental justice. The convention states unequivocally that the rights of people to participate in public life and to pursue legal recourse are intimately related to environmental protection. Its three pillars—access to information, public participation, and access to justice—are foundational in ensuring that vulnerable groups are not excluded from decisions that directly affect their environment and health.

III. The EU’s Environmental Justice Mechanism

Through its institutional framework, the EU has further developed policies to promote environmental justice. During the 2014–2020 timeframe, the EU’s 7th Environmental Action Programme² (EAP) established a clear vision for “living well, within the limits of the planet.” This initiative combined social justice and sustainability, advocating for improved safeguards for marginalized communities that are disproportionately affected by environmental damage.

The EU Green Deal,³ another component of the EU framework, intends to change the EU economy in order to attain climate neutrality by 2050. In order to guarantee that no community is left behind during the shift to a low-carbon economy, the Green Deal places a high priority on “just transition” policies. This involves support for regions and communities that may face economic hardship as a result of shifting industries, such as those dependent on fossil fuels or traditional manufacturing.

IV. The EU’s Environmental Liability Directive (ELD)

The EU adopted the Environmental Liability Directive (2004/35/EC),⁴ which establishes the “polluter pays” basis for environmental liability. According to this directive, companies and other organizations that cause environmental harm must pay for its repair, especially when land, water,

1 Original document: <https://unece.org/DAM/env/pp/documents/cep43e.pdf>. The Aarhus Convention as a tool for enhancing the role of the public in tackling climate change https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/aarhus_convention.pdf?download

2 7th Environment Action Programme <https://www.eea.europa.eu/policy-documents/7th-environmental-action-programme>

3 The European Green Deal: Striving to be the first climate-neutral continent https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

4 Directive 2004/35/CE of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 April 2004 on environmental liability with regard to the prevention and remedying of environmental damage <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32004L0035>

and biodiversity are contaminated. By giving citizens and communities the ability to sue for damages, the directive establishes an accountability framework that helps shield vulnerable populations from bearing an unfair share of the costs associated with industrial activity's environmental effects.

In addition to offering a way for impacted people or communities to request compensation for damages, the directive seeks to serve as an effective deterrent against environmental harm. It has the potential to be a powerful tool for achieving environmental justice in cases where disadvantaged communities are exposed to environmental risks due to industrial operations or government negligence.

5.2. National and Local Governance Strategies

Governments, both national and local, are crucial in encouraging circular practices. Policies include tax breaks for recycling programs, subsidies for companies implementing circular business models, and public procurement guidelines that give preference to sustainable goods. These initiatives are strengthened when the public and private sectors work together. For example, the EU promotes innovation by supporting projects that aim to achieve circularity through funding mechanisms such as the LIFE Programme and the European Regional Development Fund (EC, 2023; EEA, 2024).

Many European nations have created their own national laws and regulations to advance the objectives of environmental justice, even though the EU offers broad frameworks for environmental protection and justice. These laws are frequently more focused on particular issues impacting local communities and serve as a supplement to EU directives.

I. Environmental Justice in the UK: The Environmental Protection Act

Environmental justice has long been acknowledged in the UK, especially with the passage of the Environmental Protection Act of 1990. This Act established policies to control waste, prevent pollution, and guarantee that industrial operations follow environmental safety regulations. The Act has been especially helpful in tackling problems that disproportionately impact impoverished communities, like contamination, waste management, and air pollution.

Furthermore, the necessity of taking environmental justice into account in the framework of social equity has been emphasized by the UK's Equality Act (2010).⁵ The Act encourages equity and inclusivity in environmental decision-making processes by requiring public bodies to consider how environmental policies may affect vulnerable and marginalized groups.

II. Environmental Justice in Germany: The German Federal Environmental Agency

The work of Germany's Federal Environmental Agency (UBA),⁶ which is essential to making sure the nation's environmental policies support social justice and sustainability, serves as the foundation for the country's approach to environmental justice. Equal access to environmental benefits and safeguarding underprivileged communities from environmental harm are two aspects of the UBA's environmental justice focus. The nation's Energy Transition (Energiewende),⁷ which aims to lessen dependency on fossil fuels while making sure that the switch to renewable energy doesn't negatively affect vulnerable communities, is one noteworthy example. Furthermore, Germany's focus on community-based environmental monitoring, citizen participation, and guaranteeing fair access to clean air, water, and green energy has strengthened the country's incorporation of environmental

⁵ UK's Equality Act 2010 <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2010/15/contents>

⁶ German Environment Agency (UBA) <https://www.bmu.de/en/ministry/tasks-and-structure/federal-and-laender-authorities/german-environment-agency-uba>

⁷ Germany's Energiewende – The Easy Guide <https://www.cleanenergywire.org/easyguide>

justice principles into its policies.

Environmental justice is also being incorporated more and more into corporate law as part of the larger European legal system, where companies are expected to disclose their environmental effects and accept accountability for how their operations affect marginalized communities. This legal obligation is expanding in light of corporate social responsibility (CSR) and environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards.

Companies are now required to disclose their environmental and social impacts, especially with regard to marginalized communities, under strict EU regulations such as the Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR)⁸ and the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD).⁹ Companies are held responsible for their part in causing or reducing environmental injustice thanks to these legal frameworks.

6. CHALLENGES AND BARRIERS

There are several obstacles in the way of the shift to circular manufacturing, chiefly social, political, and economic. The initial expense of switching to circular systems is a major obstacle. When implementing new technologies or rethinking their production processes, many businesses encounter financial challenges, particularly in sectors that mainly rely on conventional linear models. Long-term cost savings may be possible with circular manufacturing, but the initial outlay needed to redesign products, acquire new technologies, and establish new supply chains may be a turnoff. Significant economic barriers are created by high upfront costs for new technologies, less expensive alternatives from linear supply chains, and a lack of consumer demand for circular products. Organizational resistance to circular principles, which are frequently marginalized by conventional business models, gives rise to social challenges. Politically, inconsistent regulations and lack of global cooperation on circular strategies further hinder widespread adoption, keeping industries locked into linear systems (EEA, 2024).

Additionally, recycling and material recovery present technical difficulties. Many products contain hazardous materials that are challenging to process in a circular system, or they are made with limited capacity for recycling. Innovation in product design and investments in cutting-edge recycling infrastructure and technologies are needed to meet these challenges. Even though technology is developing, there are still big gaps in infrastructure, scalability, and circular design. Lack of recycling facilities, restricted availability of circular products, and difficulties setting up cross-border material recycling systems are some of the main obstacles. Due to these constraints, companies find it challenging to implement circular manufacturing models on a large scale (EEA, 2024).

The requirement for systemic change presents another difficulty. Communities, governments, and industries must work together to transition from a linear to a circular economy. Legislators must establish regulatory frameworks that encourage circular practices and guarantee that companies follow environmental justice standards. This entails giving tax breaks or subsidies to businesses that use circular manufacturing techniques and making sure that these methods don't unfairly disadvantage marginalized communities. Businesses' short-term financial demands frequently clash with the long-term expenditures necessary for a circular transition. Because of the perceived high risks and unpredictable returns, businesses that prioritize short-term profitability are reluctant to adopt circular strategies. The broad adoption of circular practices in most countries is hampered by this conflict between sustainability and profitability (EEA, 2024).

⁸ Sustainability-related disclosure in the financial services sector https://finance.ec.europa.eu/sustainable-finance/disclosures/sustainability-related-disclosure-financial-services-sector_en

⁹ Non-financial Reporting Directive [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/654213/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)654213_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/654213/EPRS_BRI(2021)654213_EN.pdf)

7. PATHWAYS TO HARMONIZATION

Prioritizing circular economy principles—which promote resource efficiency and waste reduction—is a crucial tactic in combining economic, social, and environmental objectives for a sustainable manufacturing transition.

Collaboration between stakeholders is essential to the transition’s success. In order to align policies that support environmental justice and circular manufacturing, governments, corporations, and communities must have ongoing conversations. Incorporating sustainability into corporate operations can promote equitable economic growth while preventing disadvantaged populations from bearing an unfair share of the costs associated with industrial externalities. Putting money into education and innovation will help the economy shift to a circular economy by giving workers the skills they need for new green jobs (ERM, 2024). In order to balance short-term growth with long-term sustainability, stakeholders can address the challenges presented by the transition through thoughtful policy frameworks and equitable supply chain design. By fostering innovation through sustainable practices, circular manufacturing can unleash substantial growth potential. These practices not only increase competitiveness but also generate employment in a variety of industries. Businesses can support environmental and economic sustainability by emphasizing material recycling, resource reuse, and production waste reduction. Additionally, it is believed that circular economy principles are essential to achieving global climate goals and sustainable development objectives (Think2030, 2024; ERM, 2024).

8. CONCLUSION

Through the promotion of innovation, resource efficiency, and decreased waste generation, the circular economy provides a revolutionary means of accomplishing these goals. However, equity must be at the heart of governance structures and policy design for circular practices to be in line with environmental justice, guaranteeing that underserved communities have access to green jobs and cleaner production systems.

Coordinated international and local efforts are needed to align the circular economy with environmental justice and economic growth. To guarantee that no community is left behind during the transition, policymakers and corporations must embrace strategies that prioritize social equity in addition to economic efficiency. Designing circular manufacturing systems should be based on environmental justice, which addresses current disparities in pollution exposure, resource access, and waste burdens.

Strong policy frameworks, cutting-edge technologies, and stakeholder collaboration are necessary to achieve this balance, as the research has demonstrated, but there are also many obstacles to overcome. These include the need for systemic change in industries, technological gaps, and balancing long-term sustainability objectives with immediate economic pressures. Future studies should investigate how the concepts of the circular economy can be applied to a variety of sectors and geographical areas, especially in developing nations, and how advancements in green technologies and materials science can further lessen the negative environmental effects of manufacturing (Deutz, 2023). Future research could also concentrate on examining the social aspects of circular economies, specifically with relation to equitable distribution of the advantages of sustainability shifts.

Promoting cross-sector cooperation and making sure policies are inclusive are essential for continued policy improvement and sustainable development. These initiatives ought to be in line with international frameworks that prioritize fair, sustainable growth across sectors, like the Paris Climate Agreement and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Schröder and Barrie, 2024).

Declarations

The authors have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

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